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Abstract

As part of this report, a literature survey was conducted on the current State of the art in autonomous technologies and existing roadmaps in the mining industry. The review includes a detailed description of chosen technologies along with an assessment of their strengths and weaknesses and includes determining the prospects for their further development. The analysis also determined the applicability of individual technologies for the reactivation of abandoned and suspended mining projects and described the current status and development directions of geomodels, with an emphasis on digital twins. Finally, a review of regulatory requirements in EU countries was assessed with a view to developing technologies that are in line with the current legislation of individual countries.

History of Changes

Version	Date	Reason of change
0.9 (draft)	9 May 2024	The initial draft of the document was distributed between PERSEPHONE project partners to review.
1.0	17 May 2024	The first version of the document sent for revision to all PERSEPHONE project partners
1.1	24 May 2024	The second, revised version of the document after taking into account the comments and remarks of the PERSEPHONE project partners
1.2	31 May 2024	The final, submitted version of document revised by all PERSEPHONE project partners.

Executive summary

The PERSEPHONE project aims to develop pioneering technologies for sustainable mining practices in support of the EU's Green Deal and the Critical Raw Materials Act. PERSEPHONE aims to drive the green transition by minimising costs and waste in deep-mining operations, while also targeting zero human presence in high-risk zones. This involves developing energy-efficient autonomous drilling machines with advanced perception capabilities for navigation, face drilling, and core extraction. These innovations will enable the creation of data-driven digital twins and geological models, enhancing decision support and optimising extraction planning.

Within PERSEPHONE there are opportunities to further research and develop autonomous technologies for exploration and extraction in deep mines, abandoned and suspended mining projects.

In this document are analysed from a literature review standpoint the methods with technical, technological and theoretical background that describe the current SoA in the mining industry for exploration and production, including SoA autonomy practices. In addition, a general outlook on sustainability in mining, with referment to SoA technologies to reuse waste/secondary materials generated as a result of current mining methodologies can be found in this document. Furthermore, an overview of the existing deep mining exploration and extraction-related mining roadmaps, and review of regulatory requirements in the EU, with national examples are also given. Finally, the strategies for comprehensive digital modelling and digital twin data integration are highlighted.

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1. Abbreviations

3D	Three dimensional
AE	Acoustic emission
AFMAG	Audio frequency magnetic
AI	Artificial intelligence
ANFIS	Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
ANRM	National Agency for Mineral Resources (Romania)
APA	Portuguese Environment Agency
APR	Adjusted penetration rate
AR	Augmented reality
ASM	Artisanal and small-scale mining
AUSLAMP	Australian Lithospheric Architecture Magneto-telluric Project
AWG	Federal Waste Management Act (Austria)
BBERGG	Federal Mining Act (Germany)
BREF	Best Available Techniques Reference Documents
BSUIN	Baltic Sea Underground Innovation Network
CBS	Conflict-Based Search
CCDR	Regional Coordination and Development Commissions (Portugal)
CEU	Council of the European Union
CHPM2030	Combined Heat, Power and Metal - project
CIRAN	Critical Raw materials extraction in environmentally protected areas - project
CLP	Classification, labelling and packaging
CRMS	Critical Raw Materials
CSAMT	Controlled source audio-frequency magneto-telluric
C-SLAM	Collaborative Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
CUP	KGHM CUPRUM Ltd. R&D Centre
D&B	Drilling and blasting
DARPA	Defence Advanced Research Projects Agency
DC	Direct current
DEA	Danish Environment Agency
DEM	Discrete Element Method
DGEG	Directorate General for Energy and Geology (Portugal)
DHF	Directional hydraulic fracturing
DP	Dump pressure
DREAL	Regional Directorate for the Environment, Development and Housing (France)
DTU	Technical University of Denmark
EEC	European Economic Community
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EIT	European Institute of Innovation & Technology

EM	Electromagnetic
EMS	Electromagnetic spectre
EMD	Exploration and Mining Division (Ireland)
EPI	EPIROC ROCK DRILLS AB
ERP	Event-related potential
ERT	Electrical Resistivity Tomography
ESG	Environmental, Societal and Governance
ETS	European Emissions Trading System
EU	European Union
EWD	Extractive Waste Directive
EY	Ernst & Young
FDEM	Finite-Discrete Element Method
FEM	Finite Element Method
FOG	Fibre optic gyroscope
FP	Feed pressure
GBPP	Ground-Based Pilot Plant
GM	Grecian Magnesite Mining Industrial Shipping and Commercial Company Societe Anonyme
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPR	Ground-penetrating radar
GPS	Global Positioning System
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
GSB	Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
GTR	Global Tailings Review
HDMS	Hole deviation measurement system
HF	Hydraulic fracturing
HP	Hammer pressure
HRO	High Reliability Organisation
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
ICMM	International Council on Mining and Metals
IEA	International Energy Agency
IED	Industrial Emissions Directive
IGME	Spanish Geological and Mining Institute
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
INTRAW	International Raw Materials Observatory AISBL
IOT	Internet of Things
IP	Induced polarization
IPPC	Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control
IRMA	Initiative for Responsible Mining Assurance
ISRU	In-Situ Resource Utilization
ISURE	Intelligent Sandvik Underground Rock Excavation software
ITM	Inspectorate of Labour and Mines (Luxembourg)

KGHM	KGHM POLSKA MIEDZ SA
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LAMT	Lithospheric Architecture Magneto-telluric
LIBS	Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LNS	Large Neighbourhood Search
LOAM	Lidar Odometry and Mapping
LOW	List of Waste
LPMT	Long Period Magneto-telluric
LPRC	La Palma Research Centre SL
LTS	Long-term stewardship
LTU	Luleå University of Technology
LWD	Logging while drilling
MAPF	Multi-Agent Path Finding
MAV	Micro Aerial Vehicle
MBFSZ	Mining and Geological Survey of Hungary
MEMS	Micro-Electro-Mechanical System
MI	Magnetic induction
MITECO	Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge (Spain)
MRP	MineRP South Africa (PTY) LTD
MRS	Multi-Robot System
MT	Magneto-telluric
MTECT	Ministry of the Ecological Transition and Territorial Cohesion (France)
MWD	Measurement while drilling
MWEI-BREF	Best Available Techniques Reference Document for the Management of Waste from Extractive Industries
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NBV	Next Best View
NEPA	National Environmental Protection Agency (Romania)
NEXGEN SIMS	Next Generation Sustainable Intelligent Mining Systems – project
NIMBY	Not In My Back Yard
NLOS	Non-Line of Sight
NORM	Naturally occurring radioactive materials
OSH	Occupational Safety and Health
PER	Exclusive research permit (France)
PESTEL	Political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal
PLGRIM	Probabilistic Local and Global Reasoning on Information Road Maps
PR	Penetration rate
PU	Public
P-WAVE	Primary wave (compression wave)

REACH	Registration, evaluation, authorisation and restriction of chemicals
REE	Rare-earth element
RES	Renewable energy
RF	Radio frequency
RMI	Responsible Mining Index
RMIS	Raw Materials Information System
ROHS	Restrictions of Hazardous Substances
ROS	Robot Operating System
RP	Rotation pressure
RQD	Rock Quality Designation
RQI	Rock Quality Index
RRSMT	Remote reference soundings magneto-telluric
RRT	Rapidly-Exploring Random Trees
RS	Rotary speed
RSDSS	Rotary Steerable Drilling Systems
SBC	Single Boards Computer
SDAGE	Schema Water Supply and Management Managers (France)
SDE	Stochastic Differential Equations
SEA	Single European Act
SED	Specific energy of drilling
SEIA	Strategic Environmental Impact Assessment
SEM	Modulated specific energy
SEPA	Swedish Environmental Protection Agency
SH-WAVE	Secondary horizontal wave
SIMS	Sustainable Intelligent Mining Systems – project
SL	Sound level
SLAM	Simultaneous localization and mapping
SLO	Social license to operate
SMA	State Mining Administration
SOA	State-of-the-art
SOTA	State-of-the-art
SP	Self-potential
SPE	SPECTRAL INDUSTRIES BV
SUBT	Subterrain
SV-WAVE	Secondary vertical wave
S-WAVE	Secondary wave (share wave)
T	Torque
TOP	Technical operation plan
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UCS	Uniaxial compressive strength
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe

US	The United States
US EPA	United States Environmental Protection Agency
UVP-G	Federal Environmental Impact Assessment Act (Austria)
VERAM	Vision and Roadmap for European Raw Materials - project
VR	Virtual reality
WF	Water flow
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WOB	Weight on bit (thrust)
WP	Work package
WP	Water pressure
WRG	Water resources act (Austria)
YPEN	Ministry of Environment and Energy (Greece)
ZTEM	Z-Axis Tipper Electromagnetic

2. Introduction

2.1. Objectives of the PERSEPHONE Project

PERSEPHONE aims to develop new pioneering technologies for sustainable mining practices to assist the EU mining industry in reaching the goals for the latest Green Deal and supporting the future outcomes of the Critical Raw Materials Act.

The project vision and concept include the:

- a) size reduction of the mining machine,
- b) the creation of a digital twin in support of autonomy for risk-aware navigation and full digitalisation of the extraction process,
- c) key enabling technologies at TRL5,
- d) novel approaches in online near-mine exploration core analysis,
- e) integration of data analytics for mine expansion.

PERSEPHONE aims to drive the green transition by minimising costs and waste in deep-mining operations, while also targeting zero human presence in high-risk zones. This involves developing energy-efficient autonomous drilling machines with advanced perception capabilities for navigation, face drilling, and core extraction. These innovations will enable the creation of data-driven digital twins and geological models, enhancing decision support and optimising extraction planning.

2.2. Scope and Structure of Work Package 1

These various aspects are therefore taken into consideration in this document, where, as part of WP1, we describe the state-of-the-art (SoA) and the current capabilities and technologies in the mining industry that will be developed during this project. As represented in Figure 2.1, the PERSEPHONE project consists of thirteen work packages. The aim of Work Package 1 “Specification and requirements for enabling sustainable deep mining” is to define and conceptualise the project’s needs, operations and sustainable mining practices, ensuring the operational demands from end-users, and finally defining measurable benchmarking specifications. WP1 aims to be a platform of discussion and meeting with partners from different disciplines otherwise isolated.

Work Package 1 includes 6 tasks. Task 1.1 is dedicated to a literature review of deep mining state-of-the-art (SoA) technologies, existing roadmaps and related applications. Task 1.2. investigate the end-user requirements for exploration and extraction of deep and hard-to-reach deposits, while task 1.3. considers the end-user requirements for the exploration and reactivation of abandoned and suspended mines. Task 1.4 analyses the framework conditions for alignment with the UNFC and UNRMS. In task 1.5. the scenarios are evaluated and consequently defined as the benchmark specifications. In task 1.6. are defined the data requirements for the geomodels development. All literature reviews and regulations considered in all WP1 tasks are included in this deliverable (D1.1 Literature survey on SoA technologies and existing roadmaps in the mining industry).

Figure 2.1. PERSEPHONE activities and interactions

Further information on the technologies that will be developed during the project, including measurable benchmarking specifications and the overall impact can be found in D1.2 Requirements, specifications and benchmarking tools for proposed technologies.

2.3. Structure of This Deliverable and Relation to Future Work

This deliverable provides input for the design and development of new innovative technologies capable of addressing the challenges in deep mining operations, the integration of exploration with other aspects of operation and development, and the development of in-situ real-time analysis and digital twin deposits for informed exploration.

In this document, the reader will find a literature review on

- **Technical and theoretical background:** the methods with technical, technological and theoretical background that describe the current SoA in the mining industry for exploration and production, including SoA autonomy practices,
- **Mining roadmaps:** an overview of the existing deep mining exploration and extraction-related mining roadmaps,
- **Sustainable mining:** SoA technologies to reuse waste/secondary materials generated as a result of current mining methodologies,
- **Digital twin data integration:** strategies for comprehensive digital modelling,
- **Regulatory review:** a review of regulatory requirements in EU, with national examples.

In detail, Deliverable 1.1 is structured in ten chapters.

In Chapter 1, an executive summary of this deliverable is provided.

Chapter 2 is an introductory part. Here, the objectives of the PERSEPHONE project are outlined, as well as the structure of Work Package 1, where this deliverable was prepared.

Chapter 3 is the main review chapter for the SoA technologies in deep mining and deep deposit exploration. In this chapter are considered exploration techniques (geophysics and geochemistry), production technology from the mining industry, and current autonomy practices.

Chapter 4 includes a review of the existing roadmaps in deep mining.

Chapter 5 is dedicated to current applications in abandoned and suspended mine projects.

Chapter 6 reviews the concept of sustainability in mining, with a short focus on the reuse of waste and secondary materials in the current mining industry.

Chapter 7 describes the fundamentals for the geomodel development and digitalisation.

Chapter 8 provides an extensive review of regulatory requirements in the EU, with a detailed description of legislation and policies in the EU's member states in Annex 1.

Chapter 9 is a synthesis of the outcomes from the former chapters.

In Chapter 10 a list of references used to prepare the recent study is provided.

2.4. Related Documents

D1.2. - Requirements, specifications and benchmarking tools for proposed technologies

3. State-of-the-Art Technologies in Deep Mining and Deep-deposit Exploration

The increased demand for raw materials in the EU directs the mining companies to operate at greater depth. This trend creates new challenges for mining operations in terms of profitability, safety and sustainability. Thus, there is a need to develop new innovative technologies capable of addressing these challenges. The PERSEPHONE project aims to develop new autonomous technologies that increase the possibilities of exploration and extraction in deep mines as well as abandoned and suspended mining projects. Conducting a detailed literature review of the current State of the Art in the field of these technologies is the basis for constructive planning of further development based on the international experience gathered so far.

3.1. Deep-deposit Exploration Methods and Tools

Although this project investigates new technologies for deep deposit exploration in active and abandoned mines, new insights will also be useful in automated mining for newly developed mines. As such, this chapter also includes deep exploration methods. In this section, an overview of the main methods for deep exploration is given, with a short physical background of these techniques. For each method, there is a wide variety of applications, often with only small adaptations. In the first part, the general physical principles of the exploration methods will be explained, with some recent advancements. The second part will be focused on new applications, explained with some examples.

In this chapter will be discussed methods that are directly connected to PERSEPHONE. Figure 3.1 gives an overview of different shallow and deep exploration techniques, with the characteristic wavelengths used for each technique. For reference, the figure also presents the range of the visible span within the electromagnetic spectre (EMS).

Figure 3.1. Frequency bands used by various geophysical methods within EMS (Dentith & Mudge 2014).

3.1.1. Gravity measurements

The gravity method is based on anomalies in the density within the Earth. To determine these anomalies the observed gravity measurement has to be corrected for several factors: the tide effect, the instrumental drift and the Eötvös effect. The amplitude of the tide effect will vary as a function of the relative position of the moon and the sun to each other and is also dependent on the latitude and longitude. The maximum gravity effect of the tides is 0.3 mGal. Instrumental drift is a gradual and unintentional change in measured values due to small changes in the properties of the material of the measurement instrument. The drift can be determined by measuring the same site several times. Gravimeters can drift as much as 0.1 mGal per day. Gravity Notes: Instrument Drift (Sheriff, 2002). The Eötvös correction only has to be applied whenever measurements are carried out from a ship or an airplane. The Earth's force of attraction is decreased by the centrifugal force of the Earth. Because the angular speed of a body going to the east is larger than the angular speed of a stationary body, the gravity acceleration decreases when a vessel is going east and increases when it goes west.

To calculate the gravitational anomalies useful for geological interpretations, the gravity anomalies after these corrections are further processed by subtracting a regional field from the measured field. Several corrections, such as the free air correction, Bouguer correction and terrain correction have to be carried out. In mountainous regions also an isostatic correction could be necessary (Everaert, 2012).

The result in gravitational anomalies correlates with density variations of the source body. Positive gravity anomalies are associated with high-density bodies, such as igneous and metamorphic rocks, but also deposits with chromite, hematite or barite. Negative anomalies are associated with low-density bodies, such as sedimentary rocks, deposits with halite, coal seams, or weathered deposits (Adewuyi et al., 2019; Hoover et al., 1992).

3.1.2. Magnetotelluric measurements

The Magnetotelluric method (MT) is a passive technique that uses variations in the Earth's magnetic field and induced telluric currents to investigate the electrical resistivity structure of the subsurface. These variations and currents are associated with lightning storms and the interaction of the Earth's magnetic field with the sun's solar winds (Aboud et al., 2014). The ratios of the orthogonal components of the magnetic and electric fields can be expressed as an impedance tensor, which can be used to calculate the penetration of the fields into the Earth. The MT responses are sensitive to the dimensions and direction of the subsurface structure. Solving for the resistivity and thickness of the layers is often complicated, using inversion algorithms, often requiring iterative calculations and high computational power. As such a variety of algorithms have been developed, each with its own merits.

A variety of different passive MT surveying techniques are available which can be used for shallow depths of tens of meters up to deep depths, up to 100 kilometres, depending on the used technique. With increasing depth, there is an exponential decrease in the amplitudes of the electromagnetic fields termed the skin-depth phenomenon (Lindsay, 2020). The depth of penetration is directly related to

frequency and the resistivity with greater depths for lower frequencies and higher resistivities.

Audio MT methods are typically used for investigating the conductivity variations of the near-surface to several kilometres depth, while Broadband MT methods have the added advantage of also detecting responses down to 10s of kilometres depth. Measuring time for both methods range from a few hours to a week. In contrast, Long Period MT surveys (LPMT) measure responses from depths up to several 100 kilometres and provide conductivity information of the lower crust and upper mantle using low frequencies, measuring over a long period, typically 3 to 6 weeks. (Government of Western Australia: Magnetotelluric (MT) surveys (Nabighian, 1991) Although LPMT measurements are too deep for mining applications, they may be important to unravel the deeper structure of the crust and as such reduce the area of prospecting for minerals.

Human-related electromagnetic sources such as high-voltage power cables can disturb the measured signal. Low signal-to-noise levels can even inhibit interpretations. To resolve this, alternative measuring techniques have been developed such as controlled source audio-frequency MT (CSAMT) and remote reference soundings MT (RRSMT).

CSAMT is a frequency-domain electromagnetic sounding technique, which uses a fixed grounded dipole or horizontal loop as an artificial signal source. The source provides a stable, dependable signal, resulting in higher-precision measurements than are usually obtainable with natural-source measurements in the same spectral bands. However, the controlled source can also complicate interpretation by adding source effects, and by placing certain logistical restrictions on the survey. In most practical field situations these drawbacks are not serious, and the method has proven particularly effective in mapping the top 2 to 3 km of the Earth's crust (Nabighian, 1991).

RRSMT uses a reference station to eliminate non-correlated noises, improving the interpretations. The distance between the reference and base station should be small enough for a high coherence between the magnetic field data, but large enough that the magnetic field noise at both stations is uncorrelated. Gang et al. (2018) used a distance of 60 km to achieve this.

3.1.3. Audio Frequency magnetics

Airborne Audio Frequency magnetics (AFMAG) method is a passive frequency electromagnetic (EM) method which uses naturally occurring audio frequency magnetic fields from worldwide atmospheric thunderstorm activity as the source of the primary field signal. The EM fields used in AFMAG have a frequency range from about 1 Hz to 10 kHz and have the unique characteristic of being uniform, planar and horizontal, and also propagate vertically into the Earth. The investigation depth of this method is more than 1 km and as in the magnetotelluric method is determined by the skin depth, depending on the frequency and the bedrock resistivity. A reasonable approximation for the depth of investigation is taken to be 1.5 skin depths (Legault et al., 2013).

Unfortunately, the measured values are strongly affected by motion-induced noise, power lines and very low-frequency transmitters. A variety of processing

techniques are used to minimise the effects of noise, such as stacking, digital filtering, and referencing (Liu et al., 2018).

To address these problems the method theory, electronics and signal processing have been improved enormously, leading to the successful development of the Z-Axis Tipper Electromagnetic (ZTEM) system, commercially exploited for more than a decade. Recently a new system has been developed, the MobileMT system. With this system, airborne measurements of variations of the magnetic field are combined with two pairs of independent grounded orthogonal electric lines measuring 'main' and 'reference' variations of the electric field. The measurement system of the magnetic provides rotationally invariant total-field data, so monitoring or controlling the tilt is no longer necessary. Development is ongoing to make a drone version of this system. Additional advantages are a reduction of mechanical noise and increased flexibility (Prihodko et al., 2024).

3.1.4. Induced polarization and resistivity method

Induced polarization (IP) and resistivity are widely used techniques in mineral exploration. The measurements can give information about both vertical and lateral variations of the Earth's properties and can be used in the delineation of the structure and depth of buried features (Pour et al., 2023). Both methods are closely related where the resistivity measures the conductivity of the subsurface, while the IP measures the capacity of rocks and minerals to accumulate and hold electric charges over time. Both measurements are often done together. An electric current is injected into the ground and the electric potential field is measured between the electrodes. The measured conductivity values can be converted to the resistance and adapted for the spacing of the electrodes. In time domain IP, a DC electric current is injected, and the current injection is stopped after a few seconds, but measurement of the electric potential field goes on recording the slow decay of the voltage in the ground. In frequency-domain Induced Polarization mode, an alternating current is injected into the ground with variable frequencies. Voltage phase-shifts are measured to evaluate the impedance spectrum at different injection frequencies, which is commonly referred to as spectral IP. The foremost application methods are to detect the mineralization of pyrite, graphite, magnetite, or other polymetals with sulphide (Wang et al., 2019; Burlet et al., 2022; Orozco et al., 2022).

The time-domain technique has the advantage of higher potential sensitivity and additionally provides absolute measurements since the measurements are made after the cut-off of the current pulse. The sensitivity of measurements for low IP response can be improved by increasing the transmitter power and enhancing the signal-to-noise values (Pour et al., 2023). The frequency domain technique can be used to gain information about the frequency-dependence of the conductivity and enhance the interpretation of the resistivity data (Orozco et al., 2022).

3.1.5. Self-potential

The self-potential (SP) method, also called the spontaneous potential method, is a passive electrical survey technique, which measures the natural potential of the subsurface. The mechanisms which can generate these self-potential voltages can be split up into electrokinetic sources and electrochemical sources.

The electrokinetic sources can be subdivided into four types of phenomena, namely, electrophoresis, electro-osmosis, streaming potential, and sedimentation. These phenomena are related to groundwater flow together with ions, cations and charged colloidal particles transport through porous media. When in contact with this groundwater, reactive surface sites of many common near-surface minerals undergo proton exchange with and/or sorption of dissolved ions from the porewater. These interactions form a fixed layer of charge, the electric double layer of the particle, ultimately generating the self-potential source currents.

Electrochemical sources can be subdivided into mineralization redox, contamination redox and biologically enhanced redox. These SP signals are all related to redox reactions occurring in interconnected networks of ionically conductive groundwater and electronically conductive minerals originating from the mineralization or contamination. The reactions can be enhanced by microbiological activities. In the case of the mineralization redox, the metallic minerals within a mineralization can also enhance redox reactions by connecting regions of different redox and potentially serving as conduits through which electrons are transferred (EPA, 2024; Moitra et al., 2021).

3.1.6. Seismics

The seismic methods are active methods that measure seismic waves to investigate the subsurface. The information from the wave fields can be processed into planar or spatial images of the subsurface. The seismic waves are generated artificially, e.g. by explosives, hammer blows, vibrators, implosions, accelerated drop weights or airborne sound sources. The waves are recorded with geophones, accelerometers or hydrophones. Transmitter and receiver frequencies must be adapted to the tasks before starting a measurement (Pinkse et al., 2022).

The two main wave types used for seismic measurements are the compressional wave (P-Wave) and the transverse or shear wave (S-Wave). P-waves are faster and have extension-compression particle motion along the propagation direction. P-waves travel through all media that support seismic waves: solids, fluids and gases. In water and air, they are commonly referred to as acoustic waves. S-waves travel slightly slower than P-waves in solids and have particle motion perpendicular to the propagating direction, like the movement of a string of an instrument. These transverse waves can only transit material that has shear strength and does not exist in liquids and gases, as these media have no shear strength. S-waves may be produced by a traction source or by conversion of P-waves at boundaries. The dominant particle displacement is vertical for SV-waves traveling in a horizontal plane. Dominant particle displacements are horizontal for SH-waves traveling in the vertical plane. SH-waves are often generated for S-wave refraction evaluations of engineering sites (EPA, 2024).

The decisive parameters for wave propagation are the wave velocities in the different materials. The wave velocities are determined by parameters such as density, compression and shear moduli as well as porosity. The subsurface influences the propagation of seismic (elastic) waves through mechanisms such as reflection, refraction, diffraction, absorption and scattering (Pinkse et al., 2022).

The two main survey types are the seismic reflection survey and the seismic refraction survey. In the seismic reflection method, the waves travel downward initially and are reflected at an elastic discontinuity, the interface between two layers, back to the surface. Seismic refraction is based on the deflection of the waves when they encounter the bedrock's discontinuities and a principal portion of the wave-path is along the interface between the two layers, before going back to the surface. The seismic reflection method is most efficient in areas with geological boundaries that are sub-horizontal and laterally continuous. The seismic refraction survey provides less detailed information but has a higher accuracy for determining the boundary position (Burlet et al., 2022).

An example of the use of the MT technique is the Australian Lithospheric Architecture Magneto-telluric Project (AusLAMP). The Australian government started this nationwide LPMT project, in collaboration with Geoscience Australia, Northern Territory Geological Survey, universities and other research organisations. The aim of the project is to create a new national LPMT dataset. Figure 3.2 shows the current progress of the project. Results will help understanding the geological make up of Australia and how geological processes work, map geological hazards, such as historic earthquakes, and analyse risks, and finally help to identify mineral and energy resource potential on a broad regional scale (AusLAMP, 2024).

Figure 3.2. The progress of AusLAMP data acquisition. Black lines - state/territory borders for Western Australia (WA), Northern Territory (NT), Queensland (QLD), South Australia (SA), New South Wales (NSW), Victoria (VIC) and Tasmania (TAS) (AusLAMP, 2024).

Another example of the MT method is the exploration of deep-seated gold deposits by Di et al. (2020). They performed a magneto-telluric study in the Liaodong gold province designed to identify any deeper exploration targets. Figure 3.3 illustrates the equipment they used for the research. Their results suggest there may be gold orebodies present at greater depths, and also allowed to estimate the vertical extent of the known gold orebody to a depth of more than 2 km. Figure 3.4 shows a cross-section of the resistivity model.

Figure 3.3. Equipment used in this study. a) depicts the DRU broadband receiver; b) depicts the induction-coil magnetic sensors (Di et al., 2020).

Figure 3.4. Cross-section of the resistivity model. The black dashed line denotes the interpreted position for the Jianshanzi fault. The high-resistivity body is interpreted to be the K1 granite stock. The gold deposits should lie in the transition zone between the intrusive rock (presented as high-resistivity) and the country rock (presented as low-resistivity) (Di et al., 2020).

Piña-Varas et al. (2023) demonstrate the integrated use of the magneto-telluric method and gravity measurements for investigating the basement and cover architecture of the Pyrenees. The magneto-telluric and gravity methods are based on different petrophysical properties of the rocks. As such the two geophysical models provide a different resolution, enabling a better understanding of the geological evolution of the area. Comprehension of the geological structure is the first step in the exploration of mineral deposits. The results of the projects are shown in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5. Integration of results. a) MT model with the major faults and thrusts interpreted (continuous black lines) and the basement thrust sheet (e.g. Orri t.s). b) Final interpretation of the geometry at depth of the Bóixols and La Maladeta sections showing its final observed and calculated gravity data. AZ: Axial Zone; SPZ: South, Pyrenean Zone; LLST: Llavorsí-Senet thrust; GT: Gavarnie thrust (Piña-Varas et al., 2023).

In Feitoza et al. (2024), a study of the Cercal Volcano-Sedimentary Complex structure in the westernmost sector of the Iberian Pyrite Belt metallogenic province was executed for volcanogenic massive sulphides and Fe–Mn (Ba) deposits. In this study ground, gravimetric, aeromagnetic, electrical/IP and radiometric data were integrated with geological and drill-hole data. The aim of the study is to get a better understanding of the shallow and deeper structure of the region, with the purpose of contributing to the discovery of new deposits similar to the known Cu–Ag–Au Salgadoinho mineralization. The results are not conclusive, with two possible geological scenarios. Further research must be focused on the NE Salgadoinho drilling and acquisition of new seismic or electrical/EM data.

3.2. Exploration Drilling and Drilling Methods in Large Depths

3.2.1. Basic theory behind the different types of drilling methods

Drilling has undergone an impressive evolution throughout the years, befitting the ever-increasing demands of industry and economy. From the simple, primitive, percussion drilling that was invented in ancient China to break salt formations it has now evolved and implemented in fascinating ways to extract ores and other resources deep within the Earth's crust in many different ways.

It is imperative that the different types of drilling and their principles of operation are explained in a succinct but adequate way in order to arrive at an optimal solution.

- **Percussion drilling:** Percussion drilling is the first type of drilling ever recorded in history. Basically, it includes the act of lifting of a spear-like construct that is then released and uses its tip to break the rock formation. This method is probably not going to be important to the project, but it is important to note it as it shows the continuation of drilling methods (Akpede, 2010; Todd & Mays, 2004).
- **Cable tool drilling:** Cable tool drilling follows the same principle, but instead of relying on a singular construct it uses a cable that has a drill bit attached to its end. This drill bit is thrown into the borehole and breaks the rock formation. A "bailer" (a claw like apparatus) is then attached to the cable's end and is used to collect the fragments so the drilling can continue (Todd & Mays, 2004).
- **Rotary drilling:** Rotary drilling was developed with the disadvantages of cable drilling in mind. Instead of lifting and dropping the bit continuously, the bit is lowered into the borehole, and it is rotated at a high speed from a motor. This drilling technique requires the drill to be nested at the end of a hollow tube called "drill tube". From this tube, a mining liquid called "mud" is being pumped that fills the hole, effectively removing the small fragments and bailing the much-wanted ore. The mud is then filtered to remove the solid material and a pump draws it back to the borehole. As a method, it can be divided into "conventional/vertical" and "directional" drilling, based on whether the system is drilling at an angle. While this drilling method does not allow for the movement of the drilling machine, it showcases the utilization of a hydraulic system that helps remove the fragments for the borehole (Todd & Mays, 2004).
- **Auger drilling:** Auger drilling is the drilling technique that utilises a screw-like bit to apply pressure to the ground and carry the fragments with the help of a helical path called "flights". Unlike rotary drilling, it doesn't require "mud" or air. The "flights" are responsible for transporting the ore fragments to the surface. This is basically a linear screw extruder (Quan et al., 2017). This type of drilling was used in the "Ice breaker" series that were conceptually designed and intended for NASA's missions, which also included biological (bacteria) analysis sensors (Glass et al., 2014). This type of drilling shows how it is possible to evade the use of a hydraulic system to retrieve the fragments. This is actually the same as a "linear screw extruder" mechanism.

- **Diamond drilling:** Diamond drilling works the same as the rotary drilling technique, but instead of metal (most commonly carbide) bits, it features special bits that have a metal matrix with industrial synthetic diamonds embedded in it. This allows the drilling to be done with abrasion, instead of just crushing, resulting in a cylindrical "core" as an output. (Rotary drilling completely reduces the ore to fragments) (Orpen, 2020). This is in line with what was presented about the use of LIBS in intelligent mining.

The abovementioned methods represent the minimum required methods of drilling that are required to explain the evolution of drilling methods. There are more methods of drilling which are not included in the aforementioned section since they are irrelevant to this project and some of those may pose legislative issues (e.g. "fracking").

3.2.2. Rotary Steerable Drilling Systems

The previous section provides a clear overview of what is most commonly used in traditional drilling. Those systems provide us with the theory behind what is needed in order to achieve different aspects of mining and act as sources of inspiration when designing new systems. Nevertheless, they are not "flexible" systems, because they can't be controlled or operate with a decision-making algorithm (at least their general operation).

Rotary Steerable Drilling Systems (RSDSs) are systems that follow the principles explained in the aforementioned techniques but also feature the ability to steer. That means that these are the systems that can actually perform explorative mining.

The way these machines are structured is fundamentally different than normal drilling rigs. These machines most commonly have a station on the surface that communicates with the "down-the-hole" (borehole) equipment through a flexible tube. This tube allows for the transportation of fluids and other elements that are essential to the control and operation of the system. In this kind of system, it is obvious that the motor that drives the drill head's axis is part of the "down-the-hole" equipment.

In order to better understand these systems, it is imperative that the categories are explained and showcased through already constructed and analysed examples. Categories of RSDS systems:

- **Push-the-bit systems:** Push-the-bit systems are systems that use actuators that directly push the motor against the borehole's boundaries. These actuators are most commonly pads that are pushed with a pneumatic system, allowing it to retract when the pressure drops. Examples of these are Schlumberger's PowerDrive system (Figure 3.6) and Baker Hughe's AutoTrak system (Ma et al, 2016).
- **Point-the-bit systems:** Point-the-bit systems are systems that use internal mechanisms to point the bit to the desired angle. For example, the Halliburton Sperry-sun Geo-Pilot system (Figure 3.6) houses the drilling head's shaft inside of two eccentric rings and uses motors to change the direction the tool head is looking at (Ma et al, 2016).

- Hybrid systems: Hybrid systems are systems that combine the ideologies used in the two main categories to achieve similar results. The same research shows an example of these systems in the form of the PowerDrive Archer RSDS (Ma et al, 2016).

Figure 3.6. The PowerDrive system (left) and the Geo-Pilot system (right) (Ma et al, 2016).

Furthermore, there are additional RSDS systems that do not have adaptive/continuous control of the trajectory of their drilling. These systems may use “whipstocks”, which are basically wedges that allow the drill to slide off to at an angle, or a “bent-housing” for their “down-the-hole” equipment.

3.3. Sensorial Technologies for Drill Core Ore Analysis

3.3.1. Core analysis common practices

Modern mining operations often produce thousands of meters of drill core as part of their exploration process (Dalm et al., 2007). These drill cores are in many cases the primary source of information on the geological situation buried deep underneath the ground. Based on this information geologists have to come up with a geological model of the orebody. Because of this significance and the costliness of drilling, information carried by the cores should be exploited to its fullest extent (Erickson & Padgett, 2005).

Conventionally, this is done by geological logging and assaying. Geological logging involves the process of geologists inspecting and logging all the drill cores for a variety of geological properties. What characteristics are logged varies from site to site but often includes lithology, mineralogy, alteration, texture, structural integrity and more (Whately & Scott, 1996).

This process, although invaluable, suffers from many limitations. First of all, it is entirely based on visual inspection and interpretation by human entities (Koch et al., 2019). The results of this are not infrequently strongly dependent on the experience and knowledge of the specific geologists that made it. It is a highly specialised job that requires the skill to tell apart extremely subtle and important rock characteristics. Nonetheless, in practice the job is often appointed to inexperienced and junior geologists, making human factors and bias a serious problem in the process of core logging (Whately & Scott, 1996).

A second important procedure is assaying, which is the prime source of chemical data, or grade, on geology. Assaying often refers to a selection of high-accuracy, laboratory analysis techniques roughly divided into fire assays, wet chemistry and instrumental analysis (AngloA, 2024). Each technique sports its own set of

benefits and limitations. But as a rule, these techniques often have very high analytical accuracies as compared to many other analytical techniques.

In practice, drill cores are often split in half. One half is used for geological logging, while the other half is used for assaying. One limitation of assaying is that it can only be performed on a small, pulverized sample. Large stretches of core therefore can only be estimated based on small subsamples, which introduces significant representativity issues (Dalm et al., 2007; Metallurgist, 2024). Additionally, assays are expensive and time-consuming, which forces mine operations to limit the number of assays they perform. In zones of interest, an operation can take several assays per meter, while in barren zones one assay per one or several meters is sufficient.

3.3.2. Core scanning and sensors

To counteract these limitations of traditional core analysis, the implementation of sensor technology has seen a steady increase in interest over the last couple of decades. However, the mining industry is traditionally a conservative sector and only tends to adopt new innovations once its benefits have been proven extensively. Therefore, the development of core-scanning systems and widespread adoption has been relatively slow, especially considering its potential (Dalm et al., 2007).

The analytical techniques that are in use today for mining industry core scanning are mostly Hyperspectral imaging, RGB imaging and XRF (Dalm et al., 2007; Coring, 2024). Primarily because of the existence of established industrial core scanning systems (Hylogger, SisuROCK, Minalyze, Orexplore). However, the use of such systems, processing and interpretation of the data still demands highly specialised expertise (Coring, 2024). LIBS has been seeing more attention recently (see the next subchapter), but there are at the moment of writing only a limited number of systems on the market.

3.3.2.1. LIBS

LIBS is short for Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy and is a sensing technique that after decades of development has recently become commercially interesting in a multitude of applications. This is mostly related to advances in laser and optics technology that renders vital components more affordable than they were in the past (Harmon et al, 2019).

The technique provides reliable data on the atomic composition of any type of sample (solid, liquid or gas). Measurements are performed by shooting a pulsed, high-energy laser beam onto the surface of a sample (Figure 3.7). The laser ablates a very small amount of material from the surface and forms a plasma consisting of atoms, ions and free electrons. As the plasma cools down, excited electrons fall back into their atomic or ionic orbits and release radiation at discrete energy levels. This radiation is measured by a spectrometer and is characteristic of the composition of a sample at an atomic level (Harmon et al, 2019; Wise et al, 2022; Balaram, 2023).

Figure 3.7. Schematic representation of the principal steps of any LIBS setup.

1. A laser shoots repetitive high-energy pulses onto a sample.
2. Using optics, the laser pulses are focused onto the surface of the sample to create an energy density high enough to ablate material into a microscopic plasma.
3. Emissions from this plasma are collected using a series of optical elements and are transferred into a spectrometer.
4. The spectrometer transforms the collected radiation into a spectrum.
5. The recorded spectrum shows discrete peaks for which the wavelength position is known and characteristic of each element within the periodic system.

LIBS applications

Over the past decades, LIBS has seen a steady development from pure lab systems to more industrial applications. Israeli company “LDS” was one of the first to take the LIBS technique and develop it into a conveyor belt analyser for the mining industry in the early 2000’s (LDS, 2024; Wills & Napier-Munn, 2006). And by now, several other companies have entered the global market. The various benefits of LIBS over some other techniques ensure that it is seeing a rapid increase in interest in the mining industry. The main benefits for this are listed below (Harmon et al, 2019; Wise et al, 2022; Balaram, 2023):

- No (or limited) sample preparation is required.
- Full-elemental analysis in every measurement.
- Ability to analyse light elements (Li, C, Na, Mg, Be etc.).
- Very fast sampling and data acquisition (up to 100’s of Hz).
- Relatively cost-efficient.

Of course, there are also limitations. One challenge for industrial applications is safety issues related to the high-power laser that is within any LIBS system. Furthermore, the calibration process of LIBS systems can be a difficult and time-consuming process (Balaram, 2023). LIBS is fundamentally not a quantitative analysis technique and needs to be calibrated before it can provide numbers on concentration (like any analytical technique). But due to inherent fluctuations in

the LIBS process, this procedure can be more elaborate as for example with comparable XRF devices.

LIBS technology is widely researched, not only in the mining industry, but also for applications such as medical and environmental studies. Because of this development has been rapid over the last couple of years. However, most of the studies focus on lab or other well-controlled environments.

When looking at the current state-of-the-art of industrial applications of LIBS, the picture is less well-defined. There are only a very limited number of commercial systems on the market, which makes the number of published results using those extremely limited. Existing marketable systems that can be actively used in a mining operation (outside of labs) are confined to handheld-LIBS (Sciaps), core scanning (Elemission, Geotek), and conveyor belt analysers (SPECTRAL Industries). There are some examples of online slurry analysers that have been tested in representative environments e.g. (Chen et al, 2023). But these developments are very far from established yet.

Within EU-funded projects, various LIBS applications have been investigated as well. Examples of this are e.g. ROBOMINERS (slurry analyser), DINAMINE (conveyor belt scanning) and TRIM4Post-Mining (mine remediation).

3.3.2.2. Multispectral sensing

Multispectral sensing involves capturing data of a target (rock sample, cuttings, rock face, core surface or borehole inner surface) across multiple wavelengths within EMS, not necessarily visible to the human eye (Figure 3.8). Wavelengths used in geosciences and mineralogical applications typically range from deep ultraviolet (UV; wavelengths \sim 200-400 nm), to Short-Wave infrared (SWIR; wavelengths \sim 1.4-3 μ m). Identification of a particular mineral or rock type can be done by comparing their characteristic light absorption bands and by training spectral classification models with reference materials spectra. In recent years, with the miniaturization of light sources and detectors, including in the UV and infrared ranges, applications in mining have significantly evolved, with multispectral sensing being commonly integrated in processes from exploration to monitoring and analysis of ore deposits.

Figure 3.8 Typical electromagnetic wavelength range used in multispectral and hyperspectral imaging for mining applications.

Multispectral sensing of rock faces in mining utilises imaging techniques to differentiate between ore and host rock efficiently at meter to multi-meters scales. Typically, those sensors use a 2D detector in the form of an imaging camera with the capacity to acquire images in a few spectral channels (multispectral) to hundreds of channels (hyperspectral). In particular, SWIR sensors allow for detailed characterisation of vertical mine faces in active and abandoned mines,

improving the understanding of petrogenesis and facilitating the efficient extraction of resources (Krupnik & Khan, 2019). Furthermore, field-based hyperspectral technologies can map mineralogy and lithology with sub millimetre resolution (Boubanga-Tombet et al., 2018).

In core logging, multispectral sensing plays a crucial role in the non-destructive analysis of drill cores. Automated multiscale and multivariate geological logging from drill core hyperspectral data transforms complex mineralogical data into lithological domains, improving the accuracy and efficiency of geological logging (De La Rosa et al., 2022). The integration of hyperspectral data with traditional core logging techniques allows for a comprehensive understanding of the mineralogical composition, which is essential for constructing accurate 3D geological models (Koerting, 2021).

The concept of a virtual core involves the use of multispectral imaging to create detailed visual and quantitative data sets from physical cores that have been extracted or, in the case of destructive drilling, from the inner surface of boreholes (Kereszturi et al., 2022). These can be processed as digital twins of the physical object to help decision-making in resource management and extraction strategies. Advances in machine learning, data fusion techniques and their integration on small and robust computing platforms (ex: machine-learning dedicated single boards computer (SBC)) are progressively enabling the real-time processing and integration of multispectral data into mining workflows.

3.4. New Critical Raw Mineral Exploration Concepts

3.4.1. Introduction

Table 3.1 illustrates the EU criticality list of elements (EC, 2023). This list forecasts increasing demand and decreasing or high-risk supply in the mid-term to long-term from these commodities in the EU countries, thus representing a strong and possibly stable internal market drive for these minerals.

Table 3.1. List of critical and strategic raw materials (EC, 2023)

Raw materials			
Bauxite	Coking Coal	Lithium	Phosphorus
Antimony	Feldspar	Light rare earth elements	Scandium
Arsenic	Fluorspar	Magnesium	Silicon metal
Baryte	Gallium	Manganese	Strontium
Beryllium	Germanium	Natural Graphite	Tantalum
Bismuth	Hafnium	Niobium	Titanium metal
Boron/Borate	Helium	Platinum group metals	Tungsten
Cobalt	Heavy rare earth elements	Phosphate Rock	Vanadium
		Copper	Nickel

A table of the specific metal value is illustrated in Figure 3.9 (data from July 2019). It should be noted that there can be a significant difference between the metal price itself and the value of the ore. The elemental composition may also be ambiguous to judge the value of the ore (like the difference in the specific value of diamond versus graphite, both elemental carbon minerals). Naturally, the price estimates are sometimes far from the actual contract prices. Therefore, in Figure 3.10, a colour coding is applied to show which price group the actual element belongs to. The price groups are per magnitude i.e. 1-10, 10-100, 100-1000 and

>1000 USD/kg metal. As it is shown, the criticality condition does not overlap with the highest metal value range groups, some low specific value minerals (like barite, fluorspar, etc.) are also on the criticality list (Pinkse et al., 2022).

Figure 3.9. Critical elements of the EU list highlighted in green in the periodic table (Pinkse et al. 2022).

Figure 3.10. The approximate metal value of different elements, as appear in market quotes. Price groups are per magnitudes: grey: 1-10, yellow: 10-100, orange: 100-1000, red: >1000 USD/kg metal (data are based on internet research in July 2019) (Pinkse et al., 2022).

3.4.2. Exploration techniques

Because critical elements and minerals are usually trace compounds of mineralisation, they are associated with a whole range of mineral deposits, and it is impossible to pinpoint one exploration technique as the best. In this section, several alternative exploration techniques for critical element exploration will be illustrated with some examples. The list is of course not exhaustive.

a) Example 1 (Dill et al. 2023)

Conventionally applied geophysics, geochemistry and mineralogy are the most efficient and widely used disciplines for mineral exploration. Sedimentology plays a minor role, mainly for heavy minerals in placer and till deposits. Geomorphology

is ranked very low among the methods used for mineral exploration. Land-forming processes and the resultant landscapes can however play an important role as deep-seated mineral deposits are brought into the reaches of aquifers and eventually get unroofed and exposed to weathering and denudation.

The land-forming processes and mineral associations on hotspot volcanic islands and the resultant volcanic landscape are genetically linked to the REE-, Nb-, F-, Zr-, Li-, and Be mineralization: mass wasting, fluvial drainage, lacustrine, coastal marine and aeolian processes in declining order. Each of the land-forming processes can provide marker landforms indicative processes relevant for rare element accumulations. Geodynamic and volcanic activity are the driving forces and prevail over the climate impact in shaping the landscape. Therefore, landforms in combination with compositional data from mineralogy can shed some light on the origin of REE-Nb-F-Zr-Li- Be mineral.

This holistic approach can also be taken to different mineral commodities elsewhere in the world given the low maturity of the landscape in the target area. It can also be used for submarine landforms in and around an archipelago simply by minero-stratigraphic correlation from land to sea. The mineralogical terrain analysis as applied in the current study is not a fixed methodological construct but is open also to replacements and supplements by e.g. geophysics. Figure 3.11 shows a flow sheet of the various steps of a mineralogical terrain analysis for colluvial, fluvial, coastal marine, lacustrine, and aeolian landscape-forming processes.

Figure 3.11. Flow sheet to show the various steps of a mineralogical terrain analysis for colluvial, fluvial, coastal marine, lacustrine, and aeolian landscape-forming processes with its main tools (1)

Geological-geomorphological mapping and geomorphometric analysis, (2) Hydrodynamic analysis, (3) Sedimentological analysis, (4) Geochronology, (5) Chemical analysis, (6) Petrological-mineralogical analysis. Lab = laboratory-based, OSL = optically stimulated luminescence, GMS = gravel analysis using granulometry, morphology of lithoclasts and situmetry (orientation of lithoclasts) (Dill et al., 2024).

b) Example 2 (Zhang et al. 2022a):

Quartz is one of the most important and abundant gangue minerals in many magmatic-hydrothermal ore deposits, forming over a wide range of temperatures and pressures from fluids of diverse origins and compositions. Moreover, its trace element composition is sensitive to physicochemical conditions in the environment of deposition. Consequently, the chemistry of quartz has been used to constrain ore genesis in a variety of magmatic hydrothermal deposits. A recent study focusses on quartz in carbonatite-related magmatic-hydrothermal REE deposits.

Quartz is also a common phase in carbonatite-related rare earth element (REE) deposits, but its geochemical characteristics and significance for ore genesis have not previously been documented in this environment. Rare earth element mineralization in these deposits is associated with well-developed hydrothermal systems in which the dominant REE minerals, bastnäsite, parisite, and monazite, are intergrown with aegirine-augite, arfvedsonite, calcite, fluorite, barite, and quartz. The results show that quartz grains from the carbonatite-related REE deposits are characterised by low concentrations of trace elements, of which Al is generally less than 50 ppm whereas others are generally less than 10 ppm. In general, the trace element concentrations in quartz from different deposits are similar (the total concentration is commonly <50 ppm) and are distinguishable from those of quartz in other magmatic-hydrothermal systems. The low concentration of trace elements in carbonatite-related REE deposits is controlled by the unusual nature of carbonatitic magmas and their derived fluids, and thus can be used for defining the affinity of hydrothermal REE systems that are of unknown origin.

Significantly, the trace element chemistry of quartz displays a systematic spatial variation such that the concentrations of Al, Ti, Na, and K decrease with increasing distance of the samples from carbonatites. This spatial variation correlates well with the variation of physio-chemical conditions during the evolution of ore-forming fluids. This implies that the geochemistry of quartz can be used as a vector detecting the concealed carbonatite intrusions in carbonatite-related REE deposits.

c) Example 3 (Li et al., 2023):

In this study, they investigated zircons from variable granite related deposits, veins and skarn deposits, using textural, chemical and isotopic data. The results show that zircons from W–Sn-related granites are rich in U, P, Ti, Y, Nb, Ta, Pb, Hf, Th, and REE compared to Cu–Mo-related granite. For the vein-type deposits, ore-bearing veins have significant zircons captured from geological bodies through which ore-forming fluid originated and migrated (e.g., basement rocks), whereas ore-free veins possess fewer zircons and are mostly from country rocks. Finally, in skarn-type deposits, ore-bearing skarns have zircons from granitic rocks and

country rocks, whereas ore-free skarns have zircons only from one end member, either from granitic rocks or from country rocks. Figure 3.12 shows a model for zircon differences in granitic rocks associated with Cu–Mo and W–Sn deposits.

The zircon criteria summarized by this study illustrate the robustness of zircons and a pathfinder for ore explorations and suggest it can be applied to similar ore deposits worldwide.

Figure 3.12. A model to illustrate zircon differences in granitic rocks associated with Cu–Mo and W–Sn deposits (Li et al., 2023).

d) Example 4 - AGEMERA project (AGEMERA, 2024)

The EU-funded AGEMERA project will quantify the Critical Raw Material potential in Europe by providing a clearer picture of our potential resources, from areas which have been overlooked or underexplored until now. To do that 7 target sites will be analysed from points of view:

- Geological potential to decide if the resource can be exploited in an environmentally and socially friendly way
- Ecological, economic, and social responsibility to uncover local's perception about the mineral sector, and its impact on policy-making.

The AGEMERA project is supporting the identification, assessment, and utilisation of Europe's own vital raw material resources in a way that is socially, ecologically, and economically viable, concentrating on evaluating new, existing and historical mining regions.

Within AGEMERA project extensive geological and geophysical surveys across 4700 km², in 7 target sites in Europe (Finland, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Spain, Bulgaria, Poland, and Germany) and one in Africa (Zambia) will be conducted with use of novel, passive technologies for mineral exploration.

These technologies will consist of 3 non-invasive methods of surveying, which will be combined with other near-surface geophysical methods and existent geological

information for a clear picture of the Critical Raw Material (CRM) potential in that area:

- passive seismic methods,
- multi-sensing drone system combining magnetic, radiometric and electromagnetic sensing,
- muon-based multidetector density detection system.

The project will use data from open-access databases (e.g., European Geological Data Infrastructure, EGDI), the data collected from the field by project geoscientists, and various geophysical survey methods to refine and improve the genetic mineral system models of the various deposit types known to contain lithium, cobalt, molybdenum, vanadium, PGMs, niobium, tantalum, bauxite and REE.

e) Example 6- ¡VAMOS! (Bakker, 2017)

The Viable Alternative Mine Operating System (¡VAMOS!), was a research project funded by the H2020 programme that built a prototype underwater mining system that could provide a novel way of exploiting inaccessible inland mineral resources that lie beneath the water table. Figure 3.13 illustrates the prototype underwater mining system.

The project researched and developed a submerged remotely controlled underwater mining vehicle with associated launch, recovery and ore-collecting equipment. The mined slurry could be pumped up to the surface through a riser to an anchored launch and recovery vessel and then through a hose system to an on-land dewatering facility. The mining vehicle collected visual and sonar information for situation modelling, obstacle avoidance data and vehicle positioning and orientation data. The mining machine positioning is obtained by a localisation solution that fuses Short Base Line acoustic positioning with an onboard inertial motion unit providing orientation information. In addition, the mining vehicle also carries a set of sensors providing situational awareness, which allows safe and efficient remote operation. The sensors consist of a multibeam sonar system, and an underwater camera (and lights) mounted on a pan tilt unit, on several cameras and lights located at relevant machine points and in a set of custom-developed laser-based structured light systems (SLS). The system is also equipped with cutting-edge technology for environmental data collection and real-time grade control. The ¡VAMOS! technology is expected to provide major advantages in the fields of environmental sustainability and safety with respect to conventional mining methods. Two separate field trials will prove the environmental integrity and economic viability of the concept.

Figure 3.13. Artist's impression of the iVAMOS! technology in action (Damen Dredging).

3.5. Autonomy Practices in Underground Mining Environments

3.5.1. Overview of autonomy practices and application in mining projects

To emphasise how important and promising R&D area the autonomy practices in mining is, it's proper to present several "sister" projects in this domain, funded by EU. In the following section, we list just a few most relevant to our project.

3.5.1.1. NEXGEN-SIMS project (NEXGEN, 2024)

NEXGEN-SIMS project established technological advancements towards the future of sustainable underground mining in Europe. More specifically, the aim was to develop and demonstrate digitalisation solutions in combination with state-of-the-art autonomous mining machines, equipment and processes that enable carbon-neutral mining solutions. Among the innovative technological frameworks, NEXGEN-SIMS provided three pilot demonstrators:

- for robotized inspection of the face before and after the blast,
- autonomous material handling at the face,
- autonomous vehicles in mixed traffic.

Robotized inspection solutions could remotely assist mining operators with relevant information to support and improve the decision-making process.

The innovative technologies will enable a more detailed visual inspection and measurement in underground mining environments, such as blasting faces, working areas and shafts. As an example, the robotized measurement inspections will be based on autonomous micro aerial robots that will have the capability to be deployed after the blasting event to perform visual inspections and monitoring of the blasting area, gas measurements and flow rates and provide support in evaluating the overall safety and status of the working areas.

The defined NEXGEN-SIMS goals for the robotized mission are summarized as follows:

- Zero human-based interaction with the machine, except for general planning and mission overview.

- Fully autonomous inspection of high safety risk areas in underground mines
- AI-enabled navigation for enhancing local autonomy in machines.
- Data will be automatically provided and displayed for the operators to support their decision, e.g. if the blasting results were successful.
- Data will be automatically provided and displayed for the operators to support their assessment of the environmental conditions at the mining face.

Autonomous material handling is about autonomous bucket loading and dumping into a truck underground. The defined NEXGEN-SIMS mission consists of three goal technologies as follows:

a) Detection of the muck pile

In this task, we must choose the right sensors and systems to be able to detect and sort out the muck pile's position and defragmentation. This sensor will tell the autonomous loader where it should start the digging process and where to fill the next bucket. It will also tell the system if it has to call for assistance in case larger boulders are detected or if the face is empty and out of ore to dig.

b) Autonomous bucket filling

Once the muck pile has been identified the loader should plan the motion of the bucket towards the pile and fill it. But every pile doesn't look the same and boulders can affect the mission. Repeatability is another challenge, since in every bucket fill attempt the bucket load should be above a threshold to have an impact on the efficiency of the operation.

c) Dumping in the box

This is the task where the interaction between the vehicles takes place, which must be considered as a special and tough challenge. The dumping has to be precise enough so we don't harm our equipment and also accurate enough so we can fill the box as expected. Tolerance of the connectivity and positioning system must be good enough, so we know where our autonomous machines are placed. It is also the base for our safety and, with that, the continuous utilization of the vehicles.

Autonomous vehicles in mixed traffic are focused on investigating how to make two vehicles or moving objects meet and pass each other, and collaborate, in a safe way underground, and without the safety margins suffering. The NEXGEN-SIMS project was among the first efforts to address this complex task underground. The defined NEXGEN-SIMS goals for the robotized mission are summarized as follows:

- Ore transportation by autonomous machines in areas with manual operations
- Autonomous mine truck with sensors onboard for object detection in close proximity
- Mission planner to prioritize which machine needs to move
- Mixed traffic definition based on manual driving and autonomous machine

3.5.1.2. RoboMiners (RoboMiners, 2024)

The ROBOMINERS project, initiated in June 2019, aimed to revolutionize the extraction of raw materials, including strategically vital metals essential for the ongoing energy transition, from domestic sources within the European Union. ROBOMINERS envisioned constructing a modular robot miner prototype capable of performing selective mining. This solution allows the reopening of many of Europe’s abandoned underground mines, without the need for a full recommissioning and without the need for dewatering the mine. It also enables material extraction from small but high-grade mineral deposits. The proposed technology does not require the development of any mine infrastructure and even very small deposits can be mined.

The project has harnessed cutting-edge technology to create a bio-inspired robot tailored for challenging or relatively small deposits. Given the numerous risks associated with underground mining, the automation of this field is of paramount importance. The ROBOMINERS prototype (Figure 3.14) boasts a wide array of functions, including navigation, perception, excavation, material transport, and in-line material analysis. Rigorous experiments have yielded detailed insights into the technology’s suitability for varying rock conditions, resulting in significant enhancements in its excavation performance. The ROBOMINERS validation objective was TRL-4, while the concept operation is described as follows:

- Robot parts are sent underground via a borehole
- They self-assemble to form a fully functional robot
- Using specialised sensing devices, they detect ore
- Using ad-hoc production tools, they produce slurry that is pumped out
- They can re-configure on-the-job

Figure 3.14. Prototypes built during the ROBOMINERS project and their capabilities.

3.5.2. Robotic autonomy developments towards subterranean environments

3.5.2.1. DARPA Subterranean Challenge

The DARPA Subterranean Challenge (Darpa, 2024) was a three-year-long robotic competition from 2017 ending in 2021. The challenge aimed to advance the field of robotic exploration in an unknown subterranean environment and find “artifacts” (helmets, cell phones, and similar items) (Leslie et al, 2022). The competition intended to reduce the research gaps within the four key technology

areas, namely a) autonomy, b) perception, c) networking (to establish robust communications) and d) mobility. The end goal was to advance these technologies that can be implemented for autonomous search and rescue missions in for example, underground mines. Each team participating in the challenge were allowed one human operator to control the entire fleet of robots, while the area where robots were operating was unknown, dynamics, infrastructure-free subterranean environments, which resulted in competitors to develop strategies where the robots needed to bring their own communication infrastructure in order to receive instructions or return the information about any found “artifact”. For a general review of the DARPA Subterranean Challenge in terms of the challenge, acquired results, and lessons learned in (Chung et al., 2023). The teams developed large systems for controlling the robots in the challenge, one such system is Nebula (Agha et al., 2021), a system that deals with multiple robots and the mapping and coordination between them. The winning team developed Graph-Based Planner (Dang et al., 2019), as well as the rest of the system (Tranzatto et al., 2022) an efficient exploration path planner as well as a mapper. A third system that emerged from the DARPA Subterranean Challenge is for team CTU-CRAS (Rouček et al., 2020). All these different systems and more are functionally similar. All are exploring and creating a map with multiple robots, and they are detecting and placing objects on that map. This is achieved by multiple sub-parts such as path planning, navigation, motion planning, and so on. Even multiple solutions are presented from the DARPA Subterranean Challenge is they specialized for one task and is hard to transfer to other tasks. For robotics today is still a big challenge to have systems that allow for different types of missions.

The research of multi-agent systems, particularly in the realm of robotics, has recently had a focus on challenges like vehicle routing and coalition formation (Tadewos et al, 2019; Queraltà et al, 2020). However, one of the persistent issues encountered in various applications is task allocation, where agents need to be assigned to available tasks in an intelligent manner. In addressing this, the literature offers diverse approaches, including: 1) Optimization-based methods which aim to minimise or maximise a global objective function, typically requiring comprehensive knowledge about the multi-agent system's state. However, they may be too computationally intensive. 2) Deterministic approaches, which can generate optimal solutions but may suffer from time inefficiency (Korsah et al., 2012). 3) Heuristic approaches such as those explored in (Wawerla et al., 2010) that offer pragmatic solutions but might sacrifice optimality for efficiency and 4) market-inspired approaches where tasks are treated as commodities that can be transferred between agents, facilitated either by a centralised coordinator or consensus mechanisms (Tadewos et al., 2019; Dahlquist et al., 2023).

A comprehensive study on the scalability of market-based methods (Dias et al., 2004). The authors of (Karampelias et al., 2023) compared different task allocation approaches and the concept of 'on-demand' utilization of aerial vehicles was introduced. Other recent methods to increase the reactivity and improve the scalability include cloud robotics (Afrin et al., 2021) where agents are designed to outsource computation to a cloud service or share common computational resources.

It's worth noting that many approaches often assume, as in Chen et al. (2012), that all tasks are predetermined and known in advance. Considering the concept of "Multi-Machine Coordination," these strategies could be adapted to address coordination challenges among multiple machines. For instance, in scenarios where several machines need to collaborate on tasks, similar optimization, deterministic, heuristic, and market-inspired approaches can be applied. However, with considerations for their specific capabilities, communication protocols, and task dependencies.

3.5.2.2. In-space mining prospects

Space mining involves extracting valuable minerals and resources from celestial bodies such as asteroids, comets, and other objects in space. This practice has garnered considerable interest lately because it offers the opportunity to acquire rare and precious materials that are in short supply on Earth. Additionally, these celestial bodies contain abundant water reserves, a crucial mining resource for future extraterrestrial exploration and settlement endeavours. Although space mining remains primarily theoretical and in the developmental phases, its potential to transform multiple industries and facilitate humanity's journey beyond Earth into the cosmos is considerable. Some of the major challenges associated with in-space mining are legal and regulatory frameworks as well as technology challenges.

The legal ownership of resources in space presents a complex and evolving challenge. While the Outer Space Treaty of 1967 prohibits nations from asserting sovereignty over celestial bodies, it does not explicitly regulate resource extraction. Recently, prominent governmental entities such as the United States and Luxembourg have been formulating their own legislation to legalise off-Earth mining endeavours. Broadly, these laws stipulate that entities capable of accessing space resources would hold ownership over them, granting them the freedom to utilise or sell the acquired resources as they deem fit (Dallas et al., 2020).

In terms of the technology challenges extending in terms of locating, mining, and transporting resources from space is a significant challenge. The majority of the space resource extraction missions are either targeting the Moon and Mars (Just et al., 2020) or small celestial bodies like asteroids and comets (Zhang et al., 2023). In terms of lunar missions, Just et al. (2020) provide an extensive review of the lunar regolith excavation and handling for In-Situ Resource Utilization (ISRU) efforts. In (Seweryn et al., 2024), an open pit mine concept in the Moon environment is developed and defines the main objectives with economic indicators which is to excavate, process, and, ultimately, sell the lunar regolith to meet customer needs. Moreover, the authors, define the lunar open pit mine architecture representing different stages of the flow of regolith; a conceptual design for surface and underground storage; a conceptual design of the mining site; and lastly a conceptual design of transportation networks, including roads. In Europe, the Ground-Based Pilot Plant (GBPP) (Spaceapp, 2024) is a terrestrial analogue designed to test and validate technologies that will be used in future lunar missions. The focus of this initiative is to efficiently extract oxygen and metals from Lunar regolith using the molten salt electrolysis processes. The plant aims to demonstrate long-term system operational aspects at a relevant scale, including mass, power, overall efficiency, reliability, sustainability, operation and

maintenance, and safety. Additionally, space mining requires advanced robotics, automation, and resource extraction techniques that can operate in microgravity environments. In terms of developing the exaction systems which in the earlier stage need to be developed on Earth and then launched to either the Moon or Mars. Thus, unlike on Earth, these excavators need to light lightweight simple design, bounded by the physical limitations of the launch vehicles. Additionally, these mining machines need to manage dust, as it causes serious issues for the circuitry (as they are Lunar dust is electrostatic in nature), as well as it might impair the visual instruments on board. As a result, low traction excavators are being explored, e.g. RASSOR excavator (Mueller et al., 2016) (Figure 3.15) which will also solve the issue of working in a microgravity/low gravity environment.

Figure 3.15. Regolith Advanced Surface Systems Operations Robot (RASSOR) Excavator (Mueller et al., 2016).

3.5.3. Overview of the state-of-the-art of autonomous robot navigation in subterranean environments

The area of autonomous robot navigation in subterranean environments has grown significantly in the last few years. The recent developments in this field are transforming our lives with continuously increasing numbers of robotic applications (Agha et al., 2022).

3.5.3.1. Autonomous path planning and multi-machine coordination

Autonomous path planning is concerned with the design and implementation of routes for robotic systems or autonomous vehicles, ensuring that these machines can navigate and operate within the mine safely, efficiently, and with minimal human intervention. A distinction is made between off-line path planning and real-time path planning. Each has its unique characteristics, advantages, and suitable applications based on the operational demands and environments. To achieve the objectives of autonomy in mining, both off-line and real-time path planning have to be considered.

Path planning in the field of robotics is a fairly well-researched area, with the basic types A* and RRT* path planning (Zammit et al., 2022). And their improved variations, for example, GBPlanner (Dang et al., 2019) or D*+ (Karlsson et al., 2023). These path planners are designed for omnidirectional robots, unlike most mining machines. They are typically used with relatively small robots, which can lead to sub-optimal solutions when applied to larger machines in expansive

environments. Research on path planning with motion constraints for large machines such as (Song et al, 2018) exists, but there remains a gap in performance and reliability when it comes to mining machines. Even for traditional robots, there is room for improvement; achieving safer paths with lower computational costs and reduced memory usage is highly desirable.

3.5.3.1.1. Off-line path planning

Off-line path planning, also known as global path planning, involves calculating the best path for an autonomous vehicle from start to finish before the journey begins. This planning is typically conducted in a controlled environment where all necessary data about the operating environment is known in advance.

Off-line path planning is characterised by the following:

- **Pre-processed Environment:** The environment is fully mapped, and the path is planned based on this static map.
- **Computationally Intensive:** Algorithms can afford to be more complex and thorough, as the computation occurs before the operation.
- **Limited Adaptation:** The path does not change in response to real-time changes or unexpected obstacles. However, following a stochastic approach does provide path alternatives that may be considered to adapt to real-world scenarios.

The advantages of employing off-line path planning are the following:

- **Predictability:** The paths are known and can be optimised for efficiency and safety.
- **Optimization:** Allows for complex calculations that optimise the path based on multiple parameters like distance, time, and energy consumption.
- **Safety:** Higher control over the paths can reduce risks, especially in environments with known hazards.

In path planning, classical algorithms with re-planning capabilities for dynamic environments include D* Lite (Koenig & Likhachev, 2002), Field D* (Ferguson & Stentz, 2006), and Theta* (Nash et al., 2007). These algorithms excel at quickly re-planning based on local information and can identify when a path is obstructed. They store the computed path beyond the obstacle and seek a new route, which can either reconnect to the stored path or find a shorter path to the goal. However, these algorithms require enhancements for full functionality in 3D environments and integration into comprehensive exploration frameworks. Although related works (Sheckells, 2018), (Carsten et al., 2006), and (Nash et al., 2010) have adapted these algorithms for 3D applications, none have been tested in dynamically expanding 3D environments on a large scale. "Large scale" refers to scenarios where local environmental perception is continuously and sequentially expanded, such as with a robot equipped with a 3D laser scanner that merges progressive 3D dense point cloud registrations during exploration.

3.5.3.1.2. Real-time path planning

Real-time path planning, or local path planning, involves calculating the path dynamically as autonomous vehicles navigate through the environment. This

method is used when the operating conditions are unpredictable or when obstacles may appear spontaneously.

Real-time path planning is characterised by the following:

- **Dynamic Environment Handling:** Capable of adjusting the path in response to new or moving obstacles.
- **Less Computationally Intensive per Decision:** Makes quicker, less complex calculations to facilitate immediate response to changes.
- **Continuous Adjustment:** Regularly updates the path based on real-time sensor data and environmental feedback.

The advantages of employing real-time path planning are the following:

- **Flexibility:** Can adapt to new information and unexpected conditions, enhancing navigational safety and effectiveness.
- **Scalability:** More suitable for complex environments where conditions change frequently, like urban settings or dynamic industrial areas.
- **Responsiveness:** Quick adjustments enhance the ability to deal with dynamic scenarios effectively.

3.5.3.1.3. Multi-machine coordination

The study of Multi-Agent Path Finding (MAPF) problems has experienced significant growth in recent decades, driven by their vital role in various industrial applications involving multi-robot systems. A plethora of MAPF solvers have emerged, with search-based algorithms being the predominant approach. For example, M^* , an A^* -based MAPF algorithm proposed by Wagner & Choset (2015), explores the configuration space using joint states and coordinates agents only when they encounter obstacles. MAPF-LNS, introduced by Li et al. (2021), employs Large Neighbourhood Search to replan paths for a subset of agents, aiming to minimise collisions. Conflict-Based Search (CBS), pioneered by Sharon et al. (2015), stands out as one of the most widely used MAPF solvers, addressing conflicts between agents and path planning for individual agents hierarchically while ensuring completeness and optimality. Extensions of CBS, such as ECBS by Li et al. (2021a, 2020), and ICBS by Boyarski et al. (2021), have been proposed to expedite CBS by finding bounded-suboptimal solutions and prioritizing cardinal conflicts, respectively.

However, most existing MAPF algorithms assume that agents' footprints resemble particles operating in discrete grid maps, neglecting the agents' kinematics. Recently, a few researchers have endeavoured to generalise MAPF to better reflect real-world scenarios. For instance, Li et al. (2019) introduced MAPF for Large Agents, allowing agents to occupy multiple vertices simultaneously based on their given shapes and volumes, with collisions occurring when agents share vertices at the same time step. Ma et al. (2019) proposed TPSIPPwRT, capable of computing continuous movement with specified velocities rather than uniform discrete movements. Honig et al. (2016) presented a MAPF solution considering kinematic constraints of non-holonomic robots, incorporating maximum and minimum translational and rotational velocity limits and ensuring a guaranteed safety distance between robots to avoid time-consuming replanning. Wen et al., (2022) introduced a body conflict tree along with a spatiotemporal Hybrid-State A^* to

address multi-agent path-finding problems for car-like robots. Kottinger et al. (2022) utilised a merge and restart strategy to resolve conflicts, employing a sampling-based planner to generate kinodynamically feasible plans for robots. Li et al. (2020) leveraged ECBS to initially find discrete solutions for path-finding of multiple non-holonomic robots, refining the solutions into smooth trajectories using nonlinear optimization.

3.5.3.2. *Exploration strategies*

Exploration approaches in robotics literature can be broadly classified into two high-level strategies: frontier-based and sampling-based approaches. In robotics, a frontier is the boundary between unknown and known (or free) space around the robot. This concept was initially introduced by Yamauchi (1997) for single robots and later extended to multiple robots (Yamauchi, 1998). The original frontier-based exploration method involved selecting the closest frontier to the robot's current position and performing a 360-degree sensor sweep to detect new frontiers. Modern frontier-based methods generally follow this approach with modifications, such as clustering frontiers. These methods have been further studied by Juliá et al. (2012) and Holz et al. (2010) for comparison with other exploration techniques.

A 3D exploration tool based on frontier clustering was proposed by Zhu et al. (2015), which used a quadrotor equipped with a stereo camera. This approach selected the closest frontier cluster for incremental exploration. However, this method may not be optimal for aerial vehicles since the closest frontier cluster might not always be directly ahead, requiring additional energy for yaw movements. Authors in Patel et al. (2022) introduced a local waypoint selection planner for subterranean exploration, computing safe look-ahead poses for aerial robots navigating obstructed areas. Other vision-based exploration approaches include the work of Fraundorfer et al. (2012), utilizing Micro Aerial Vehicles (MAVs) with continuously updating frontiers. Work by Cieslewski et al. (2017) proposed a rapid frontier selection approach for UAVs, selecting frontiers corresponding to high flight velocities, which showed superior exploration gains compared to traditional NBV planners. However, this approach may revert to classical frontier-based methods when no frontiers are visible, impacting energy efficiency and performance in complex environments, as discussed by Zhou et al. (2021).

Exploration can also be approached using Stochastic Differential Equations (SDE), as presented by Shen et al. (2012), simulating particle expansion with Newtonian dynamics to identify unknown areas for MAV exploration. The second major exploration strategy is sampling-based approaches, which often integrate exploration and path planning. These methods compute local goals to maximise information gain while minimising travel distance, actuation cost, or similar metrics, as studied by Lindqvist et al. (2021). Sampling-based approaches utilizing Rapidly-Exploring Random Trees (RRT) have been extensively researched, with notable contributions from Bircher et al. (2016), Pito (1999), and Dang et al. (2020a). Authors in Sun et al. (2022) proposed a hybrid approach with an adaptive frontier detector for rapid exploration based on local sampling in RRT, benchmarking exploration in indoor, forest, and multi-story building environments. However, UAVs may exhibit back-and-forth movements during

exploration, a common challenge in sampling-based methods. Work by Dharmadhikari et al. (2020) presented a motion primitives-based exploration-planning approach, aiming to improve trajectory tracking for local exploration. While promising for energy-efficient exploration, this method may get stuck in local minima due to the lack of a global repositioning scheme.

Global graph-based planners, such as those presented by Dang et al. (2019) and Dang et al. (2020b), represent the state-of-the-art in subterranean exploration of unknown environments, with dedicated global repositioning strategies. Comparisons of our work with Dang et al. (2020b) are provided to evaluate exploration metrics.

Hybrid approaches also exist, combining elements of frontier-based and sampling-based methods. Authors in Dai et al. (2020) presented an information-driven frontier exploration method for MAVs, employing a hybrid control sampling and frontier-based approach. Graph-based strategies for multi-robot exploration of subterranean caves and tunnels were demonstrated as part of the DARPA Subterranean Challenge by Kulkarni et al. (2022).

Exploration strategies extend to legged and ground robots as well. Probabilistic Local and Global Reasoning on Information Road Maps (PLGRIM), a hierarchical value learning strategy for autonomous exploration of large subterranean environments, was discussed by Kim et al. (2021), focusing on near-optimal coverage plans. The Frontloaded Information Gain Orienteering Problem (FIG-OP) strategy, using topological maps for planning exploration paths within fixed time budgets, was presented by Peltzer et al. (2022). This strategy was tested with ground robots in multi-kilometre subterranean environments for time-constrained missions.

3.6. On-line Sensor-based Traversability and Risk Assessment

Autonomous traversability and risk assessment play a crucial role in ensuring the safety, efficiency, and sustainability of deep mining operations. By integrating advanced technologies such as deep learning, semantic understanding, and sensor fusion, autonomous systems can navigate through challenging terrains, mitigate risks, and contribute to the advancement of mining automation. Real-time autonomous traversability estimation schemes are a novel autonomy package that has not been yet implemented within the autonomous mine ecosystem or are currently available in the open.

3.6.1. Traversability in extreme environments

In the context of mining automation, where rugged and unpredictable terrains are commonplace, the reliance on geometric features alone for navigation poses significant challenges. Traditional geometric-based navigation methods often overlook crucial environmental properties such as the type of surface or the presence of obstacles like glass or wire mesh. These oversights can lead to unsafe traversable routes for robotic platforms, especially in complex scenarios where geometric information alone is insufficient. To address these challenges, researchers have turned to vision-based traversability-guided navigation systems. These systems utilise RGB images and depth information to assess

terrain traversability based on both geometric features and semantic understanding. By incorporating semantic segmentation techniques, such systems can classify terrains and identify obstacles with greater accuracy, enabling more informed decision-making for autonomous navigation.

Among the works that explore the concept of Vision-Based traversability-guided navigation include (Palazzo et al., 2020) where the authors propose a deep learning-based approach to estimate and anticipate the traversing score of different routes in the field of view of an on-board RGB camera. In a similar manner, Guan et al. (2022) proposes a group-wise attention mechanism to classify terrains, based on their navigability levels using coarse-grained semantic segmentation in RGB images. Furthermore, Gao et al. (2021) propose a contrastive learning-based method, where a feature representation is learned to discriminate regions with different traversability, using a fine-grained semantic segmentation for off-road scene understanding. The resulting maps contain both fine-grained labels and confidence values.

On the other hand, Maturana et al. (2018) describes a semantic mapping system for autonomous off-road driving that builds a 2.5D grid map in real-time using geometric and semantic information from LiDAR and image sensor data respectively. In a similar manner, Guan et al. (2021) presents a terrain traversability and navigation system for autonomous excavators in unstructured environments, which takes RGB images and 3D point clouds as inputs, in order to generate a traversability grid map for planning and navigation. Likewise, Schilling et al. (2017) propose a multi-sensory terrain classification algorithm, which computes geometric features from lidar point clouds and extracts pixel-wise semantic labels from RGB images using a fully convolutional network. Moreover, Zhou et al. (2022) present a vision-based traversable area segmentation, based on LiDAR-based traversable area extraction and a Bayesian fusion algorithm for real-time traversability mapping. Furthermore, advancements in deep learning techniques, such as the WayFAST framework mentioned in the text Gasparino et al. (2022) have facilitated the development of traversability masks that represent terrain traversability as grayscale images. These masks, generated using RGB and depth images, offer a nuanced understanding of the terrain, allowing robotic platforms to navigate safely through diverse outdoor environments, including those encountered in mining operations. Overall, the discussed research highlights the importance of integrating semantic understanding with geometric information for effective traversability assessment and navigation in unstructured environments, a critical aspect of automation in mining where safety and efficiency are paramount.

3.6.2. State of the Art in SLAM for underground environments

An extensive overview of SLAM strategies employed in extreme underground conditions, particularly focusing on lidar-centric approaches has been presented by Ebadi et al. (2024). LiDAR, or Light Detection and Ranging, emerges as a primary sensor modality for mapping underground spaces due to its ability to generate high-resolution 3D point clouds. The paper discusses various SLAM strategies implemented by different teams during the DARPA Subterranean (SubT) Challenge, a global robotics competition aimed at assessing and pushing the state of the art in autonomous robotic exploration and mapping in complex

underground environment (Figure 3.16, 3.17, 3.18, 3.19, 3.20 and 3.21), showcasing the diversity of approaches and the maturity of lidar-based solutions. In CERBERUS' SLAM architecture each robot estimates and operates on its own individual map. Periodically, these maps are sent to the mapping server on the base station for accumulation and for global multi-robot optimization.

Figure 3.16. Overview of team CERBERUS' SLAM architecture.

Figure 3.17. Overview of team CoSTAR's SLAM architecture (LAMP). Each robot runs a local front-end and communicates to the base station, which runs a multi-robot front-end (for loop closure detection) and back-end (for pose graph optimization).

Figure 3.18. Overview of CSIRO's decentralised multi-robot SLAM system in SubT. Each robot runs its own Wildcat's LIDARinertial odometry module independently. The resulting locally optimised odometry estimate and surfel sub-maps are used to generate Wildcat frames. These frames are stored in a database and are shared with other robots and the base station. Robots and the base station then use their collection of frames to independently build and optimise a pose graph.

Figure 3.19. CTU-CRAS-Norlab UGV SLAM architecture (Norlab ICP Mapper). Green boxes correspond to the inputs and output, and the purple ones represent submodules of the SLAM architecture.

Figure 3.20. Overview of team Explorer’s SLAM architecture. Each robot estimates and operates on its own individual map.

Figure 3.21. Overview of team MARBLE’s SLAM architecture.

Operating in extreme underground environments poses unique challenges for SLAM systems, including limited visibility, tight computational constraints, and the presence of obscurants such as dust and smoke. Authors in Ebadi et al. (2024) highlight these challenges and discuss the opportunities for innovation in SLAM algorithms, sensor fusion techniques, and system engineering. The paper also explores the potential of heterogeneous multi-robot operations, involving both aerial and ground robots, to tackle these challenges collectively and improve mapping efficiency.

Recent advancements in underground SLAM, particularly focusing on LiDAR-centric solutions, have significantly enhanced feature detection, point cloud alignment, and motion estimation through the integration of inertial data, according to Ebadi et al. (2024). However, challenges such as ensuring robust perception in rough terrains and developing resilient algorithms to adapt to environmental changes persist. While incorporating non-traditional sensing

modalities like thermal vision and radar holds promise, integration complexities remain. Achieving robust failure detection and recovery methods for multi-modal SLAM systems in autonomous exploration settings is crucial. Further research and innovation are necessary to overcome these challenges and achieve effective navigation and mapping in complex underground environments. Scaling up multi-robot LiDAR-centric SLAM requires a distributed approach to mitigate communication and processing bottlenecks, while open-source implementations can facilitate development. Additionally, scaling down SLAM systems necessitates miniaturization and low-cost sensing, demanding engineering efforts and research into vision-based SLAM under degraded conditions.

3.6.2.1. Multi-robot localization and mapping

In the existing literature, many MRS (Multi-Robot Systems) solutions utilise either a collaborative SLAM approach or a map merging approach as an intermediate step to achieve a certain goal (Agha et al., 2022). The common denominator often lies in the fact that a global frame of reference is needed to identify and localise objects of interest in the global frame of reference. Here we aim in considering works that are applicable in real-life scenarios, where wide-area connectivity and the corresponding said challenges arise. The considered solutions should also achieve the possibility of constructing a global map in real-time scenarios so that the shared information can be utilised throughout the manifestation of the mission. Given the evident differentiation between collaborative SLAM and map merging, where SLAM algorithms persistently aim to estimate position and map the environment, while map merging focuses solely on aligning multiple local maps into a unified global representation, we opt to organize the related works into two distinct subsections, addressing each aspect separately. It is worth noting that both approaches share the common objective of transforming local maps into a global frame.

3.6.2.2. Collaborative SLAM (C-SLAM) approaches

An early example of collaborative SLAM is the CoSLAM approach (Zou et al., 2012), a vision-only collaborative SLAM solution tailored to handling dynamic environments. CoSLAM utilises powerful GPU (Graphical Processing Units) processing to meet the immersive requirements of processing data from multiple synchronized cameras. However, the authors do not elaborate on any component related to the communication and connection of the multiple camera set-up. Other works that exhibit remarkable performance, such as Engel et al. (2018) and Forster et al. (2013), do not consider communication or connectivity feedback and rely on the assumption that a large amount of data could always be transmitted from the network. Frequently, this is a common practical problem that restricts the application of such techniques in realistic conditions.

Authors in Queralta et al. (2019) presented a multiagent mapping approach and proposed connecting multiple vehicles utilizing cellular networks. However, they assume that GNSS information is available, making the solution unsuitable for GNSS-denied environments. Additionally, they do not consider network conditions or any feedback to address communication challenges on map information transmission. Due to that, the deployment of this solution will be challenging considering real-life cellular networks.

A thorough solution designed to explore subterranean environments under intermittent communication conditions was presented by Saboia et al. (2022). This work consists of many parts, including the co-design of exploration and communication, focusing on the mission objective, i.e., the exploration component. Nevertheless, the authors address the challenge of communicating diverse types of essential data (including maps), targeting the maximization of situational awareness between the multi-robot systems. The communication-related aspect targets two main objectives, the deployment of lower-level communication KPIs (Key Performance Indicators), like SNR, and a token bucket rate-limiting algorithm to optimise the mesh network deployment and regulate data transmission. Data transmission regulation serves in many ways, e.g., congestion, available bandwidth, interference, etc. Although the authors considered network KPIs on the map information transmission, there is no application layer feedback mechanism in place in the map transmission phase. Thus, data transmission is safely performed while avoiding network overload but does not consider application layer KPIs and hence cannot operate at full performance. Finally, this work does not explicitly define the use of the merging of map information.

A very comprehensive work from Schmuck & Chli (2019) takes a multiagent SLAM approach and intelligently accounts for the communication aspect of the solution. By doing so, this approach ensures that individual robots benefit from the collaborative scheme, and in the case of communication loss, each robot's autonomy is maintained. The proposed architecture employs a server that handles computationally intensive processes and is responsible for further data coordination tasks. An intelligent design limits the publishing rate to a maximum value for each robot. However, this solution does not consider the dynamic changes that could emerge in a public wireless network (e.g., cellular networks), thus limiting the framework's performance.

When examining C-SLAM systems, it is important to understand the distinctions included in the nomenclature. Below are written the outlines of the differences between types of C-SLAM systems, according to different metrics/characteristics, where the data is being processed into a 3D map:

- Centralised: The term “Centralised C-SLAM systems” refers to systems that use a main computational resource that accepts the data from the robots and performs some of its analysis for them.
- Decentralised: This term refers to systems in which all the data processing is done solely by the individual actors of the robot team.

Another characterisation that has to do with data processing is whether the system is distributed or not. Distributed systems are systems in which the data processing is being handled by multiple actors. Even if a system is centralised, it can still be distributed (Lajoie et al., 2021). For example, SLAM front end (feature extracting and preliminary sensor processing, etc.) on the robots and SLAM back end (optimization, multiple map stitching, etc.) on the server.

3.6.2.3. Map merging approaches

Another popular solution that targets the map merging approach appeared in Hörner (2016), where a map merging framework has been developed suitable for multi-robot scenarios. This work initially preprocesses the point cloud maps to

remove outliers, then performs a 3D feature extraction algorithm with SIFT points (Lo & Siebert, 2009) or Harris corners (Harris & Stephens, 1998) and finally compares features to find correspondences and align the two-point clouds. Subsequently, the succession of this solution relies on the sensing equipment, various map characteristics, and the utilised SLAM algorithm. Finally, this work resulted in a ROS (Robot Operating System) package that is commonly known and used throughout the robotics community (Hörner, 2018). Although the solution is validated in complex scenarios, it did not examine the communication aspect of the problem nor the real-time applicability. The 3D feature extraction process is a time-consuming operation, resulting in processing times of 10 to 30 seconds or more, depending on the size of the maps. These amounts of time can be considered large, especially for aerial platforms and real-life, time-critical missions. Similarly to the aforementioned, the work in Drwiega (2021) proposed a 3D map merging scheme for multi-robot systems based on overlapping regions, and to be more specific, based on the SHOT descriptors (Salti et al., 2014) and the SAC-IA alignment method. Although the results were promising, it did not consider any communication aspects for a multi-agent system and from the comparisons made in other works (Stathoulopoulos et al., 2023), the hand-crafted global descriptor extraction operation results in processing times of 100 to 260 seconds, making it unsuitable for any real-time application.

A learning-based approach in the localization and mapping problem is discussed by Dubé et al. (2020), focusing more on compressing and transmitting local maps. During this work, the authors propose a solution where the robot's surroundings are captured and decomposed in segments. Each segment is represented by a low-dimensional descriptor encoding the robot's surroundings. Then, the same descriptor is fed to a neural network that reconstructs the initially observed surroundings. This approach is particularly interesting and presents an intelligent mechanism to reduce data transmission (since the data required for transmission is the lower-dimensional descriptor) when the considered architecture is deployed over a wireless network. However, the authors do not present any communication-aware mechanism to transmit the descriptors.

In the scope of multi-machine real-time and infrastructure-free mapping and localization, Damigos et al. (2024) presents a multi-agent, centralised, and real-time 3D point cloud map merging scheme for ceaselessly connected robotic agents. Centralised architectures enable mission awareness to all agents, making tasks like search and rescue more effective. The centralised component is placed on an edge server, ensuring low communication latency, while all agents access the server utilizing a fifth generation (5G) network. In addition, the proposed solution introduces a communication-aware control function that regulates the transmissions of map instances to prevent the creation of significant data congestion and communication latencies as well as address conditions where the robotic agents traverse in limited to no coverage areas. The presented framework is agnostic of the used localization and mapping procedure, while it utilises the full power of an edge server.

Finally, following the above and in the field of resource-constrained robots and the need for effective place recognition in multi-robotic systems, RecNet (Stathoulopoulos et al., 2024), is a novel approach that concurrently addresses

both challenges. The core of RecNet's methodology involves a transformative process: it projects 3D point clouds into range images, compresses them using an encoder-decoder framework, and subsequently reconstructs the range image, restoring the original point cloud. Additionally, RecNet utilises the latent vector extracted from this process for efficient place recognition tasks. This approach not only achieves comparable place recognition results but also maintains a compact representation, suitable for sharing among robots to reconstruct their collective maps.

3.6.3. Autonomy in deep mining use case

3.6.3.1. Application of autonomous mobile robots in mines

The mining industry is facing increasing pressure to improve productivity and safety while minimising environmental impact. Traditional mining methods are often labour-intensive, hazardous, and inefficient, necessitating the adoption of innovative technologies to address these challenges. Autonomous mobile robots emerge as a promising solution to revolutionize mining operations by introducing automation and intelligence into the industry (Zhang et al., 2022; Rogers et al., 2019; Lopes et al., 2018).

Autonomous mobile robots have the potential to navigate and operate in challenging mining environments autonomously, reducing the need for human intervention in hazardous conditions. By leveraging advanced sensors, algorithms, and artificial intelligence, these robots can perform a wide range of tasks, including exploration, mapping, drilling, and transportation, with greater precision and efficiency than traditional methods.

Examining the significance of autonomous mobile robots in transforming the mining industry, insights are drawn from recent research on SLAM technologies, unmanned subterranean exploration, and automation in mining to highlight the key findings and insights shaping the future of autonomous mobile robots in mining operations. By exploring the potential applications of these robots in various mining environments, we aim to provide a comprehensive overview of their role in revolutionizing the mining industry.

3.6.3.2. Transitioning from Mining 4.0 to 5.0

The transition from Mining 4.0 to Mining 5.0 represents a significant shift in the mining industry, marked by the integration of advanced digital, biochemical, and environmental technologies. Zhironkin & Ezdina (2023) provide valuable insights into this transition, emphasizing the potential impact of these innovative technologies on enhancing productivity, safety, and sustainability in mining operations.

In Mining 4.0, digitalisation plays a central role, with the introduction of cyber-physical systems, artificial intelligence, wearable smart sensors, and machine learning. These technologies enable real-time monitoring, predictive maintenance, and optimization of mining processes, leading to improved efficiency and resource utilization. However, the transition to Mining 5.0 goes beyond digitalisation, embracing principles of circular economy, renewable energy, and human-centric industry models.

Autonomous mobile robots emerge as key enablers of this transition, offering unparalleled capabilities in navigating and operating autonomously in challenging mining environments. These robots can perform a wide range of tasks.

Advanced mapping and navigation technologies, such as Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM), LiDAR, and odometry, play a crucial role in enabling the autonomous operation of robots in mines. SLAM algorithms allow robots to create detailed maps of their surroundings and localise themselves accurately in real-time, even in GPS-denied environments. LiDAR sensors provide high-resolution 3D maps of underground spaces, enabling robots to navigate complex terrains and avoid obstacles effectively. Odometry techniques help robots estimate their motion and position relative to their surroundings, further enhancing their navigation capabilities.

By leveraging these advanced mapping and navigation technologies, autonomous mobile robots can operate efficiently and safely in underground mines, contributing to the transition from Mining 4.0 to 5.0. With their ability to integrate digital, biochemical, and environmental technologies, these robots represent a paradigm shift in the mining industry, unlocking new opportunities for increased productivity, reduced environmental impact, and improved worker safety. By reducing the need for human intervention in hazardous conditions, autonomous robots enhance safety and productivity in mining operations.

3.6.3.3. High-accuracy navigation and alignment for precise autonomous drilling & excavation operations

Precise autonomous drilling operations are crucial for achieving efficiency, safety, and optimization in mining operations. By leveraging advanced technologies such as laser scanning, AI, and simulation training, autonomous drilling systems can enhance drilling accuracy, minimise risks, and contribute to the overall success and profitability of mining ventures. A similar direction is pushed by Epiroc (2023) to bring automation through digital twins to reinforce existing practices in order to achieve mining efficiency and operator safety simultaneously. The work in Epiroc (2023) integrates onboard 3D LiDAR scans to process and dynamically update drill plans accordingly. The presented work (Sandvik, 2022) motivates real-time drill planning and execution using onboard optical sensors and scanners. While in Epiroc (2023) the use of digital twin is highlighted, Sandvik (2022) integrates an on-hand 3D model of mine for optimised execution of drilling and excavation operations.

3.6.3.4. Multi-machine real-time and infrastructure-free mapping and localization

Deep mines present unique challenges such as limited communication infrastructure, complex terrain, and hazardous conditions, which necessitate advanced technologies for autonomous navigation and operation. By enabling infrastructure-free mapping and localization, autonomous systems can efficiently navigate and operate in these challenging environments without reliance on external infrastructure, thereby improving operational efficiency and productivity. The collaborative approach facilitates comprehensive mapping coverage and improved localization accuracy, enabling autonomous systems to adapt to dynamic environment conditions by continuously updating their maps

and adjusting their navigation paths to ensure safe and efficient operation. This level of autonomy is not yet implemented in current industrial practices.

Regarding localization, navigation and mapping in an underground environment, it is generally accepted that traditional RF technologies, such as GPS, fail to operate the depths at which the robots operate. Thus, it is required to employ methods of navigation that don't rely on GPS and RF technology. Furthermore, in multi-machine solutions, there is the problem of obstructed communications between the robots.

One can find the following not RF reliant methods that should work in an underground environment:

- **Magnetic Induction (MI):** Magnetic Induction is a technique that maps the magnetic field values of the space that are then used to navigate throughout the space. This technique can also be enhanced by introducing coils that change the local magnetic field into salient values that are easily recognizable by a magnetometer. While the accuracy of MI navigation is presumably ideal for the project's requirements when used in ideal conditions, the obvious drawback of this method is that it requires a robot to pre-map the environment in order to navigate through it (Kim et al., 2017). Additionally, it doesn't provide any kind of information regarding obstacles and environmental hazards, such as submerged areas or crevices. While it has these drawbacks, it could be potentially used alongside another navigation/localization method as a way of navigation in already mapped areas, which will save considerable time.
- **Vision-based navigation:** Vision-based navigation refers to sensors that can return optical data regarding the surrounding environment. The camera is such a sensor. By capturing images from the environment at a high enough frequency, it is possible to find out the structure of the mine. This method is commonly referred to as visual SLAM (simultaneous localisation and mapping) and it can be done even without the use of an IMU ("structure from motion"). This approach also enables the implementation of obstacle detection and avoidance logic, while also making it possible to avoid other nearby robots. The disadvantage of this technique is that it requires adequate lighting conditions in order for it to work, as well as discernible geomorphological elements. Its accuracy is also not good enough for the project's requirements.
- **LiDAR-based navigation:** LiDAR-based navigation refers to the use of a LiDAR sensor which projects beams of light to the surfaces which are then returned to its photo diodes. The time it takes for the light beams to return to the robot's position is used to calculate the distance from the surface's boundaries. While LiDAR gives us a straightforward method of SLAM (also called LOAM) with adequate accuracy, it is important to note that it can be greatly affected by dust particles and that it is not as flexible as a camera as it always faces a certain, limited direction. At least with the camera, it is possible to search a greater portion of the robot's surrounding area. A solution to that would be to mount the LiDAR in a base that can move, providing it with a range of motion. Another solution would be to include

additional robots with LiDAR sensors to assist with mapping in difficult areas (Tatsch et al., 2023).

- **Dead-reckoning localization:** Dead-reckoning localization is the practice of measuring the velocity and acceleration of the robot in all of its axes and adding them to its previous position to estimate its current position. In order to understand the boundaries of the surrounding area it requires external pads. This approach introduces a big accumulative estimation error in the case of great travel times and is therefore not recommended.

The above methods are employed by individual robots in order to achieve their own navigation. In order for the above methods to work, it would be easier to differentiate them to SLAM and non-SLAM methods. This is because, at their core, there are general approaches that work for any kind of SLAM-based robotic navigation schemes (referred to as C-SLAM/Collaborative SLAM methods in the relevant literature) and there are approaches that work for systems that do not support SLAM.

3.6.3.5. Case study of implementation autonomous path planning and multi-machine coordination for improvement of mining process – Elytica platform

The Elytica platform provides optimisation, simulation and predictive modelling as an on-demand cloud-based service. These services are consumed by various existing applications through the deployment of REST APIs. EpiSim is one such application, designed to simplify the development of mine simulation models. It provides an easy-to-use interface to capture complex mining logic and to allow the simulation of both tramming and mining cycle activities. The ability to simulate the entire mining value chain assists users of the system in answering important questions related to resource and fleet management, production bottlenecks and constraints, and potential opportunities for optimization. A screenshot from the Elytica platform is shown in Figure 3.22.

Figure 3.22. Screenshot from Elytica software.

The current Elytica optimization and simulation platform will be adapted to cater for off-line path planning, real-time path planning, and multi-machine coordination.

Tramming routes and underground production areas are currently designed manually using Elytica EpiSim. By adding off-line path planning capability, the computing-intensive task of evaluating the feasibility of thousands of different tramming routes may be automated.

Off-line path planning involves pre-computing the best routes for autonomous agents before they begin their operation. This approach, especially beneficial in controlled or predictable environments, relies heavily on optimization techniques to ensure that paths are not only feasible but also optimal with respect to various criteria.

The first step in creating an off-line solution as part of Elytica is to accurately model the environment and the task. This involves:

- **Mapping the Environment:** Create a detailed and accurate map of the operating area, including all relevant features such as pathways, obstacles, zones of different traffic densities, and other environmental details.
- **Defining the Tasks and Constraints:** Specify what the autonomous agents need to accomplish (e.g., reaching a destination, covering a set of waypoints) and the constraints they must adhere to (e.g., no-go zones, maximum travel distance, time windows).

The next step is to define the appropriate objective function. Some of the most important objective functions include:

- **Minimising Distance:** Calculate the shortest possible path for each journey.
- **Minimising Time:** Find the fastest routes based on allowable speeds and conditions.
- **Energy Efficiency:** Optimise paths to minimise energy consumption, which is critical for battery-operated autonomous vehicles like drones or electric vehicles.
- **Balancing Workload:** In scenarios involving multiple agents, distribute tasks in a way that balances the workload among all agents.

The final step is to decide on the most effective and efficient algorithmic approach:

- **Graph-Based Algorithms:** Use graph theory where nodes represent locations and edges represent possible paths. Algorithms like Dijkstra's or the A* algorithm is popular for finding the shortest path on graphs.
- **Integer Programming:** Especially useful for more complex problems involving multiple objectives or discrete choices, like route selection or scheduling.
- **Dynamic Programming:** Used for problems with a temporal component, where decisions at one time point affect future possibilities.

The Elytica platform already accommodates interfaces to both commercial and open-source solvers which will allow the comparison of a wide range of algorithmic approaches.

Combining real-time path planning with multi-machine coordination in environments such as autonomous vehicles, robotics, or industrial automation systems requires advanced optimization techniques. These solutions must address the complexities of dynamically changing environments while ensuring efficient and safe operation among multiple autonomous units.

The first step in creating a real-time path planning and multi-machine coordination solution as part of Elytica is to accurately model the problem. This involves modelling the physical environment, the autonomous agents (machines), their objectives (e.g., destinations, tasks), constraints (e.g., speed limits, no-collision zones), and interactions. Each agent's path and actions need to be represented as variables within an optimisation framework.

The next step is to define the objectives and the necessary constraints. The optimisation objectives can vary based on the specific application but generally include minimising travel time, reducing energy consumption, maximizing throughput, or balancing workload among machines. These objectives must be quantitatively defined to be used in the optimization process.

Some of the constraints that could be considered in solving the problem include:

- **Collision Avoidance:** Ensuring machines do not enter the same space at the same time.
- **Traffic Management:** Controlling how machines navigate through shared spaces to prevent bottlenecks.
- **Dynamic Obstacle Navigation:** Adjusting paths in response to moving obstacles or changing environmental conditions.

To address the real-time aspect, the system must be capable of quickly recalculating paths and decisions as conditions change. This can involve a combination of several optimization techniques such as:

- **Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP):** Suitable for problems where decisions are discrete (e.g., whether to take a route or not).
- **Heuristic and Metaheuristic Algorithms:** Algorithms such as Genetic Algorithms, Particle Swarm Optimization, or Simulated Annealing, which can find good solutions quickly for very complex or non-convex problems.

By integrating these components as part of the Elytica platform, real-time path planning and multi-machine coordination can be effectively solved with optimization, resulting in efficient, robust, and safe autonomous systems capable of operating in dynamic and complex environments.

3.6.3.6. Automation and robotization of underground mining in Poland

Bołoz & Biały (2020), provide a comprehensive overview of the current state and ongoing developments in the automation and robotization of underground mining in Poland. It begins by acknowledging the unique challenges posed by the mining industry's specific conditions, such as difficult working environments and high implementation costs, which often limit the utilization of technical solutions. Despite these challenges, significant progress has been made in recent years, with the emergence and application of robotic and automated machines tailored to the mining sector.

Various examples of such advancements include the MIKRUS automated longwall system (Figure 3.23, 3.24), which revolutionizes coal seam exploitation through mechanized longwall systems. Developed by FAMUR S.A., this system integrates cutting-edge technology to enhance operational efficiency and safety in thin coal seam mining. Similarly, Mine Master's self-propelled mining machines, designed for ore mines like KGHM Polska Miedź S.A., exemplify the integration of automation to improve productivity and mitigate risks associated with harsh operating conditions.

Figure 3.23. MIKRUS system produced by FAMUR S.A.

Figure 3.24. Cabin for monitoring the automatic operation of the MIKRUS system from the surface.

Additionally, the article delves into research projects aimed at furthering automation in mining, such as the development of an autonomous machine for breaking rocks. Through collaborative efforts involving KGHM ZANAM S.A., AGH University of Science and Technology, and KGHM CUPRUM, innovative solutions are being devised to automate hazardous tasks traditionally performed by human operators. Initiatives like the euRobotics Topic Group on Mining and the Space Mining Conference underscore Poland's commitment to advancing robotics in mining through collaborative research and knowledge-sharing platforms.

The potential benefits of these advancements, include improved operational efficiency, enhanced safety for underground workers, and the ability to operate in environments unsuitable for human presence. It underscores the importance of continued research and development to overcome existing challenges and unlock the full potential of automation and robotization in mining.

In conclusion, Bołoz & Biały (2020) paint a picture of a dynamic landscape where innovation and collaboration drive progress in automation and robotization within the underground mining sector in Poland. While acknowledging the obstacles and complexities inherent in this endeavour, it also highlights the tangible benefits and transformative potential of these technological advancements. Ultimately, Poland emerges as a key player in the global effort to revolutionize mining practices through automation and robotics.

3.6.4. Autonomous vehicles as mobile surveyors of abandoned mines

3.6.4.1. Overview of autonomy practices in an unknown environment

Autonomy in unknown environments involves the development and deployment of systems that can operate and make decisions without prior knowledge of the environment they are in. This capability is crucial in mining, especially in cases of evaluation of abandoned mines. Autonomy practices can be classified in different categories, based on the autonomy level that is addressed. In general, autonomous systems require sensors and algorithms to combine data from multiple sensor modalities to perceive the environment. From the aggregated data, the autonomous system may be able to localise itself and create a geometric map of the environment. Given a map and the current autonomous system position, control signals can be defined to traverse the environment and navigate through it. While navigating, the system may encounter exceptions, requiring an additional level of autonomy, namely the capability of making decisions autonomously. As conditions change, the autonomous system may require tuning its algorithms and parameters in order to adapt to the new conditions. This is often accomplished by incorporating ML techniques that are capable of adapting the changes. Below, the state of the art in the mentioned categories is briefly presented.

3.6.4.2. Sensing and perception

Recent advancements in robotics have seen significant progress in sensing and perception capabilities, enabling robots to perceive and understand their surroundings with unprecedented accuracy and efficiency. State-of-the-art robotic systems leverage a diverse array of sensors, including cameras, LiDAR, radar, and inertial measurement units (IMUs), to gather rich sensory data from the environment. These sensors are integrated into sophisticated perception pipelines that employ advanced computer vision and signal processing algorithms to extract meaningful information about objects, obstacles, terrain, and environmental conditions. For example, LiDAR sensors provide high-resolution 3D point clouds of the robot's surroundings, allowing for precise mapping and localization through techniques such as SLAM. Additionally, deep learning approaches have revolutionized perception tasks by enabling robots to recognize and classify objects, detect obstacles, and even predict future actions based on visual and sensor data. This combination of sensor technologies and perception algorithms has propelled robotics research towards more autonomous and intelligent systems capable of robustly navigating and interacting with complex and dynamic environments (Alatise & Hancke, 2020).

3.6.4.3. Mapping and localization

Once sensors gather data, autonomous systems use mapping and localization algorithms to create maps of the environment and determine their own position within it. Mapping involves constructing a representation of the environment, while localization involves determining the system's position within that map. Techniques such as SLAM are commonly used for this purpose (Sousa et al., 2023; Lluvia et al., 2021; Alatise & Hancke, 2020; Saeedi et al., 2016).

3.6.4.4. Path planning and navigation

Autonomous systems use path-planning algorithms to determine the best route from their current position to a specified goal while avoiding obstacles and adhering to constraints. Path planning algorithms consider factors such as terrain complexity, energy efficiency, safety, and mission objectives. Navigation systems integrate path planning with real-time sensor data to ensure that the system can adapt to dynamic environments and unexpected obstacles.

3.6.4.5. Decision making and control

Autonomous systems require sophisticated decision-making capabilities to respond to changing environmental conditions and unforeseen events. Decision-making algorithms incorporate knowledge of the environment, mission objectives, and system constraints to make optimal decisions in real-time. Control algorithms translate high-level decisions into low-level commands for actuators such as motors, thrusters, and manipulators (Benrabah et al., 2024; Rybczak et al., 2024; Dinelli et al., 2023).

3.6.4.6. Learning and adaptation

Autonomous systems often incorporate machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques to improve their performance over time. Learning algorithms enable systems to adapt to new environments, learn from past experiences, and optimise their behaviour based on feedback. Techniques such as reinforcement learning, deep learning, and evolutionary algorithms are commonly used for learning and adaptation in autonomous systems (Rybczak et al., 2024; Garaffa et al., 2023).

3.6.4.7. Safety and reliability

Safety is paramount in autonomous systems operating in unknown environments, particularly in applications such as aerospace, exploration, and defence. Robustness and fault tolerance are essential to ensure that the system can continue to operate safely even in the presence of sensor failures, communication errors, or unexpected events. Redundancy, fail-safe mechanisms, and rigorous testing are used to enhance the safety and reliability of autonomous systems.

3.6.4.8. Unmanned subterranean exploration

In robotics, the exploration algorithm is an essential component of navigational architecture, which determines the robot's next navigation point. These exploration strategies primarily address the Next Best View (NBV) problem and involve incrementally mapping the environment as the robot progresses.

Authors in Martz et al. (2020) examine the complexities of exploring underground environments using robotics, focusing on mines and tunnels. These spaces, while important for various purposes like maintenance and remediation, pose significant risks to human explorers. Prompted by incidents like the toxic leakage from the Gold King Mine, the study underscores the necessity of specialised robotic platforms capable of navigating hazardous conditions and collecting data in environments devoid of natural light. The research tackles challenges in locomotion, navigation without GPS, and communication inherent in underground

exploration, with the overarching aim of developing resilient robotic systems for safe and efficient mapping of subterranean landscapes.

- Locomotion:** The study explores diverse methods for robotic movement in underground settings, highlighting obstacles such as rugged terrains and water barriers. It discusses the limitations of single-modal terrestrial robots like wheeled vehicles and bio-inspired designs, particularly in areas with sludge or water. Aerial vehicles offer an alternative perspective from above but may be restricted by payload capacity. Aquatic vehicles encounter difficulties in navigating shallow or irregular water levels. Multi-modal platforms (Figure 3.25) combine various locomotion methods for versatility, although challenges such as dam crossings remain.

Figure 3.25. Diagram of the Marsupial platform created by Texas A&M.

- Navigation and Localization:** Due to the ineffectiveness of GPS underground, the research investigates alternative navigation and localization techniques. Mapping methods such as feature maps and occupancy grids aid in route planning and obstacle avoidance. Path-planning algorithms like A* and D* facilitate efficient route generation. Localization relies on filters and dead reckoning techniques, with additional methods like beacon-based and visual-based navigation enhancing accuracy. Systems like Millibot and LEDDAR address the challenges of navigating GPS-denied environments through multi-sensor fusion.
- Communication:** Effective communication is crucial for robotic platforms operating autonomously or under human control. It enables data transmission, operational oversight, and data retrieval in case of platform loss. While tethered connections offer reliability, they face challenges such as snagging and drag, especially underwater. Radio waves provide versatile communication options across different frequency bands, with repeater beacons extending signal range. Innovative technologies like Persistent Systems' wave relay MANET product line and Vital Alert's digital magnetic induction network offer robust communication solutions tailored for underground environments, addressing challenges like signal loss through solid strata and enabling lightweight data transmission in caves.

Overall, the study highlights the importance of advancing robotic technologies to overcome the unique challenges of underground exploration, paving the way for safer and more effective mapping and exploration of subterranean landscapes.

3.6.4.9. *Wireless mesh network*

In order to enable autonomous robotics exploration missions in critical infrastructure-less underground mining environment, the adoption of an onboard wireless reconfigurable mesh network is needed. This will allow the exchange of information between the robotics platforms operating in various tunnels of the mining facility. The adoption of Wi-Fi IEEE 802.11s-based mesh network in UAV swarms has been discussed (Morgenthaler et al., 2012), evaluating the usage of some UAVs of the swarm as intermediate airborne network relay to enable connectivity between Non-Line of Sight (NLOS) robotics platform. More in detail, the concept of Flying Ad hoc NETworks (FANETs) has been also discussed (Bautista et al., 2020; Esrafilian et al., 2020), showcasing the need to introduce new link quality routing metrics in order to optimize the performance of a fully wireless mesh network integrated in a swarm of moving drones or other kind of mobile robotics platforms. Furthermore, the concept of dynamic mesh network needed for data transfer among high mobility nodes is evaluated and discussed under different conditions and throughput requirements, related to the swarm coordination and critical data exchange in infrastructure less environments (Cai et al., 2019; Neumann et al., 2008).

3.6.5. **Conclusions**

The conclusions drawn from the exploration of autonomous mobile robots in mining operations align well with the objectives of the Persephone project. They affirm the importance of robotics in enhancing efficiency, safety, and sustainability in mining. The implications highlight the relevance of advanced sensor technologies and modular robotic systems pursued in the project. Future prospects emphasize the need for ongoing research to integrate emerging technologies and address industry challenges. Overall, the conclusions validate the significance of the Persephone project's objectives and underscore the importance of collaboration for driving innovation in mining technology.

3.7. **Rock Mass Preconditioning for Reducing Energy Consumption of Extractive Processes**

In geomechanics, rock mass preconditioning is a method aimed at weakening the strength parameters of rocks, e.g. by forcing them to crack, in order to reduce their potential to accumulate elastic energy and thus reduce the risk of seismic activity and rock burst occurrence.

According to Córdova et al. (2020) rock pre-conditioning is essentially the treatment of the rock mass with an appropriate dynamic process to aimed at generating cracks and fractures by activation of the in situ structural network or by explicit creation of a set of new fractures (Figure 3.26). The main purpose is to weaken the competent rock mass in the primary domain material. According to recent research works three main ways of preconditioning the rock mass may be highlighted:

- **Preconditioning with hydraulic fracturing (HF)** – this method was commonly used in the oil industry. It assumes a fluid injection to the rockmass with a pressure what will initiate and propagate a tensional fracture through the rock mass (Stacey, 2010; He et al., 2016; Basson et al.,

2021). The boreholes are oriented in way that ensures fractures development in the plane of the principal stresses $\sigma_1 - \sigma_2$, so they are able to open up in the minimum principal stress direction σ_3 (Liu et al., 2022). As was highlighted in Córdova et al. (2020) the application of this technique has resulted in a significant reduction of the seismic hazard in subjected sites.

- **Preconditioning with explosives** – this method is commonly described also as rock mass destressing or destress blasting and consists in forcing the formation of a network of cracks by initiating a charge or group of charges of explosives at specific time intervals (Fuławka et al., 2022). The primary assumption of this method is to conduct blasting in confined conditions to maximise the energy transfer to rock mass. In case of torpedo blasting, deep holes ensure that there are no open faces. In terms of short holes (for example in room and pillar mining) one open face is allowed due to technological requirements (Mertuszka et al., 2022). Creating new fractures and reducing the overall strength of the rock mass is the primary objective of this method. To increase the resulting damage in the rock mass, the placement of initiation points along the charge and the timing between holes can be chosen to amplify blast-induced seismic effect (Fuławka et al., 2023).
- **Mixed preconditioning:** In exceptional cases, it is also possible to use a hybrid method including HF and destressing by blasting activities in order to improve the fragmentation of the rock mass that with simultaneous ensuring of high extraction and productivity rates. The method of mixed preconditioning was described, among others, in the work of Catalan et al. (2012).

Figure 3.26. Basic assumptions of rockmass destressing (Fuławka et al., 2022).

Regardless of the rock mass preconditioning method the results should be indicator for at least one of two phenomena: fractures of rock mass and induced seismic vibrations. These factors may affect the rock mass differently or their effects may be combined. As it was pointed out by Vennes & Mitri (2017) as well as Drover & Villaescusa (2019) and Drover et al. (2018), the main goal of rock mass preconditioning is to generate such energy that will allow fracturing of the rocks within the overloaded area and thus move the stress concentration zone far away from the production panel. Such effects may be observed mostly in the direct

vicinity of the preconditioning site. Still, in the case of preconditioning by means of blasting, it may be assumed that a higher energy of detonation allows for reaching more distant zones. In turn, Brauner (1994) highlighted that induced seismic vibrations may contribute significantly to decreasing the friction of joint planes and may contribute to expanding the pre-existing network of joints within the rock mass and creating new fractures. This effect may be considered far-reaching (Figure 3.26 - right). It means that regardless of the analysed approach, the main goal of rock mass preconditioning is preventing energy accumulation in the stiff layers and triggering the seismic event if the rock mass in the vicinity of the mining panel is overstressed.

3.7.1. Technology rock mass preconditioning

3.7.1.1. Directed hydro fracturing

The method of HF rock mass preconditioning was developed already in 1947 but it waited almost fifty years to be tested and implemented to the mining industry. Applying high pressure in a previously drilled hole causes inducing of tensile cracks and thus hydraulic fractures are formed (Shimizu et al., 2011). As it was pointed out in Karkocha (2015) effective HF should weaken rock strength and minimise rock bursting ability. This requires hydraulic fracturing to produce cracks at great range. However, achieving this effect requires drilling a significant number of longer holes, preferably reaching the high-strength rock layers. Research presented in Myszkowski et al. (1997) and Myszkowski (2007a, b) indicates that the range of HF-induced discontinuities in the rock mass may be up to 25 meters around the fracturing well. Which is a highly satisfactory result, exceeding preconditioning associated with, for example, standard mining blasting.

Figure 3.27. The essence of the hydraulic fracturing method (Myszkowski et al., 2019).

One of the best developed hydrofracturing methods is the so-called Directional Hydraulic Fracturing (DHF) of the Roof. The essence of this technology is to create cracks in the rock mass in the immediate vicinity of the drilling hole (Figure 3.27), dividing the rock layers into blocks of specific dimensions and shapes (Jendryś et

al., 2021). This is possible by making a transverse wedge-shaped disc-shaped cut out (Figure 3.28).

Figure 3.28. Device for making transverse wedge-shaped in rock mass (a) sealant placed in the prepared hole before fracturing (b) (Myszkowski et al., 2019).

The orientation of the cut is always closely related to the direction of the drill hole and is perpendicular to the axis of the hole. Then, in the area of the cut, the liquid is injected under high pressure, which forces the creation and propagation of discontinuities around the hole.

As a result, the fragmentation of the rock mass caused by directed fracturing methods reduces its stiffness and enables its faster deformation in the area of mining works, which ultimately results in:

- reduction of seismic activity,
- reduction of dynamic pressures,
- triggering a controlled roof collapse (within liquidation zones),
- intensive degassing of the rock mass.

Ultimately, based on many studies and experiences in the field of rock mass preconditioning, it should be noted that DHF is a very effective method from the point of view of rock burst prevention, however, due to the technology of work, it may disturb the mining process, e.g. by periodically stopping works related to the exploitation and transport of mined material. Additionally, the impact of DHF on the workability of rocks in mining operations has not been considered so far. Analyses in this area would enrich knowledge in terms of not only the impact on the level of safety but also the profitability of mining by reducing mining resistance in selected parts of the mine.

3.7.1.2. *Torpedo blasting*

Rock mass preconditioning may be realised with the use of so-called torpedo blasting. Such a way of rock mass fracturing may be applied both in roof layers and in floor stratum. Torpedo blasting in the roof is aimed at disintegrating the rock medium and involves firing a significant charge of explosives in long blast holes reaching the overstressed roof layers. Examples of rock mass preconditioning with the use of torpedo blasting have been presented in papers (Wojtecki et al., 2017; Burtan et al., 2024). The firing of the explosive charge causes the propagation of waves that travel over long distances. The magnitude and reach of seismic waves depend mainly on the elasticity of the rock medium,

the distance and location of the explosive charge and the size of this charge (Gogolewska, 2010). Torpedoing blasting in most cases is performed in strong and elastic layers of the roof. An example of destress blasting utilised in one of the Polish coal mines has been presented in Figure 3.29.

Figure 3.29. Scheme of destress blasting in one of Polish hard coal mines (Wojtecki et al., 2017).

Torpedo blasting, in exceptional cases, can also be used at the level of the deposit in a horizontal arrangement (Figure 3.30). In this approach large charge of explosives is detonated in direct vicinity of roof rocks. A rock layers affected in this way should be characterised by a steep nature of fractures. The friction occurring on the surface of these cracks, resulting from numerous irregularities and interlockings, stops the vertical downward movement of rock blocks above the goafs/backfilling area. Immediately after detonation of the explosives, the rock block slips against the force of friction, which results in a rock burst in the excavation when mining crew is in safe place. This method was used successfully in Polish copper mines.

Figure 3.30. Scheme of horizontal destress blasting in one of the Polish copper mines.

Depending on the exploitation system used and the local geological arrangement of rocks, torpedo blasting can also be carried out in the floor layers (Figure 3.31). Floor preconditioning is usually performed when there is a zone of stress concentration in the footwall layer. Performing such blasting causes the stresses to be released by destroying the structure of the floor, and the stress concentration zone moves deeper into the rock mass. This method involves the simultaneous firing of explosive charges in holes drilled in the bottom of the excavation. In the case of Polish copper mines, the blast holes are made at an angle of 60–70°, their length is approximately 1.5 m and their diameter is from 40 to 50 mm. The distance between the holes is from 1.5 to 2.0 m. On the one hand, this approach is intended to minimise the potential of the rock mass to create floor bursts. On the other hand, in the case of systems with roof deflection, causing cracks in the floor layers facilitates the process of tightening the excavations and, as a result, minimises the potential for accumulating seismic energy in the pillars and roof layers.

Figure 3.31. Scheme of floor destress blasting in one of the Polish copper mines.

3.7.1.3. Face preconditioning and multi-face destress blasting

In exceptional cases, it is possible to apply a comprehensive approach by simultaneous pre-conditioning of the roof, the bed level and the bottom of the workings (Figure 3.32). Such a platform can effectively help to distance the stress zone from the exploitation front while facilitating the process of roof deflection. However, this type of method should only be used in workings drilled into hard rock. Otherwise, such an approach could have a negative impact on ground control issues. This approach is called face destress and taking into account the impact on the immediate vicinity of the work front, it can be assumed that this preconditioning method may have a positive impact not only on geomechanical safety but also on mining efficiency by "softening" the deposit being excavated.

Figure 3.32. Face distress blast design in hard rock (Carr, et al., 1999).

3.7.1.4. Multiface distress blasting

Multiface distress blasting is a method used mainly in room and pillar mining systems and involves the simultaneous detonation of several to several dozen mining faces in order to maximize the area that is simultaneously affected by mining, and to improve the seismic effect by the amplification of seismic waves propagating from individual faces (Figure 3.33).

Figure 3.33. Scheme of multiface distress blasting.

In the case of multiface distress blasting, rock mass preconditioning is performed using standard production holes. Changes are mainly made to D&B patterns by modifying the type of cut, maximizing the delay charge, and modifying the delay sequence (Figure 3.34).

Figure 3.34. Example of D&B pattern before (left) and after (right) modification.

Detonation of large amounts of explosives in blast holes makes it possible to precondition the rock mass both in the immediate vicinity of the location of explosives and in zones distant from the place of work by inducing high-amplitude

seismic waves (Fuławka et al., 2022). As shown in research (Mertuszka et al., 2022; Fuławka et al., 2022; Fuławka et al., 2023), appropriate modifications of D&B patterns make it possible to increase the seismic effect several times (Figure 3.35) without affecting the operating costs. The advantage of preconditioning the rock mass with multiface blasting is the possibility of combining high mining efficiency and minimising geomechanical hazards while having no negative impact on the continuity of exploitation. Taking into account the technologies of multiface destress blasting, it is obvious that the maximum pre-conditioning effect is generated in the immediate vicinity of the mining front. Therefore, it is worth analysing how preconditioning of the rock mass using multiface destress blasting affects the efficiency of rock mining.

Figure 3.35. Comparison of seismic waves generated by destress blasting before modifications (left) and after modifications (right).

3.7.1.5. Combined methods of hydraulic fracturing and controlled blasting

Attempts were also made to simultaneously precondition the rock mass using both hydraulic methods and those based on the use of explosives. Combined methods of hydraulic fracturing and controlled blasting were presented in research (Krawiec, 2005). Water pressure control blasting induces hydraulic fracturing in the borehole surrounding, which simultaneous increase of number and range of hydraulic cracks. As Huang et al. (2011) pointed out. This technology may be implemented by following steps:

1. Drilling a borehole for hydraulic fracturing and injecting the water-proof bulk emulsion or cartridge explosive.
2. Sealing up the borehole with cement and injecting water until it reaches the adequate pressure value.
3. Detonating the explosives to initiate water pressure blasting which will cause high strain area surrounding the borehole. While the stress exceeds

the rock will rupture and create radial fractures which are extended 3-5 times borehole diameter.

4. Conducting water injection, pulse or cycle injection to carry on hydraulic fracturing.

On Figure 3.36 scheme of water pressure blasting has been presented.

Figure 3.36. Water pressure blasting borehole scheme (based on Krawiec, 2005): a) situation before blasting; b) situation after blasting; 1 – primer (detonator and booster), 2 – explosives, 3 – water under pressure, 4 – stemming (solid) (Karkocha, 2015).

Another promising method of rockmass preconditioning is the intensive preconditioning concept which is a combination of hydraulic fracturing (in down-holes) and confined blasting (in up-holes). Both preconditioning methods are applied before the initiation of the cave and the intent is to ‘modify’ a considerable volume of the mining block. Figure 3.37 is an illustration of the intensive preconditioning concept first reported by Catalan et al. (2012).

Figure 3.37. Sequence to implement intensive preconditioning (Catalan et al. 2012).

This technique can induce improved creation of new fractures, expand the range of existing ones and improve gas drainage (for example methane in coal-beds). Still, joint preconditioning using blasting and hydraulic fracturing is a topic which should be further developed. A set of theoretical calculations and modelling, with taking fluid viscosity and induced pressure should be performed.

3.7.2. Evaluation of preconditioning efficacy

3.7.2.1. Laboratory tests

A well-preconditioned rock mass, due to extensive cracks, should be characterised by lower strength parameters. Of the most common geotechnical tests performed to determine peak rock strength is Uniaxial compressive strength which corresponds to the level of axial stress that produces the failure rock sample. Such a test allows us to determine also elastic constants, Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio, of the rock material (Ulusay & Hudson, 2007). Still, according to research presented by Catalan et al. (2017) both hydraulic and blasting preconditioning had only a little impact on UCS values in the analysed area.

Figure 3.38. Distribution of Uniaxial Compressive Strength results during to intensive preconditioning process (Catalan et al., 2017).

As presented in Figure 3.38, the normally distributed data shows a slight difference in UCS after the combined effect of hydraulic fracturing and confined blasting. Still, Catalan et al. (2017) pointed out that this difference is insignificant from the practical point of view. Therefore it may be stated that analysing the effect of preconditioning based solely on UCS data may not be a sufficient way of evaluation.

3.7.2.2. Monitoring

3.7.2.3.1. Acoustic emission monitoring (AE)

Brady & Brown (1993), emphasized that before reaching the peak strength level, three phases of rock destruction must be achieved:

- 1st phase is a crack closure process,
- 2nd phase consists of elastic deformation increase until an axial stress is reached (i.e. crack initiation, σ_{ci}). This is when stable crack propagation is ongoing, and
- 3rd phase is when the axial stress reaches a point of unstable crack growth and irrecoverable deformations commence. This process continues until the peak or uniaxial compressive strength is reached (σ_c).

Knowing the process one may observe that acoustic emission (AE) monitoring may be a suitable tool for investigating brittle rock failure while this process is associated with acoustic emissions. This technique has been widely used in rock mechanic studies and engineering applications because the initiation and damage process of a piece of rock can be identified (Cai et al., 2004, 2007; Manthei & Eisenblätter, 2008; Cheon et al., 2011; Xie et al., 2011). Correlating AE signals with the stress-strain diagram allows for estimation of the starting point of micro fractures development and propagation during a UCS test. Numerous research studies confirmed that AE is suitable way of monitoring crack behaviour and can be used with high degree of confidence (Boukharov et al., 1995; Rudajev et al., 2000; Moradian et al., 2010; Aker et al., 2014).

3.7.2.3.2. Seismic velocities monitoring

Continuous high-accuracy seismic measurements may be used for monitoring of ground vibration level after each blasting operation (Fuławka et al., 2022a). On the other hand, it may be also used for monitoring of seismic wave propagation velocities which may be correlated with the rock burst risk (Porębski et al., 2018; Gogolewska & Smolak, 2021). The aim of this method is to determine the propagation velocities of seismic waves between sources and receivers. The source is usually an explosive charge located in the blasthole, while the receiver is a special geophone probe, accelerometer or seismometer. As a result of the measurements, the map of seismic velocity distribution is created. It is assumed that proper rock mass preconditioning leads to changes in the seismic velocities within the given panel, so effective stress-release blasting or hydrofracturing should result in a decrease in seismic wave velocities (Mertuszka et al., 2022).

As part of the EU-funded NEXGEN SIMS project, one of the most innovative, low-cost systems for continuous seismic tomography was developed, aimed at identifying the effectiveness of rock mass preconditioning through blasting. As demonstrated during the demonstration in in-situ conditions, the use of seismic systems enriched with appropriate computational algorithms and automated recorder excitation systems makes it possible to track the speed of propagation of seismic waves each time after the detonation of explosives, which in turn is the basis for determining whether preconditioning was effective or no.

An example of the use of the NEXGEN SIMS autonomous seismic measurement system in monitoring the effectiveness of preconditioning is shown in Figure 3.39.

Figure 3.39. Seismic velocity maps before (left) and after (right) destressing with modified D&B patterns.

Seismic velocity maps confirm that properly conducted destress blasting may significantly change the stress state in the surroundings of the analysed mining panel. More information about NEXGEN SIMS project may be found under the link <https://www.nexgensims.eu>.

3.7.2.3. Numerical simulations

Sometimes, precise monitoring aimed at analysing the effectiveness of preconditioning cannot be used due to technological limitations or high costs of installation and maintenance of devices. In such a case, the effectiveness of preconditioning can be determined based on numerical simulations. Simulations can be conducted on a small scale (mining face) or on a macro scale (mining panel).

Based on current experience, it can be observed that the finite element method is most often used for large-scale 3D analyses. Although this method is a continuous method and does not enable the simulation of crack propagation, it is possible to determine the state of stress, e.g. before and after destress blasting, which may indirectly indicate the effectiveness of preconditioning (Figure 3.40). Moreover, a well-validated numerical model can be a useful tool for the theoretical verification of various preconditioning scenarios, which reduces the costs of the work carried out (Figure 3.41). An example of numerical modelling using focused 3D FEM is presented in the papers (Baranowski et al., 2019; Pytel et al., 2019; Baranowski et al., 2020; Burtan et al., 2024).

Figure 3.40. View of a large-scale 3D numerical model (left) and calculation results in top view (right).

Figure 3.41. Safety stock distribution for various multi-face destress blasting scenarios

Recently numerical methods to determine the effectiveness of rock mass preconditioning were used, among others, in the Sustainable Intelligent Mining Systems (SIMS) project co-financed under the Horizon 2020 program (SIMS, 2021) or the Baltic Sea Underground Innovation Network (BSUIN) project co-financed by the Interreg Baltic Sea Region program.

The dynamic development of numerical methods in recent years has resulted in the development of new non-continuous and hybrid numerical codes that enable dynamic calculations of the rock cracking process caused by preconditioning of the rock mass. Using discontinuous methods (most often Discrete Element Method - DEM or Finite-Discrete Element Method - FDEM), it is possible to determine the impact of stress blasting (Li et al., 2021b; Ding et al., 2022) and hydrofracturing (Rogers et al., 2010; Lisjak et al., 2015; Chen et al., 2022; Lu et al., 2022) on the range and density of cracks, which is a measurable indicator of the effectiveness of the work being carried out. An exemplary application of the FDEM method to simulate cracks after the detonation of blast holes is presented in Figures 3.42 and 3.43, while Figure 3.44 shows an exemplary diagram of the detonation of a series of blast holes.

Figure 3.42. Detonation of a blast hole with a diameter of 48 mm made in dolomite, using an explosive with a detonation velocity of 2,800 m/s.

Figure 3.43. Detonation of a blast hole with a diameter of 48 mm made in dolomite, using an explosive with a detonation velocity of 4,800 m/s.

Figure 3.44. Detonation of a series of blast holes with a diameter of 51 mm, made in dolomite. Condition before the start of detonation (left) and after detonation of all holes (right).

3.7.2.4. Tracking of seismicity level and location

The long-term distribution of seismic activity, especially in terms of energy may be an indicator of the rock mass preconditioning in a long perspective. Proper preconditioning may result in increase of low-energy events number, but at the same time should definitely turn into the decrease in number and magnitude of high-energy seismic events. Blasting and hydrofracturing generate cracks which may induce micro seismic events, but also prevent further energy accumulation in rock mass which decreases rock mass proneness to seismicity. An example of such evaluation has been well presented in the final reports of the NEXGEN-SIMS project.

According to research prepared by KGHM CUPRUM distribution of seismic activity in 2023 in one of the mining panels of Lubin underground copper mines, between January and April 2023, multi-face destress blasting was carried out with modified D&B and the use of electronic detonators (green dots in Figure 3.45). According to the analysis, seismic activity in terms of energy gradually decreased from month to month and in May 2023, high-energy tremors in the analysed mining panel were almost completely eliminated. Due to the temporal lack of availability of people involved in the NEXGEN-SIMS project, in May 2023 the mine operator

switched to using standard D&B patterns again. This resulted in a renewed accumulation of stresses and a sudden increase in the energy of seismic tremors in June 2023. After switching back to a modified D&B pattern, the seismic energy gradually decreased again until the complete elimination of high-energy tremors in December 2023.

Figure 3.45. Seismic activity in G-2 mining panel in 2023.

As shown by the analysis, the use of modified blasting metrics and the use of a data-driven approach contributed largely to the reduction of seismic energy released in the G-2 mining panel in the analysed period. As a result, seismicity in energy terms decreased by 95% in the period January-May 2023 and 97% in the period June-December 2023. Of course, it should be borne in mind that seismic activity is affected by many factors, such as the local geological condition, the exploitation system, extraction depth, etc., therefore it cannot be clearly stated that 100% of the effect obtained was achieved only by implementing modifications to multi-face blasting. However, based solely on data, this impact seems to be clear and research in this scope has to be proceeded further. On the other hand, when analysing the effectiveness of hydrofracturing hypocentral location of seismic events may be a useful tool for tracking the rock mass preconditioning process. When running hydraulic fracturing, once the water pressure exceeds rock strength, cracks are generated, and then microseismic event occurs. Localizing the spatial positions of those events using monitoring will bring information on the cracking range dynamically and rate the effect of hydraulic fracturing. The process of hydraulic fracturing can be manipulated by changing the viscosity of fluids injected into the borehole (Shimizu et al., 2011), controlling the water pressure and adding blasting-based destressing (Huang et al., 2011).

3.7.2.5. *In situ tests*

In addition to continuous monitoring and numerical simulations, the effectiveness of preconditioning can also be estimated based on observations conducted in *in situ* conditions and additional tests aimed at determining the degree of the rock mass destressing.

3.7.2.5.1. Ground penetrating radar surveys

Ground-penetrating radar (GPR) is a geophysical technique that utilises radar pulses in order to imagine the subsurface. This method allows for non-invasive exploration of underground solid medium like rocks by using electromagnetic radiation in the microwave band of the radio spectrum. GPR can detect reflected signals from structures beneath the surface. According to Tooper et al. (2000) ground penetrating radar (GPR) is a suitable method for determining the effect of preconditioning on the rock mass. The electromagnetic pulse emitted by the GPR antenna is reflected by fracture planes, particularly if the cracks are open and the sides of the fractures are coated with the residues from the post-blasting fumes. As a result, the intensity and the depth of fracturing ahead of the mining face may be identified. Then the fracture pattern ahead of a face before and after preconditioning may be compared, which brings a general overview of preconditioning effectiveness. An example of a scan can be seen in Figure 3.46.

Figure 3.46. GPR scan results with preconditioning holes (black stars) and proposed location of additional preconditioning holes (white stars) (Tooper et al., 2000).

As one may observe, the GPR technique allows do efficiently imagine rock mass conditions to the depth of a few meters and may be a useful method for regular evaluation of preconditioning efficiency.

3.7.2.5.2. Face advance and drilling rates

Preconditioning at the deposit level, thanks to the reduction of the stress state in the rocks, should result in a reduction of mining resistance and, consequently, an increase in the progress of mining works. A parameter that can be easily measured is the drilling rate. As noted by Tooper et al. (2000), appropriate preconditioning of the rock mass with the use of explosives made it possible to increase the average face advance per blast by over 50%. The situation is similar in terms of drilling progress. The use of preconditioning using explosives allowed for an increase in drilling progress by 26 to 47%.

3.7.3. Summary

Based on extensive research it may be stated that the effect of preconditioning should be analysed both in space and time. The main mechanism of preconditioning is stress transfer resulting from induced deformations in the

fracture zone ahead of the face. Still, it may be assumed that proper fracturing of rock mass may actually modify the material properties of the rock and increase the effectiveness of drilling works by softening of rock material. Because the stress state changes continuously during the underground excavation process the preconditioning must be integrated permanently into the production cycle in a controlled, well-planned manner. Considering that fact one may observe that there are some possibilities related to the implementation of preconditioning measures in regular mining operations. Properly destressed and well-fractured rockmass definitely will bring safer conditions in a deep underground environment and possibly will ease the excavation process by decreasing the energy required for drilling and crushing of rocks. Still, this approach has to be further developed.

One of the main focuses of the PERSEPHONE project is to investigate the effect of rock preconditioning on the drilling/excavation process. This effect may be reflected as increasing energy efficiency, improving the drilling/excavation performance, or even extending the applicability of excavation machinery to harder and more challenging types of rocks.

It is assumed that the pre-conditioning process of rock may be achieved by means of mechanical/non-mechanical methods depending on the efficiency levels. The scope of this task would be to survey and compare the available technologies for this purpose and perform lab experiments complemented by theoretical/numerical modelling using simulation capabilities in order to prove the selected concepts. Moreover, preconditioning of the rockface, followed by efficient, accurate and strategic drilling would lead to significant reductions in the use of water and electricity at the mining front.

3.8. Hole Deviation Monitoring System

3.8.1. Introduction

Drilling operations are a very common activity in many exploitation processes starting from exploration of the minerals, through exploitation and supporting processes. The drilling process can be employed directly for exploitation purposes e.g. to drill blastholes or as support operation e.g. bolting process, geologic recognition, oil and gas exploitation, drains, holes for hydraulic fracturing etc. In most cases proper orientation and direction of holes are very important to ensure their efficient usage (Laguillo et al., 2022; Bustos et al., 2020; Zongwei & Jiancheng, 2018; Yanshun et al., 2012; Bulant et al, 2007). In this place, it is also noteworthy that some works require long holes i.e. more than few dozen meters in case of blastholes or a few kilometres in case of recognition holes or gas/oil exploitation holes. Thus, it should be aware that deviation can reach a few meters (blastholes) or tens of meters (exploration holes, hydraulic fracturing holes). The importance of problems depends on the purpose of the hole and the level of discrepancy. In the case of exploration of holes knowledge of the real route of holes is very important to credible characterise ore body structure. Hence control of deviation and measurement of the real trajectory of the holes is the key issue to achieve good quality of geologic recognition, exploitation efficiency of gas/oil or proper efficiency of blasting works.

In general view deviation of blastholes can be divided into three groups (Figure 3.47) (Bustos et al., 2020), namely:

- Collar position error,
- Inclination error (inaccurate azimuth), and
- Trajectory deviation (route of holes changes along length, borehole is not straight).

Figure 3.47. Characteristics of different types of deviation (Bustos et al, 2020).

The first two types of deviations are relatively easy to measure due to the fact that these parameters can be measured outside of holes where access is easy. Measuring trajectory is much more complicated because the sensor has to be put into a hole. The trajectory of the hole in the 3D space is generally determined along the hole by three parameters i.e. length, inclination angle and azimuth (Figure 3.48).

Figure 3.48. Parameters of hole surveying (Laguillo et al., 2022).

Modern drilling rigs are equipped with many support systems which control the drilling process to provide an accurate hole path, to support this process many

operations are automated (Epiroc, 2024; Sandvik, 2024). Nevertheless, some deviations of bore holes are still observed (Orive et al., 2017). It is due to impact of many factors i.e. operators' skills, type of rock mass, presence of voids, fractures, length of holes, maintenance of drilling rigs etc. Therefore even in modern drilling rigs hole's deviation problem still exist (Oppong & Agyei, 2020; Navarro et al., 2019; Navarro et al., 2018). An example of real trajectory of blastholes drilled during small underground shaft construction can be seen in Figure 3.49.

Figure 3.49. An example of a real trajectory of vertical blastholes.

Parameters of blastholes were as follows: vertical holes, length 23 m, diameter 64 mm. The maximum deviation at the bottom of holes #1 and #2 was 1.2 m and 0.9 m respectively. It can be seen in Figure 3.49, that the distance between the ends of holes #1 and #2, which was planned 1.1 m in reality reached 2.1 m. Additionally, holes were also inclined in different directions. Knowing the real value of the hole's deviation allowed us to adjust the blasting pattern to the real condition and achieve the satisfied blasting effect. However, it should be aware that inaccuracy of drilling may cause local variations of charge concentration which lead to over- or under-break of excavations. Research carried out by Navarro et al. (2019) showed that in the case of blasting works in tunnels absolute 3-D error reached 0.11 ± 0.03 m/m.

Modern drilling rigs are supported with MWD (Measurement-While-Drilling) systems that provide accurate location of blastholes i.e. collar position, azimuth, inclination and length. These data allow us to calculate the theoretical direction of blastholes and the position of hole's bottom. However, the real trajectory of the blastholes is unknown (Navarro et al., 2019). Calculated, in this way, the hole's path can be displayed by means of different kinds of software developed by producers of drilling rigs like Epiroc, Sandvik or blasting companies like Orica, Maxam or independent software developers. In general, this software is able to process data provided by MWD systems or external hole deviation measurement tools.

Depending on the applied technology, measurement systems can be divided into groups which is shown in Figure 3.50.

Figure 3.50. Types of hole's deviation measurement system.

Direct solutions employ devices which are deployed into the hole to perform measurement. These units employ different types of sensors to determine real hole trajectory, e.g. magnetometers, accelerometers, gyroscopes etc. Depending on the hole type, length and diameter different solutions can be applied. Measurement units can be integrated with drilling machines incorporated with MWD systems or applied as separate devices and measurement is carried out after drilling works.

3.8.2. Indirect hole deviation measurement systems

As was mentioned in the introduction, all modern drilling rigs can be equipped with systems that provide accurate location of blastholes i.e. proper collars' coordinates, azimuths and inclinations of holes direction. These systems are integrated with drilling machines. Current solutions employ laser scanners, inclinometers, accelerometers etc. to yield data for calculation. The typical measurement system is shown in Figure 3.51. This is a well-known technology, which is commonly used in geodesic measurement and GIS (Geographic Information System) systems. There are used normal geometric relationships and geometric data can be calculated and transposed into different reference systems including local mining geodesic systems. In Figure 3.52 blasthole positioning systems are presented (Navarro et al., 2018), where the trajectory of blasthole positioning is calculated according to the equations:

$$X_A = L_A \sin(\alpha) \cos(\beta) \tag{3.1}$$

$$Y_A = L_A \sin(\alpha) \sin(\beta) \tag{3.2}$$

$$Z_A = L_A \cos(\alpha) \tag{3.3}$$

Figure 3.51. Example of a coordination system (Navarro et al., 2018).

Figure 3.52. System of the positioning of blast hole (Navarro et al., 2018).

As was above mentioned these kinds of systems determine the theoretical trajectory of holes. This calculated route of boreholes can be displayed by means of dedicated internal software prepared by producers of rigs or external software developers. In the case of Epiroc and Sandvik company, it is Tunnel Manager or iSURE software accordingly (Epiroc, 2024; Sandvik, 2024). Nonetheless, the real route of blasthole is unknown and even if any deviation occurs cannot be incorporated into current blasting parameters.

3.8.3. Direct hole deviation measurement systems

Instead of indirect measurement systems, there are also direct systems that can be used to measure real hole deviation. These solutions employ additional devices which are moved through the full length of the hole to perform the measurement. These sensors employ different types of technology to determine real hole trajectory e.g. magnetometers, accelerometers, gyroscopes etc. Depending on the hole type, length and diameter different solutions can be applied. In general, external hole deviation systems can be divided into two groups:

- Magnetic and gravitational systems, and
- Inertial systems (Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) sensors).

3.8.3.1. Magnetic and gravitational systems

The old version of deviation measurement tools, which are still in use, are devices based on magnetic sensors and inclinometers. Magnetic sensors are used natural Earth magnetic field for north orientation and have some important drawbacks. Users should be aware that these kinds of sensors can be affected by magnetic ore or some electrical devices in the surrounding area. The following sensors are employed to determine the necessary parameters:

- magnetic sensors for azimuth,
- accelerometers and inclinometers for inclination, and
- length of cable (rods) is used for orientation along the hole.

All these sensors are arranged in three orthogonal directions (Figure 3.53).

Figure 3.53. Arrangement of sensors in measurement module.

These kinds of devices are still present on the market e.g. REFLEX EZ-AQ, Probe Mk3, INCLIS 30. The main parameters of the listed devices are shown in Table 2.

Table 3.2. Main parameters of some survey devices (magnetic/gravitational).

Parameter	REFLEX EZ-AQ™ *	Micro Probe Mk3*	INCLIS-30*
Inclination range	±90°		±90°
Dip accuracy	±0.25°	±0.25°	±0.2°
Azimuth range	360°	360°	360°
Azimuth accuracy	±0.35°	±1.0°	±0.5°
Diameter	35 mm	35 mm	30 mm
Survey type	Multi-shot	Multi-shot	Continuous

*Sources of data (Micro Probe, 2024; Reflex, 2024; INCLIS, 2024).

These kinds of tools are manual handling therefore their application is limited. Below there is an example of measurement of this method, where REFLEX EZ-AQ device was applied. In this case, deviation was measured in up-holes with an average length of 12 m and diameter of 76 mm. Long-term survey activity allows to collect data from more than 2,000 holes (Bustos et al., 2020). Deviation distribution data from the whole dataset is shown in Figure 3.54.

Figure 3.54. An example of deviation’s distribution (Bustos et al., 2020).

3.8.3.2. Gyro-based systems (IMU sensors)

In the last decade, new types of measurement probes have become more popular during deviation surveys. These new devices are equipped with gyroscopes and accelerometers (IMU sensors) to determine the orientation of the probe in the borehole during the measurement process. IMU sensors used in measurement devices are often composed of triaxial accelerometers and gyroscopes (in some cases magnetometers are also used). In the case of such devices the following sensors are used for the measurement the orientation parameters:

- gyroscopic sensors for azimuth,
- accelerometers for inclination, and
- length of cable (rods) is used for orientation along the hole.

Gyroscopes can be related to the predefined direction or North-seeking. The North-seeking gyros are more complicated and more costly (Laguillo et al., 2022). On the other hand, gyro-based devices are more accurate in relation to magnetic systems. The main parameters of some available on-the-market devices are shown in Table 3.3.

Table 3.3. Main parameters of some survey devices (gyroscopic)

Parameter	REFLEX GYRO SPRINT - IQ™ *	Carlson BORETRAC® 2 *	GyroLogic™ Evo *
Inclination	±90°	±90°	±90°
Dip accuracy	±0.3°	±0.1°	±0.15°
Azimuth range	360°	360°	360°
Azimuth accuracy	±1°	±0.1°	±0.5°
Diameter	42.5 mm	40 mm	35 mm
Survey type	Multi-shot, continuous	Multi-shot	Multi-shot, continuous

*Sources of data (Reflex, 2024; Carlson, 2024; GyroLogic, 2024).

This technology can be also applied in long directional holes (Eren & Suicmez, 2020; Škrjanc & Vulić, 2016). This kind of applications of IMU sensors was described by Yang et al. (2019). As was mentioned before, knowledge about accurate hole trajectory in 3D space is also a key issue in the oil-gas industry. It concerns in particular part of holes with horizontal trajectory. One of the main problems in this type of drilling technology is the limitation of data transmission which is due to extreme environmental conditions. To solve this problem integrated measurement system incorporated IMU sensors can be applied (Yang et al., 2019).

In gyro-based systems also fibre optic gyroscopes (FOG) can be utilised to measure deviation parameters. Tests performed by Noureldin et al. (2004), Yanshun et al. (2012) and Zhang & Lin (2016) were showed that this technology can be also implemented in hole deviation measurement. In this test, where single-axis FOG was applied, an error for a dip angle larger than 45° was less than 0.1°, for 20° it increased up to 0.3°, which is still a very low level. In this test sensor was placed inside the bearing assembly close to the drill bit which is very promising to provide reliable data which are gathered by the MWD surveying system for directional holes (Noureldin et al., 2004).

It's noteworthy to mention that inertial technology can be also applied to measure the real route of underground pipelines and this kind of structure (Wang & Song,

2012). Looking into this technology it seems that is quite well developed into oil-gas industry or geologic long holes where rotary drilling is applied. In this case module with measurement devices is integrated with drilling devices and is placed close to the drill bit. In many cases, data can be gathered in a real-time manner and transferred to the surface. Nonetheless, this technology is still insufficient for drilling long blastholes using percussion drill technology where shock and vibration levels are very high. According to the authors' knowledge, at the moment there is only one commercially available system called S-Sense developed by Robit company which allows to measurement real path of the blasting hole during the drilling process. For the time being the system was tested in surface application and cannot be used underground for up-holes application. The system is available for holes with minimum diameters of 70 mm, with an accuracy of $\pm 0,5^\circ$ for inclination and $\pm 1,0^\circ$ for azimuth (Robit, 2024).

Still, most blasting hole measurements are performed manually by workers. Hence, this method is unpractical, time-consuming and can be dangerous, especially in the case of long up-holes. To avoid these limitations and make this process more efficient and safer some innovative solutions were developed. As it is very common practice to use explosives charging units to load blastholes in underground mines, this kind of unit was equipped with a sensor that was connected to the hoist and pushed into holes. During this process, the real trajectory of blastholes was determined. In this case, Riosensor was used and developed by MAXAM company which allowed to measure deviation in an automatic way. The system was tested in an underground mine with up-holes up to 23 m. The following parameters were measured: depth, inclination and azimuth (Orive et al., 2017). A similar system was described by Laguillo et al. (2022). In this case, the explosives charging unit was incorporated with IMU and MEMS (Micro-Electro-Mechanical System) sensor. Some parameters of these sensors are shown in Table 3.4. In this solution, a loading hose was used as a probe carrier along the hole.

It seems that the process of automation of deviation measurement will be continued due to safety reasons and efficiency purposes. Real-time measurement and data analysis can be used during the explosives loading process to adjust blasting parameters to the real trajectory of blastholes. This kind of system also increases safety level due to the fact that the operator is able to measure the hole's deviation from the safety location. The layout of this kind of system is shown in Figure 3.55.

Table 3.4. Parameters of probe sensors

Dimensions (length, diameter, weight)	900 mm, 50 mm, 4.5 kg	
Protection grade	IP 68	
IMU sensor	Triaxial gyroscopes + Triaxial accelerometers + Kalman Filter	
Measurement range	Accelerometer $\pm 8g$	Gyroscope $300^\circ/s$
Azimuth range	360°	
Inclination range	$\pm 90^\circ$	
Sensor resolution	$< 0.2^\circ$	

Figure 3.55. Layout of borehole surveying system (Laguillo et al., 2022).

3.8.4. Conclusions

It may be stated that hole deviation is still an inherent part of drilling works in many exploration activities despite undoubted progress in drilling technology, hence measurement of this parameter is still much desired. Nevertheless, current available technology should be still developed to meet increasing mining industry requirements. In the case of directional drilling, there are some effective and accurate solutions to perform effective trajectory measurement. However, particularly in the field of underground blasting works where percussive drilling is applied to prepare blasting holes, a lack of efficient measurement technology is visible, despite some positive trials and innovations. Currently, none of these technologies is commonly used. Additionally, a significant part of measurement units available on the market are manually operated which is highly ineffective due to time consumption and safety issues. Therefore more effort should be placed into developing measurement devices which can be incorporated directly into the drilling process. It seems that the recent development of IMU and MEMS technology creates new possibilities for new types of measurement devices. Development should be also focused on the automation of the process and integration with the drilling machines, which allows to do that faster, safer and more accurately particularly during the drilling of long up-holes. Other solutions can cover the integration of measurement systems with explosives loading units which are often employed in the underground exploitation process.

3.9. Real-time Rock Characterisation

Proper recognition of mining areas is a key issue in the process of safe and efficient mining operations. Knowing rock mass parameters helps engineers select and adjust mining methods, ground support, blasting parameters etc. to the local

conditions. This data, collected and analysed in real-time can be employed immediately to modify the mining operation to improve the exploitation process. Therefore, there is a need to determine many parameters that can describe an interesting part of the rock mass it concerns mechanical properties, geophysical properties and geologic structures. This data can be obtained from laboratory tests, special geophysics research, geologic recognition etc. Most of these kinds of tests are complicated, expensive and time-consuming, hence each new source of valuable data is strongly desired for the mining and exploration industry. One of the sources of this kind of data is machines working in the mine.

The exploitation of raw materials in deep mines engages lots of different machines which are utilised in different stages of mining operations. Among others, they are applied to the following processes:

- exploitation,
- transport,
- ore conditioning, and
- ground support process.

Depending on the ore type and their geologic structure different types of mining methods are applied which implicate specific types of machines are utilised. In the constant process of developing new machines, there are implemented lots of systems and sensors to optimise working parameters in order to maintain the health of important modules and avoid costly damages. It means that modern machines are able to monitor and collect lots of different types of data. At the first stage of machine's development, installed systems, supported by sensors, were focused on the management and control of mechanical parameters e.g. engines, transmissions, gears, compressors etc. These data are also utilised to automatize the drilling process, which is also a very visible trend in the mining industry.

3.9.1. Data collected by Measurement-While-Drilling systems

Among different types of machines, there are specific groups that are often used in the exploitation process and have direct contact with the rock mass. These machines are different types of drilling rigs and bolting machines. Drilling rigs can be applied directly in the production process where they are used to boring blast holes or to drill geologic recognition holes (e.g. core holes), hence through direct contact between bit and rock, rock mass properties can be determined along prepared holes. It may be stated according to numerous authors that the physical description of the interaction between rock and bits is very complicated and depends on many factors related to the rocks, presence of discontinuities, water, bit types, temperatures, etc., therefore in many cases relations between parameters are empirically derived (Rai et al., 2015).

All these types of modern machines can be equipped with support systems that are able to control working parameters and gather data. These kinds of systems are called measurement-while-drilling (MWD) interchangeable monitor-while-drilling (MWD) and logging-while-drilling (LWD) (Navarro et al., 2018; Rai et al., 2016; Hatherly et al., 2015; Rai et al., 2015; Li et al., 2014; Segui & Higgins, 2002). This kind of a system is able to measure many factors (Table 3.5).

Table 3.5. Main MWD parameters

Parameter	Abbreviation	Unit
Penetration rate	PR	m/s
Torque	T	Nm
Weight on bit (thrust)	WOB	N
Rotary speed	RS	rev/min
Rotation pressure	RP	Pa
Specific energy of drilling	SED	J/m ³
Modulated specific energy	SEM	-
Water flow	WF	m ³ /s
Water pressure	WP	Pa
Feed pressure	FP	Pa
Hammer pressure	HP	Pa
Dump pressure	DP	Pa
Sound level	SL	Pa

These parameters can be used for geological characterisation of the rock mass and rock mechanical parameters (Khanal et al, 2020; Hatherly et al., 2015; Leung & Scheduling, 2015; Li et al., 2014). The abovementioned parameters can be divided into three groups i.e. directly measured parameters (e.g. torque, rotation speed, feed pressure etc.), calculated parameters (e.g. penetration rate, specific energy etc.) and inferred parameters (e.g. blastability index) (Segui & Higgins, 2002). Specific energy (SED) is described as energy which is needed to drill unit of volume of the rock, and can be expressed (Li et al., 2014):

$$SED = \frac{F}{A} + \frac{2\pi \cdot T}{A \cdot z} \quad (3.4)$$

Where: F – thrust, T – torque, z – penetration per resolution, A – cross-section area of the hole.

Modulated specific energy (SEM) can be defined as the product of SED and the logistic function of rotational work fraction (Leung & Scheduling, 2015).

MWD systems utilise many types of sensors like pressure sensors, movement transducers, electromagnetic sensors etc. supported by recorders, microcomputers and other peripheral accessories. Briefly, the MWD system consists of two main parts, namely hardware, which measures different parameters by means of sensors and software, which analyse and interpret collected data (Figure 3.56).

Figure 3.56. MWD systems structure (Li et al, 2014).

An example of a drilling rig that was fully equipped with an MWD system was Atlas Copco WE3 boomer. The system was able to log, with a maximum sampling rate 2.5 Hz, the following data: hole depth, penetration rate, percussive pressure, feed pressure, damping pressure, rotation speed, rotation pressure, water flow and water pressure. This solution was used to characterise rock mass conditions during tunnel construction (Eldert et al., 2021; Eldert et al., 2020). Another type of system is able to obtain a 1 cm resolution with a sampling rate of 400 Hz (Babaei Khorzoughi et al., 2018).

3.9.2. Rock parameters determined by MWD systems

It should be taken into consideration that MWD parameters depend on the rock mass but can be also affected by other factors like sensors' calibration and drill rig maintenance. The process of drilling, which covers changing different parameters, affects MWD data. Therefore, the process of analysis of gathered data must cover proper data processing like filtering, detection and removal of outliers, correction of systematic variation etc. (Navarro et al., 2018; Babaei Khorzoughi & Hall, 2016). An example of data processing is shown in Figure 3.57.

Figure 3.57. Flow chart of MWD data processing (Navarro et al., 2018).

In general view four different methods can be utilised to yield rock properties: regression analysis, theoretical analysis, AI models (machine learning) (Bout et al., 2021; Eldert et al., 2020; Li et al., 2014). Advanced AI models are increasingly used in MWD data analysis to obtain more accurate results. They are applied to different machine learning algorithms like logistic regression, artificial neural network, random forest, extreme gradient boosting or support vector machine, fuzzy logic etc. (Zhong et al., 2020a; Kadkhodaie-Ilkhchi et al., 2010).

Type of rock parameters and geologic conditions that can be measured and revealed by MWD systems:

- voids, fracture zone, faults (Babaei Khorzoughi et al., 2018; Hatherly et al., 2015),
- rock layers (lithology) (Hatherly et al., 2015),
- RQD (Rock Quality Designation) (Navarro et al., 2018; Schunnesson, 1996),
- RQI (Rock Quality Index) (Rai et al., 2014),
- UCS (Kahraman et al., 2015),
- tensile strength (Kahraman et al., 2015),
- point load strength (Kahraman et al., 2015),
- sonic velocity (Hatherly et al., 2015), and
- P-wave velocity (Basarir, 2019).

It must be highlighted that models applied to the determination of the rock parameters have to be calibrated to adjust the model to the site (Segui & Higgins, 2002). It should be also mentioned that calibration of the sensors is also very important it depends on both the sensors of the mechanic parameters above-mentioned and the sensors that are involved in the coordination system (Navarro et al., 2018). All the above-mentioned parameters that might be measured during the drilling process allow for the collection of data that can be used in different configurations to calculate and determine rock parameters. There must be also the awareness that practically all of the machine producers develop their own MWD systems both in the type of used sensors and analysis methods.

3.9.2.1. Void, fracture zone and fault detection

MWD data can be successfully utilised for fracture and voids detection (Ghosh et al., 2017; Hatherly et al., 2015; Li et al., 2014). It may be noted that many of experienced drill rig operators, even when applying old types of machines are able to detect these kinds of structures by observation of some working parameters e.g. problems with water flow, changing rotation speed etc. Current applied systems are able to detect these kinds of geological structures automatically with connection to the coordination system which indicates the direct location of the voids/fractures. An example of changes in drilling parameters affected by the fracture zone is shown in Figure 3.58. Babaei Khorzoughi et al. (2018) conducted research aimed at the detection of fracture zones and their dip angle on the base of rotation speed and torque. Results showed that in some cases it is possible to identify open fractures of blastholes close to orthogonal angles. Detection of the voids and joints is also possible by the measure of sound level during the drilling process (Rostami et al., 2015).

Figure 3.58. Drilling parameters affected by fracture zones (Schunnesson, 1996).

3.9.2.2. Lithology detection, strata boundaries

Analysis of parameters recorded by MWD systems allows also us to determine the rock type and boundaries between rock strata. Depending on the applied MWD system, different parameters and their relationship may be employed to detect rock type and strata boundaries (Silversides & Melkumyan, 2021; Zhong et al, 2020; Chen & Yue, 2015; Li et al., 2014). Leung & Scheduling (2015), proposed a methodology, where SEM was applied to detect coal-seam strata. In this case, MWD system was employed in rotary drilling. According to Zhong et al. (2020), data collected by MWD systems may be successfully used to identify coal strata. In this case, the analysis was employed an AI algorithm using PR, RS, T and WOB parameters. The outcome of the analysis was very promising, the coal identification rate achieved above 90%. However, it should be stated that good results depend on the quantity and quality of data.

3.9.2.3. RQD (Rock Quality Designation)

Rock Quality Designation (RQD) is one of the parameters that is used to classify rocks. RQD is defined as the sum of the length of intact pieces of core (> 10 cm) to the total length of core expressed in percentages (Schunnesson, 1996) (see equation below):

$$RQD = 100 \cdot \frac{\sum L_i}{L_t} \quad (3.5)$$

Where: RQD – Rock Quality Designation (%), L_i – length of i -pieces of core (length above 10 cm), L_t – total length of core.

As was pointed out by Schunnesson (1996) and Eldert et al. (2021) observed some correlation between drilling parameters and the RQD index. The approach

proposed by Eldert et al. (2021) was based on the penetration rate (PR) and rotation pressure (RP) represented by their combined and normalised value. Research conducted during tunnel construction showed a correlation with MWD data (Figure 3.59). In this case, multilinear regression and Levenberg-Marquardt method were applied.

Figure 3.59. The plot of combined normalised penetration rate and rotation pressure and RQD (Elder et al, 2021).

3.9.2.4. RQI (Rock Quality Index)

Another parameter that may be derived from MWD systems is the Rock Quality Index (RQI) which can be expressed by formula (for rotary drilling) (Rai et al., 2016):

$$RQI = \frac{E_h \cdot t}{L} \quad (3.6)$$

Where: E_h – hydraulic feed pressure, t – drilling time, L – hole depth.

As can be seen from the formula, the drilling parameter that is taken into consideration in this example is hydraulic feed pressure. The accuracy of this parameter depends on the input data, therefore proper maintenance and calibration of sensors are needed. It should be also considered to change of penetration rate due to bit wear. It's also noteworthy that this parameter can be helpful with blasting design due to its possible correlation with the powder factor (Rai et al., 2014; Rai et al., 2016).

3.9.2.5. UCS (Uniaxial Compressive Strength)

Uniaxial compressive strength (USC) is one of the main rock strength parameters that is used to describe rock strength in many geotechnical models. It is also employed very often in numerical models to characterise rock mass. Hence knowing the value distribution of this parameter in the rock mass can help increase the accuracy of these models. This parameter can be also yielded from MWD systems. The way of estimation of UFC from measured drilling parameters was proposed by Basarir et al. (2014), where the value of penetration rate was employed to determine UCS value. Analysis was performed using some multiple

regression models and AI model (in this case it was an Adaptive Neuro-fuzzy Inference System – ANFIS). Gowida et al. (2021), proposed AI models based on more drilling parameters e.g. ROP, WOB, torque etc. In this model correlation (R-value) between predicted USC value and actual reached 0.98. Another model was proposed by Ma et al. (2023), where drilling data were obtained from bolter machines. In turn, Ding et al. (2021) proposed an approach based on the specific energy (Figure 3.60). Prediction models were also described by Gamal et al. (2021) and Hiba et al. (2022).

Figure 3.60. Relationship between drilling specific energy and UCS (Ding et al., 2021).

3.9.2.6. Tensile strength

Park & Kim (2020) showed that parameters measured during drilling may be focused on the penetration rate (PR). This parameter was used in the normalised form i.e. Adjusted Penetration Rate (APR). The regression model prepared after tests showed the correlation between APR value and tensile strength (Figure 3.61).

Figure 3.61. Regression model of APR versus tensile strength (Park & Kim, 2020).

Better results can be obtained by the AI analysis. A test performed by Hiba et al. (2022) showed that AI analysis (ANN algorithm) allowed us to achieve very good

results ($R > 0.95$) in predicting tensile strength based on the MWD parameters (Figure 3.62).

Figure 3.62. Results of AI analysis (Hiba et al., 2022).

3.9.2.7. Poisson's ratio

As was pointed out by Sidding et al. (2021), data gathered by MWD systems (weight on bit, penetration rate, pump rate, feed pressure, drilling rate, flow rate and torque) and analysed by machine learning tools can be used to obtain Poisson's ratio. In this case, two algorithms were used, namely artificial neural network (ANN) and adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS). It's noteworthy to mention that in this case correlation value between actual and predicted value reaches more than 95%.

3.9.2.8. Other parameters

It should be stated that MWD systems, their configurations and analysis methods can be also employed to determine other parameters, for instance, RMR (Rock Mass Rating) which is used during tunnel construction (Galende-Hernández et al., 2018), estimation of chemical assay values (Khushaba et al., 2022), Bond work index (BWI) (Park & Kim, 2020), sonic velocity (Hatherly et al., 2015), P-wave velocity (Basarir, 2019) and others. Producers of drilling rigs developed also on their own parameters e.g. Epiroc implemented Rock Hardness Index and Rock Fracturing Index (Epiroc, 2024). It should be stated that parameters implemented by producers of drilling machines are, in most cases, relative not absolute.

3.9.3. Conclusions

There is a fact that modern drilling machines are equipped with lots of sensors that are able to collect data about many working parameters to optimise the drilling process in a real-time manner. According to many researchers quoted in this paper data gathered by MWD systems can be used to determine many of the absolute rock parameters. These kinds of data can be easily used in the process of geotechnical mining management e.g. numerical modelling of rock mass

behaviour. Still, it seems that this source of information is not utilised effectively. Nowadays, to yield absolute parameters from MWD data needs advanced data processing analysis which is time consumed process. Additionally, due to the fact that rock structures are very complex and depend on many local conditions, there is a need to calibrate system to each site, to determine the relationship between MWD parameters and absolute rock parameters. It means that some obstacles must be overcome to speed up this process and finally achieve a stream of data in real-time.

Looking into recent developments in this field it seems that there is very promising technology in this area, namely AI processing and analysis methods. Development of these models is very fast, and the increasing volume of reliable data allow to improve models and achieve more accurate and reliable models to calculate rock parameters. In the next steps, these systems should be integrated with drilling machines to create a comprehensive system which is able to measure, collect and process data to calculate desired rock parameters at the end of the process. Knowing local rock parameters allows to optimise the exploitation process from the geomechanical perspective locally.

4. Existing Roadmaps in Deep Mining

At this stage there is no existent public roadmap specifically targeting deep mining, the subject in most roadmaps includes, and is not limited to, new technologies in the mining industry, application to existing mines and mining conditions, re-opening of abandoned mines. Therefore, in this chapter, we analyse roadmaps targeting new mining exploration and production technologies from European projects, industrial organizations, and national policies.

4.1. ROBOMINERS

ROBOMINERS is a 4.5 years H2020 project, which ended in November 2023, that aimed to develop a Bio-Inspired, Modular and Reconfigurable Robot Miner, equipped with selective mining perception and mining tools for small and difficult-to-access deposits (RoboMiners, 2024). A consortium that includes geoscientists, roboticists and engineers worked to build a modular robot prototype (Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 4 to 5), design a new mining system via simulation and modelling and to use the prototype to study and advance future research on different areas of robotics and raw materials alike (Lopes et al., 2020).

The ROBOMINERS project completed two roadmaps for the years 2030 and 2050 (Lopes et al., 2023), aiming to guide the technology line to reach TRL-6/7 by 2030 and TRL 8-9 by 2050. The roadmaps were derived from the outputs of WP8 work and two road mapping workshops with internal and external experts contributing to the vision for the future. The main focus of the roadmaps is on research and technology, aiming to provide a structured and adaptable guide towards real testing and commercialization of the ROBOMINERS technology line.

4.1.1. Key components and objectives

The roadmaps are structured into four layers of assessment: Exploration, Development and Operation, Robot-miner, and PESTEL (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal), each sub-divided into specific topics. The immediate research plan focused on the current design and recommendations for each component, while the medium to long-term roadmaps are built under four layers of assessment. The roadmaps for 2030 and 2050 detail actions and targets to elevate the ROBOMINERS technology to TRL-6-7 and TRL-8-9, with a focus on exploration, development, operation, robot-miner, and PESTEL aspects.

The roadmaps are designed with the help of data gathered from other foresight-adapted tools and methods run throughout the project, including focus groups, horizon scanning, Delphi surveys, visioning, and preparation for pilots, as well as two dedicated road mapping workshops.

The roadmaps for 2030 and 2050 outline specific actions and targets for each thematic area. Notably, the Exploration roadmap focuses on optimising sensing capabilities and real-time data analysis, the Development and Operation roadmap centres on initiating operations in accessible sites and integrating sophisticated geophysical tools, the Robot-miner roadmap aims to achieve a TRL-6/7 for software, hardware, and robot capabilities, and the PESTEL roadmap focuses on navigating through permitting issues and leveraging government regulations.

Overall, the roadmaps provide a structured and adaptable guide towards real testing and commercialization of the ROBOMINERS technology line, considering various political, economic, and socio-environmental facets.

4.1.2. Gaps and challenges

The roadmaps aim to identify the gap between the current state of the ROBOMINERS Consortium and the envisioned technology state by 2030 and 2050, providing ideas on how to bridge this gap and what the technology developers should do. The roadmaps aim to provide a timeline and direct support for the implementation of the first ROBOMINERS pilots by 2030, while also supporting breakthrough research for the further development of the technology line by 2050.

Key findings include limitations of the Production Tool in hard rock scenarios and the need for alternative tools, the relevance of Geophysical Instruments for real-time analysis, innovative approaches for Robot Assembly and Operation, robustness of Movement and Bioinspiration in harsh environments, the value of the Transport System for ore transport, the importance of the Mining Ecosystem for remote or hazardous mining operations, and the essential role of Autonomy and Navigation for the robot's efficiency.

Table 4.1. PESTEL (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal considerations)

Challenges	Priorities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Navigating through permitting and leveraging government regulations to facilitate ROBOMINERS technology adoption. • Establishing ethical guidelines for autonomy, catering to social needs, and propelling political and social acceptance by demonstrating technological robustness. • Reducing operational and capital expenditure, elevating commercial applications, broadening collaborations, and bringing private funding into technological refinement and development. • Minimising environmental impact, securing a social license to operate, and adhering to responsible mining practices. • Addressing political and legal challenges, particularly in the context of permitting and regulatory environments, to facilitate technology adoption. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing a viable business model, ensuring the creation and operation of a spin-off company, securing both public and private funding, and striving towards achieving operational profitability and commercial operation. • Elevating the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) to 8/9 by the early 2030s through tangible pilots and real-environment tests, while ensuring the technology is adaptable, resilient, and applicable in diverse mining scenarios. • Enhancing sensing capabilities and data analysis for efficient navigation and material assessment, particularly in challenging mining conditions and for accessing small, remote mineral deposits. • Initiating operations at accessible sites, integrating advanced geophysical tools, and laying foundational steps towards a robot-driven mining infrastructure. • Addressing the political and legal challenges, particularly in the context of permitting and regulatory

	environments, to facilitate technology adoption.
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Table 4.2. Challenges and priorities related to exploration

Challenges	Priorities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The need for constant research, development, and testing of new tools, methods, and capabilities to achieve a commercial state by 2050. • Integration of exploration with other aspects of operation, development, robot-miner, and PESTEL, including the establishment of underground labs for quick analysis, digital twin deposits for informed exploration, and environmental safety during exploration and production. • Addressing political and legal challenges, particularly in the context of permitting and regulatory environments, to facilitate technology adoption. • Avoid putting resources into research and development of automatized arms and in-situ diagnosis, as suggested by experts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhancing sensing capabilities and data analysis for efficient navigation and material assessment, particularly in challenging mining conditions and for accessing small, remote mineral deposits. • Fostering predictive geochemical models, integrating real-time exploration methods with various geological scenarios, and emphasizing exploration as an inherent aspect of mine design. • Developing and incorporating an array of sensing technologies and navigation software, including real-time analyses and diverse sensor technologies, to enhance mineralogical knowledge and precision in mineral extraction. • Advancing exploration technology to allow the use of gained exploration data to update available local and regional geological models, granting a better understanding of geology and mining possibilities.

Table 4.3. Challenges and priorities in the scope of Development and Operation

Challenges	Priorities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Navigating through complex geological structures and transitioning towards extreme environments such as deep sea, ultra-deep deposits, and even outer space by 2050. • Developing a fully integrated, robot-maintained mining ecosystem and achieving a highly digitized operational model incorporating blockchain verification and Virtual Reality support. • Advancing mining methods towards alternative, innovative, and socially acceptable approaches, including novel concepts like the "queen bee" strategy and operations under extreme conditions. • Maturing into a sophisticated, intelligent, and environmentally considerate mining operation, including advanced processing technologies and innovative slurry transport mediums. • Addressing political and legal challenges, particularly in the context of permitting and regulatory environments, to facilitate technology adoption. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commencing operations in accessible sites and integrating geophysical tools by 2030, with a focus on navigating through complex geological structures, and expanding operational horizons to extreme environments by 2050. • Developing a robot-driven mining infrastructure by 2030, evolving into a fully integrated, robot-maintained ecosystem by 2050. • Advancing data processing, machine learning applications, and information and communications technology integrations by 2030, evolving into a highly digitized, blockchain-verified, and Virtual Reality-supported operational model by 2050. • Enhancing production capabilities in hard rock environments by 2030, advancing towards alternative, innovative, and socially acceptable mining methods by 2050. • Focusing on flexible conveyance and tethered operations alongside pre-processing mechanisms by 2030, maturing into a sophisticated, intelligent, and environmentally considerate mining operation by 2050, with advanced processing technologies and innovative slurry transport mediums.

Table 4.4. Challenges and priorities in scope of Robot-miner utilisation

Challenges	Priorities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designing a robot-miner that is adaptable to different mining environments, including extreme conditions such as deep-sea and ultra-deep deposits, and ensuring its resilience when facing problems and challenges. • Developing a fully integrated, robot-maintained mining ecosystem that is environmentally friendly, reliable, and adaptable to different conditions. • Addressing the need for flexible and specialised robots, each tailored for specific tasks, and ensuring the robot-miner's capabilities and adaptability to different mining scenarios. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Achieving a TRL-6/7 for software, hardware, and robot capabilities by 2030, with a focus on developing autonomy, refining software and hardware design, and testing prototypes in mining settings. • Focusing on the development of diverse robot versions, power and control architectures, and tolerance in electronics and hydraulic systems to transition towards more specialised robots by 2030. • Enhancing communication and collaboration capabilities among robot-miners, ensuring redundancy, reliability, and durability of systems,

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overcoming the limitations of the current robot-miner design, such as the pumping system, and improving its overall technology line to achieve higher TRLs by 2030 and beyond. • Securing public and private funding to support the commercialization and operationalization of the robot-miner, as well as obtaining a social license to operate and address environmental impact concerns. 	<p>and enabling high-level robotic capabilities such as swarm robotics and predictive maintenance by 2050.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initiating operations in accessible sites, integrating sophisticated geophysical tools, and developing ore path planning and scaling robot-miner communications by 2030, with a long-term goal of continuous operation and developing a financially viable operational model by 2050. • Ensuring the robot-miner's efficiency through self-reconfiguration, deploying technologies on real robots, and extensive testing, with a shift towards commercial deployment in collaboration with private companies by 2030.
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4.2. VERAM

The VERAM project, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 program, aimed to develop a comprehensive research and innovation roadmap for European raw materials up to 2050 (VERAM, 2024). The roadmap, a key deliverable of the project, was the result of inclusive participation from over 400 stakeholders, including associations and organizations across the raw materials sector. It addressed future trends such as digitalisation and sustainability, with a focus on boosting technological leadership and innovation capacity in Europe (Wall et al., 2018). The roadmap identified four priority areas and nine research and innovation areas, encompassing specific activities to meet the needs of the raw materials community and address societal challenges. The roadmap aims to guide future research and innovation plans at both European and national levels, particularly in the context of Horizon Europe.

4.2.1. Key components and objectives

The roadmap identifies four priority areas and nine research and innovation areas, focusing on fostering a sustainable supply of raw materials, resource-efficient processing, raw materials in new products and applications, and closing material loops through recycling. It encompasses 178 concrete research and innovation activities, aiming to address future trends shaped by digitalisation, sustainability, and evolving consumer behaviour while boosting European leadership in technology and competitiveness.

The key components and objectives can be further detailed as follows:

- a) Priority Area 1: Increase the Efficiency of Recovery Processes and Product Life-Cycle Optimization
 - Focus on optimising and redesigning the entire product life cycle, including product design, manufacturing, use, and end-of-life (EOL) processes.
 - Actions aimed at increasing the efficiency of recovery processes and promoting more successful reuse and recycling of complex products.

- Striving for a better balance between costs and benefits in the recycling loop.
- b) Priority Area 2: Successful Reuse and Recycling of Complex Products
- Emphasis on developing knowledge and tools that enable successful reuse and recycling of complex products.
 - Actions aimed at developing novel materials and integrating them into designs for substituting critical materials.
 - Development of prototypes of new materials containing construction waste for use in other applications with similar characteristics.
- c) Priority Area 3: Strike a Better Balance Between Costs and Benefits in the Recycling Loop
- Focus on developing applications that allow the use of secondary materials with higher concentrations of impurities or degraded molecules, offering new market opportunities for recycles.
 - Actions aimed at increasing the durability of construction materials and developing viable and suitable recycling technologies to anticipate the spreading of potentially disruptive technologies and innovative products in advanced applications.
- d) Priority Area 4: Development of Material Applications and Markets
- Rationale for product manufacturing evolution, emphasizing high performance, high quality, competitive cost, and short product development time.
 - Focus on developing models and simulation tools for new product design approaches and associated new production technologies to obtain greater functionality from less material and energy input.
 - Emphasis on developing tools and systems that enable information exchange on product design, architecture, and composition along the value chain, for increased integration of end-of-life management of the product's value chain and for enhanced impact and efficiency of recycling processes.

4.2.2. Gaps and challenges

One of the main challenges includes the difficulty in defining the vision for 2050 and the required activities, particularly in the context of stakeholder workshops. The need to align concepts and terms used by different sectors within the raw materials value chains, as well as the challenges in visualizing the complex pathway of the raw materials value chains were also addressed.

More in details, the challenges include:

- **Integration of Stakeholder Input:** The integration of stakeholder input into the roadmap draft involved a complex process, including verifying track changes, integrating proposals into consistent chapters, and addressing comments made by stakeholders. The raw material sector partners involved in the project used different concepts and terms to describe their core activities, causing challenges in analysing the results and defining suitable terms and illustrations for both sectors and their value chains.
- **Defining Long-Term Vision and Activities:** This challenge was particularly evident in determining the right terms suitable for both sectors and defining the right illustrations for the sectors and their value chains. The

workshop participants mainly contributed to revising the expected activities towards 2030, indicating the difficulty in establishing a clear long-term vision for the raw materials sector.

- **Complex Recycling and Material Quality:** The complexity of recycling and the increasing demand for purer raw material qualities to manufacture goods was the main highlight. The recycling industry faces difficulties in keeping pace with the shortening of technology and product life cycles, as well as the introduction of disruptive technologies in various sectors such as photovoltaics, packaging, ICT, batteries, and electronics. Additionally, there is a need to develop strategies to make materials more resistant to degradation during recycling loops, indicating the challenges in maintaining material quality throughout the recycling process.

4.3. CHPM2030

The CHPM2030 project aimed at developing and implementing a combined geothermal energy and mineral extraction technology for 2030, with full-scale commercial applications envisioned by 2050 (CHPM2030, 2024). The project achieved its goal this through exploration, development, operation, and market strategies, as well as stakeholder engagement and funding opportunities. The project also involved the identification of potential pilot areas, the development of a harmonized study area evaluation template, and the coordination of future technological component research. Additionally, the project aimed to create joint initiatives for further exploration, generate models for targeting exploration, and establish guidelines for the selection of geophysical data processing.

During the project were carried out two different roadmaps for 2030 and 2050, outlining the strategy and development of the Combined Heat, Power, and Metal (CHPM) technology for the years 2030 and 2050, with the aim to set the ground for pilot implementation of the CHPM technology, with the first pilots and commercial applications envisioned in 2030 and 2050, respectively (Miklovicz et al., 2019).

4.3.1. Key components and objectives

The CHPM component roadmap provides insights into the current technological components, immediate research plans for 2025, pilot research plans for 2030, and long-term objectives for 2050. Preparation for future pilots investigates potential pilot areas in Europe and provides detailed exploration plans for specific regions, focusing on stakeholder engagement and funding opportunities. The overall CHPM concept explores the feasibility of combining geothermal energy with mineral extraction and identifies targets, actions, signposts, and wild cards related to exploration, development, operation, and market, all linked to the CHPM technology.

4.3.2. Gaps and challenges

The relatively low TRL at the start of the project presents a challenge for achieving pilot readiness level by 2030 and commercial applications by 2050. The need for further research and development to reach pilot readiness level, coordination of future development of CHPM technological components, and the exploration of potential pilot areas in Europe, are key actions for the future project success.

More in details, the challenges include:

- **Lack of Knowledge and Data:** The lack of knowledge about the quantity and types of metal-rich minerals at depth and the composition of deep groundwaters limits the experimental quantification and modelling simulations of metal release processes, which is crucial for the development of the CHPM technology.
- **Technical Improvements:** Technical improvements, such as the need to develop the technology to install low- to mid-enthalpy Enhanced Geothermal Systems (EGS) in specific mining areas, must be overcome to successfully develop the CHPM technology. Additionally, the establishment of a reliable, communicating fracture system for heat exchange and chemical reactions is needed.
- **Exploration and Development Plan:** The roadmap emphasizes the need for an exploration and development plan to achieve a pilot readiness level by 2030. This plan includes actions, timelines for implementation, and recommendations for the next research program, focusing on preparing the ground for subsequent pilot implementation.
- **Funding and Stakeholder Engagement:** The document mentions the importance of funding opportunities and stakeholder engagement for the successful implementation of the CHPM technology. It also highlights the need to monitor job creation and map other projects feeding into CHPM objectives to build on their results.

4.4. Industrial overview

Industrial Minerals Europe (IMA-Europe) is an EU voice of industrial minerals producers and importers. IMA-Europe helps industrial mineral companies continuously improve their performance and reputation by tackling issues related to minerals' properties and safe use, from their extraction and processing to their entire value chain. In response to the European Commission's initiatives for a competitive, low-carbon economy and resource-efficient Europe, IMA outlined the European industrial mineral sector view in the "Imagine the Future with Industrial Minerals 2050 Roadmap".

The roadmap emphasizes the vital role of industrial minerals in everyday products and technologies, highlighting their significance in the transition to a low-carbon economy. It foresees an industry with enhanced resource efficiency, improved recycling, increased demand from innovative applications, better access to minerals, highly skilled jobs kept in Europe, and continuous engagement with local communities and the workforce.

The roadmap focuses on the steps the industrial minerals industry will take to meet the increasing demand for resources in a sustainable, innovative, and resource-efficient manner. It emphasizes reducing specific energy consumption, minimising transport emissions, extracting locally, developing innovative technologies and sustainable products, contributing to a resource-efficient economy, protecting and promoting biodiversity, engaging with local communities and the workforce, and partnering with policymakers. The industry is committed to achieving zero waste, improving recycling rates, and contributing to biodiversity conservation.

With the aim to maximise resources, reduce transport emissions, and promote innovative technologies and sustainable products, IMA also expects a shift from road transport to water and rail where possible and easier access procedures for raw materials in all Member States.

4.4.1. Key components and objectives

- Role of Industrial Minerals.
- Reduced Carbon Emissions: Specific measures to reduce carbon emissions, including transitioning from truck-based freight to rail and barge, facilitating local extraction permits, and promoting innovative technologies for sustainable products are suggested.
- Global Economic Trends: IMA acknowledges the expected global economic growth driven by Asia and the increasing demand for raw materials as a result of growing middle-class populations. It also highlights the potential competition for land and access to water among different industry sectors.
- European Competitiveness: The roadmap emphasizes the need for Europe to maintain competitiveness in the global market by implementing smart regulation approaches, realistic taxation levels, and competitive energy prices. It also calls for a value chain approach to identify industry clusters and operations at an early stage.
- Resource Efficiency: The importance of maximizing resources and promoting resource efficiency at every stage of the supply chain, from the mine site to processing and manufacturing. Use of better resources rather than simply using less.

4.4.2. Gaps and challenges

- Transition to a low carbon economy.
- Importance of transportation and buildings.
- Increasing urbanization and population in cities by 2050.
- Global economic growth driven by Asia.
- Greater demand for goods and raw materials.
- Growing need for food and agricultural products.
- Potential competition for land and access to water among industry sectors.

4.5. National Overview –Sweden Example

A roadmap (Greberg et al., 2022) has been developed jointly by representatives from the industry, institutes, academia, SMEs, NGOs, and relevant authorities. It outlines the urgent challenges confronting the research and innovation effort and pinpoints the industry's research and innovation needs. The document is a strategic research and innovation roadmap for the Swedish mining, mineral, and metal-producing industry. It emphasizes the industry's significance in contributing to the climate transition and securing a sustainable supply of minerals and metals.

4.5.1. Key components and objectives

The roadmap identifies eight prioritized thematic areas for research and innovation in the mining industry. These areas include:

- Exploration and Resource Characterisation: Focuses on developing methods to locate new mineral deposits and improve knowledge of ore formation and structure to achieve more resource-efficient mining operations with reduced environmental impact.
- Mining: Aims to fully utilise the material and energy content in raw materials, enhance extraction of metals, secure viable use of by-products, maximise recyclability of discarded consumer goods, and limit negative atmospheric and water emissions.
- Research and Innovation Aims, Strategies, and Actions: Aims to significantly improve resource efficiency, reduce energy consumption, minimise environmental footprint, and increase recovery of by-products.
- Environmental: Aims to minimise the negative environmental impact of mining, increase the use of waste as a resource, and optimise water management throughout the mine life cycle.
- Development of Business Models and Decision Processes: Focuses on waste volume minimization, positive environmental impacts, and the extraction of value from waste through business models based on ESG values.
- Strategic Tools and Guidelines for Stakeholder Management: Aims to develop tools and guidelines for improved stakeholder management, sustainable supply chain management, sustainability auditing, community development practices, and social innovation.
- Legislation and Environmental Regulations: Aims to analyse the root cause of environmental problems, study the application of EU directives, and design and implement environmental regulations to promote continuous pollution reduction while considering long-term industry competitiveness.
- Social Cost-Benefit Approach and Land Use Decision-Making: Aims to make an international comparison of strategies for permitting indigenous rights and mining operations to co-exist, develop and test a social cost-benefit approach for investments in mining industries, and identify strategies to improve the legitimacy and efficiency of land use decision-making with respect to mining concessions.

These thematic areas encompass a wide range of research and innovation needs in the mining industry, including environmental sustainability, resource efficiency, stakeholder management, and social impact.

4.5.2. Gaps and challenges

Here are some additional details for each thematic area in the gaps and challenges:

- a) Organisation, learning, and leadership:
 - Attracting and retaining people from diverse social groups.
 - Developing education and job opportunities for all genders, ethnicities, and age groups.
 - Addressing the need for a diverse and inclusive work environment.
- b) Exploration and resource characterisation:
 - Developing methods for locating new mineral deposits.

- Improving knowledge of ore formation and rock quality.
 - Achieving resource-efficient mining with minimal environmental impact.
- c) Mining:
- Establishing integrated data-driven approaches.
 - Developing interdisciplinary tools for rock mass characterisation.
 - Improving communication along the mineral value chain.
- d) Digitalisation and innovation:
- Creating attractive workplaces in a safe environment.
 - Identifying and addressing risks associated with increased digitization.
 - Developing new qualifications and lifelong learning programs.
- e) Stakeholder management and sustainability:
- Developing strategic tools for improved stakeholder management.
 - Implementing sustainability criteria and indicators into operational management systems.
 - Achieving social innovation through collaborations and partnerships.
- f) Climate transition and sustainable supply of minerals and metals:
- Addressing the impact of climate change on mining operations.
 - Meeting the growing demand for sustainable minerals and metals.
 - Developing an understanding of how permitting processes and EU directives affect the mining industry.
- g) Challenge-driven innovation:
- Funding collaborative projects contributing to sustainability goals.
 - Researching battery performance and recycling methods for battery vehicles.
 - Developing new methods, tools, and techniques for product and business model innovation.
- h) Technology development:
- Improving knowledge of innovation management best practices.
 - Identifying system-level strengths and weaknesses in the mining ecosystem.
 - Addressing challenges related to energy efficiency, productivity, and environmental impact in mining operations.

In conclusion, Ghorbani et al. (2023) provided an in-depth analysis of the transition towards deep underground mining, driven by the depletion of shallow mineral deposits and environmental concerns. Its outlines of the key drivers and challenges of deep underground mining, including environmental, financial, geological, and geotechnical aspects, are of relevance for the future of the mining industry. Potential solutions, such as the integration of mineral processing and mining, leveraging modern tools like digital and automated mining, and the role of legacy data in bridging current and future mining practices are significant to the Persephone project. Ghorbani et al. (2023) well exemplifies the need for interdisciplinary innovation, experimentation, and rigorous introspections of legacy data to enable the transition towards deep underground mining.

5. Applications in Abandoned and Suspended Mine Projects

Abandoned and suspended underground mines are projects that have been halted for various reasons, which range from techno-economical setbacks to environmental issues. These abandoned mines vary in size, depth and structure. Can be very small consists of a shallow shaft and some short workings and very big with an area of even a few square kilometres (DMP, 2024; Ashby & van-Etten, 2021). It should be also emphasized that the environmental impact of these mines ought to be also considered in the light of safety and potential reuse in various directions i.e. tourism (Hojka, 2023), science (e.g. underground laboratory (EUL, 2024; Konieczna-Fuławka et al., 2023), resumption of mining operations (Dvořáček et al., 2021) etc. Therefore, there is a need to develop technology to explore these structures to collect different types of data (e.g. shape and dimensions of structures, parameters of the underground atmosphere (temperature, humidity, oxygen and other content, and parameters in a safe way and with cost-efficiency. In these aspects, robotics technology with high autonomous features seems to be very suitable for this kind of application. As it seemed very often autonomous robotic systems are successfully utilised in the research of volcanos, see bed or other planets (Thrun et al., 2004). This kind of robotic system which was used to abandoned mines exploration was described by Thrun et al. (2003 and 2004) where the mobile robot was developed with capabilities of mines exploration. In this case, SLAM technology was developed to ensure proper navigation, localization and mapping. Another technology was proposed by Pinto et al. (2020) to explore underground flooded mines. Among solutions that utilised mobile platforms in the forms of legged robots or chassis with wheels or caterpillars, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV's) are also used (Jabrayan, 2023; Ashby & van-Etten, 2021; Park & Choi, 2020).

There are also some solutions which combine two types of autonomous vehicles i.e. legged and aerial (Figure 5.1) (Lindqvist et al., 2022). This solution was developed for the underground search-and-rescue reason, but the capability of this system like high mobility and agility, long-term operation, and payload makes this autonomous unit very flexible and versatile to use for other applications including penetration and mapping of the old workings and other underground structures like shafts for instance.

Figure 5.1. Mixed (legged-aerial) autonomous system (Lindqvist et al., 2022).

In the last decades, huge progress in the development of drone technology (UAVs) has been observed (Merkert & Bushell, 2020). In many situations, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles seem to be a very good solution to examine some underground workings (Ashby, 2021) similar solutions are developed in NEXGEN SIMS project (NEXGEN, 2024). The drone developed by LTU in NEXGEN SIMS project is shown in Figure 5.2.

Figure 5.2. An autonomous drone for mine inspection.

It should be also noted that these autonomous and automated platforms can be also equipped with many types of sensors. All these technologies are developing very fast and extending their capabilities in many facets including long operational time, mobility, agility, autonomic abilities, data collection and real-time analysis (Merkert & Bushell, 2020). All these features are often supported by AI usage etc. It also should be noted that together with technology development, costs of those kinds of devices are decreasing, hence their usage can be commonplace in the near future.

There are many areas in Europe and worldwide where low-profile mine drives exist, which once upon a time were used for accessing ore deposits. Only in Euboea Island, central Greece, and only in mining concessions managed by Grecian Magnesite (GM), there are currently more than 100km of low profile (2m x 2m, approx.) underground mine drives that intersect magnesite mineralization zones of exceptionally good to superior quality. All these existing networks of abandoned/suspended underground mines were developed by handheld equipment between 1832 and 1965 and since then they have been abandoned or suspended due to the discovery of large-scale near-surface deposits. The decision-making teams of mining companies back then favoured the development of surface operations over underground ones for the following reasons:

- Before 1965 mine technology and relative solutions were more reliable for surface operations than for underground works.
- The exploration technology and work were easier to be executed and more productive for near-surface deposits, compared to finding and interpreting steeply dipping mineralised zones.

Taking into consideration the case of GM and its Euboean deposits, where the magnesite mineralization has the form of steeply dipping parallel vein systems of

highly fluctuating true thickness, under an irregular terrain covered by dense forests, the required exploration work is generally conducted with inclined boreholes of mean length 300m/exploration string. The respective exploration work is currently time-consuming, tedious, and it has a high cost and a medium to high environmental impact.

At the same time, there exists a dense network of low profile (2m x 2m approx.) old underground mine drives that intersect mineralised zones of very good to superior quality. These drives are unsupported, and re-entry of personnel is laborious and entails high risks. Adding to it, the execution of drive widening and supporting works under the frame of exploration tunnelling is accompanied by high costs and risks, since specific and not all magnesite grades are in general targeted through underground works.

GM is currently taking advantage of the existing abandoned/suspended underground network of drives in its Euboean mining concessions according to the following scheme:

- All drives where human access is possible are surveyed with SLAM technologies, thus the as-built regime of the areas of interest is mapped with high precision. However, surveying low-profile and unsupported underground mine drives is risky, laborious, time-consuming and is accompanied by high costs. The surveying work is twofold and is always executed by the presence of senior surveyors and geotechnical engineers. At first, control targets are established underground with high-accuracy open traverses. Finally, point-clouds of the as-built network of drives are generated with portable laser scanners.
- After completion of 3D surveying work, field geologists map all surveyed underground stretches, which in general expand both horizontally and vertically, intersecting mineralised zones. During this process, a large number of magnesite samples are collected-assayed and critical structural features are measured. All these data are finally draped to their exact locations in space.
- The attitude of mineralised zones and their grades are used to develop ore body domains. Then, through geostatistical analysis and interpretation of results, resource models are generated, as well as scenarios entailing the geological processes that formed the ore deposits.
- In the last stage, ad-hoc exploration boreholes are executed either from the surface or underground to cross-validate the above-mentioned inferences.

Under this framework, the potential utilization of an autonomous exploration system in abandoned/suspended underground mines could significantly cut down exploration costs and render known resources into reserves. At the same time, abandoned/suspended underground mine mapping and exploration could be executed with minimum risks and without requiring the mobilization of experts in harsh and unfavourable environments. Moreover, the utilization of existing underground drives for exploration purposes could skyrocket the green transition of mining companies, since intervention works on terrains of high environmental value could be kept to a minimum.

6. Sustainability in Mining

6.1. Advances in Sustainability Practices

6.1.1. Introduction and sustainability challenges in mining

Sustainability is regarded as a "*normative concept*" (Berg, 2020; Harrington, 2016; Scoones, 2016; Ramsey, 2015), which means it focuses on people, their values, and desires. According to Harrington (2016), the quest for sustainability involves connecting what is known through scientific study to applications in pursuit of what people want for the future.

Consequentially, one needs to distinguish that "*sustainability in mining*" is not the same as the sustainability of society, economy, or industry/value chain. While the United Nations' definition states that "*meeting current needs (and desires; authors) in a way that doesn't compromise the ability of future generations to do the same (UN, 2024)*"; others (i.e., Friend of the World – World Sustainability Organisation) define the "*sustainable mining as being conducted in a manner that minimises the impact on the surrounding environment and leaves mine sites in an acceptable state for re-use by people or ecosystems.*" (FriendOTE, 2024); or i.e. a company approach definition "*sustainable mining is when we conduct essential resource extraction while improving social, economic and environmental outcomes (Bravus, 2024).* Another view of sustainability is its relation to entropy (a thermodynamic measure). As Saleem H. Ali from the Centre for Social Responsibility in Mining at the University of Queensland, Australia explains, "*application of 'mineral renewability' for operational purposes that is defined by the level of entropy (or disorder) that mineral use will generate. The question of renewability from a chemical perspective is simply one of expending enough energy to bring back the material from a higher level of entropy to allow for reuse or recycling. The energy needed to counter the entropy created by the mineral's use is the main metric to evaluate whether that material's use is sustainable or not. From an operational perspective, metallic minerals are used in lower levels of entropy. That is why we are usually able to recycle them, whereas with minerals like coal, the use itself converts the material to such a high level of entropy (in the form of carbon dioxide) that it is essentially non-renewable*" (Ensia, 2024). This is why "*mining is inherently unsustainable; It is destructive to the biophysical environment, and its contributions to human well-being are uneven and often overwhelmed by the social and economic damage it inevitably inflicts*" adds Jamie Kneen, Communications and Outreach Coordinator at MiningWatch Canada (NYT, 2022). An attempt to move from the life cycle of the mine to the life cycle of the mineral (Gorman & Dzombak, 2018) (Figure 6.1) or positioning the raw materials value-chain into the circular economy loop as proposed by EIT RM (EIT, 2018) (Figure 6.2) would be the closest mining could get to sustainability. Still, even such a shift cannot be achieved it. Mining, by its nature, is not a zero-harm activity (Barbanell, 2023). It poses significant risks to the environment and local communities, including air pollution, water depletion and pollution, and biodiversity loss.

Figure 6.1 – Proposed systems view of mined materials in society that includes environmental sustainability metrics from mining and “life cycle” metrics to assess the sustainability of production and extraction for the long term (Gorman & Dzombak, 2018).

Figure 6.2 – The raw materials value chain. The entire loop represents the circular economy (EIT, 2018).

From the definitions mentioned above it is questionable whether mining in essence can be sustainable. The “irreversibility” of mining operations and activities related to them is arguably one of the most important factors that impedes or prevents mining from being sustainable. To conclude, it’s neither correct nor fair to claim that mining is sustainable, as it is impossible.

Given the fact that the Earth contains a finite amount of minerals – making mining a finite activity – the term **responsible mining** is preferred over sustainable mining (Jarvie-Eggart, 2015). However, the mining industry can act responsibly by creating win-win outcomes for both, local communities and for local fauna and flora but not geodiversity/geological legacy. Responsible mining is commonly defined as mining that involves and respects all stakeholders, minimises, and takes account of its environmental impact, and prioritises a fair division of economic and financial benefits (Arvanitidis et al., 2017; Bice, 2016; Broad, 2014).

One could argue that sustainability in mining can be attributed to its operational parts, such as sustainability of parts of mine (i.e., structures, shafts), by implementing different methods for disaster prevention and risk management to prevent/mitigate several hazardous consequences (i.e., surface deformations and failures, pollutant emissions and emanation), or by introducing and following the corporate social responsibility by which according to (Gergely, 2009) the company (including mining companies) recognises unsustainability (the destruction of natural environment and the increase of social injustice) and takes essential steps – systematically, progressively, and focused – towards a more sustainable world. Nevertheless, by doing all the listed actions, the mining industry still cannot achieve sustainability at its essence, but it can adhere to the responsible mining concept.

6.1.2. From sustainability to responsibility

Many past environmental disastrous events linked to mining activities such as the dam collapse in Jagersfontein, South Africa in 2022 (NYT, 2022), collapses of mine-tailing dams in Brazil at Doce River in the state of Minas Gerais in 2015 (Garcia et al., 2017) and in the city of Brumadinho in 2019, the cyanide spill at Baia Mare gold mine in Romania in 2000 (BBC, 2024), or the destruction of Juukan Gorge Aboriginal cave system in May 2021 (MT, 2024) have shown that mining industry has to drastically change its modus operandi if it wants to continue with its business. Adding the estimated more than 700 casualties in the mining industry since 2019 (NYT, 2024), many unrecorded casualties from accidents in legal mines and fatalities in illegal mining practices, put additional pressure on the mining industry. As Melissa Barbanell, the Director of International Engagement US for the World Resources Institute (PB, 2024) puts it “the biggest challenge for the mining industry is the trust deficit that is the result of the bad mining legacy”.

It is not surprising that in his study Carvalho (2017) concludes that based on numerous detrimental impacts of mining in the past, all future EIAs of mining projects should encompass the entire life cycle of the mine, should incorporate the assessment of negative impacts and societal benefits also, and must incorporate the liability and the cost – and thus make funding provisions timely – for post-mine environmental rehabilitation. He also emphasises that current mining activities need to reinforce procedures for the protection of the environment and public health, as it is today easier to see that mining usually brings into the biosphere large amounts of nontargeted chemical elements often with toxic properties to the environment and humans (e.g. radioelements and toxic metals) and previously neglected. Carvalho (2017) sees proper steps in the way that responsible mining companies tend to adopt everywhere good mining procedures according to the best international standards, although this might be far from being the general

behaviour yet. He states that the current development of societal values, in particular the growing value ascribed to the environment and life quality, makes unavoidable that future mining depends on achieving better conservation of the environment, long-term management of natural resources, and fair social-economic impacts in the life of local communities combined with improved safety in mining activities. He concludes that the mining industry with its activities needs to ensure that present and future generations will have resources or alternative means to satisfy their basic needs of food, water, and energy. This implies that metal recycling must increase, and alternative sources of energy must be tapped to decrease environmental impacts and depletion of conventional energy resources.

In their research, Howe et al. (2023) have shown that although technological factors are vital for developing strategies to mitigate the risks of environmental disasters, focusing on organisational and human factors is also essential. Their results suggest that the application of High-Reliability Organisation (HRO) theoretical concepts by mining companies can offer new strategies to increase organisational resilience and improve reliability in environmental performance when working towards the elimination of mining-related environmental disasters.

6.1.3. The societal context of extractive projects

Mining necessarily takes place in a societal context and society has certain expectations as to the performance of the extraction projects. Inter alia society expects that mining projects behave responsibly with respect to the environment and society itself. On the other hand, the way the mining industry can and will operate also depends on the way how a country is governed and how rules and regulations are implemented in practice. These aspects are generally dubbed as the ESG (Environmental, Societal and Governance) aspects.

A mine and its associated extractive waste management facilities will impose a long-term relationship with the host community. The picture particularly European societies have of mining is shaped by past practices in the mining industry and its nonchalant behaviour towards negative impacts on the environment and society. This has resulted in a widespread opposition against (new) mining projects. Such opposition often is an expression of the NIMBY (Not In My Back Yard) syndrome with which all larger-scale project battle.

It is now widely agreed that stakeholder participation in decision-finding procedures will aid in finding solutions of more general acceptance. A right to participate in decision-finding procedures has been codified, for instance, in the ‚Aarhus-Convention‘ (UNECE, 1998). It is also widely agreed that projects, such as mining projects, not only require (formal) environmental licenses but also an (informal) ‚social license to operate‘ (SLO), as Thomson & Boutilier (2001) call it. Obtaining the support for, or at least the tolerance of a mine increasingly faces difficulties anywhere in the world.

Obtaining SLO involves not only technical measures to reduce and minimise environmental and societal impacts, thus improving the ESG performance of mining operations along the whole life cycle of a mine (UN, 2002). In this sense a much broader and inclusive definition of SLO is used here, than what Owen &

Kemp (2013) assume the industry's understanding to be. Industry slowly recognises that this can constitute a substantial business risk (Falck, 2016).

Much of the literature on SLO concerns areas other than Europe, where in particular the governance situation is very different. In areas outside Europe often issues of social justice and the redistribution of (monetary) benefits dominate the discussion, which are not necessarily related to the mining project as such but are imbedded into wider governance issues in these areas. Recognising this difference, the H2020 project MIREU aimed to address this and to develop SLO guidance specifically for Europe (Tost et al., 2021).

In its commentary, the International Energy Agency (IEA, 2022) provides arguments substantiating that without widespread implementation of ESG principles (or pillars) (Figure 6.3), the transition to clean energy may face serious challenges. Responsible mining translates ESG principles into practice (Maybee et al., 2023; PB, 2024; Forbes, 2023; Micon, 2024; RM, 2024).

Figure 6.3 – Three pillars of ESG practices (Techtarget, 2024).

In one of the most referred publications on responsible mining, the Framework for Responsible Mining (Miranda et al., 2005) author proposes seven basic principles:

- I. Sustainable development – The principle of sustainable development provides the key foundation for the remaining six principles. Initially articulated in the Brundtland Commission report (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987), sustainable development is commonly accepted to mean “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.”
- II. Equity – Principle 3 of the Rio Declaration (UN, 1992) states that development must occur in an equitable manner that respects the rights of future generations while considering the current needs of society. In this context, equity implies fairness in the distribution of costs and benefits of development, as well as in the treatment of women and other traditionally marginalised groups.

- III. Participatory decision making – Principle 10 of the Rio Declaration (UN, 1992) states that all citizens have the right to participate in natural resource development decisions, which must be accompanied by effective access to information and opportunities to seek appropriate forms of redress and accountability if agreements are not respected.
- IV. Accountability and transparency – Corporations are increasingly held accountable to a broad range of stakeholders, including their shareholders, employees, affected communities, and governments. In the mining sector, this implies that companies should support independent monitoring and oversight and disclose the impacts of their operations.
- V. Precautionary approach – Interpreted in the context of mining, the precautionary principle implies that governments have the right to decide against promoting development and to establish regulations to prevent serious environmental degradation when development proceeds. It also implies that governments should exercise precaution when considering new mining technologies that may negatively impact the livelihoods of future as well as current generations.
- VI. Efficiency – For the mining industry, this principle implies greater efficiency in the use of energy and water, maximizing reuse and recycling of materials, including the metals produced, and minimising waste. This “cradle to grave” approach to mineral development also entails establishing links throughout the mineral product supply chain to promote greater eco-efficiency in minerals use; and
- VII. Polluter pays – National legislative frameworks have recognized that individuals and corporations responsible for generating pollution are responsible for paying for cleanup and environmental remediation. The polluter pays principle is captured in Principle 16 of the Rio Declaration, which states that countries are responsible for ensuring that polluters pay for costs associated with development.

Thus, Miranda et al. (2005) suggests the following four components as central to defining responsible mining:

- Acknowledging the need to preserve ecologically and culturally significant areas,
- Ensuring environmentally responsible mine development,
- Ensuring that mine development results in benefits to workers and affected communities, and
- Ensuring that appropriate corporate governance structures are in place.

According to Micon International (Micon, 2024) interlocking responsibility realms or components that constitute responsible mining are six – Governance, Environmental, Social, Technical, Economic, and Financial (Figure 6.4), which basically underline the proposed concept proposed by Miranda et al. (2005).

Figure 6.4 – Realms of Responsible Mining (Micon, 2024).

As noted above mining causes environmental and societal changes that impact the physical environment and local communities. If managed poorly, mining can lead to environmental degradation, and increased conflict, among other challenges. If managed responsibly, mining can create jobs, facilitate investment, improve infrastructure and lead to improved quality of life at a significant scale (Byambajav et al., 2019).

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Mining in general changes the physical and socio-economic environment around it. While mine-site remediation aims to reduce the impact of permanent legacies, such as spoil heaps and tailing-ponds as much as possible, solutions have to be found for a societally and environmental beneficial after-use of the sites. This process of care, which takes after closure and remediation of a mine is generally called long-term stewardship (LTS; IAEA, 2006, and references therein). LTS aims to find sustainable solutions for site uses that are compatible with the remediation solutions and the needs and expectations of the local communities concerned. LTS solutions can be an essential element in maintaining SLO for a mining site. Making extractive waste sites long-term stable and compatible with the Extractive Waste Directive (EWD, 2006) resulted in a variety of guidance documents produced on behalf of the European Commission (MWEI-BREF, 2018; EC, 2019; Eco-Efficiency, 2023).

Many elements of responsible mining can be identified, depending on the industry, government and civil society perspectives. According to the Initiative for Responsible Mining Assurance (IRMA) (RMI, 2024) responsible mining is “benefiting the economies and improving the lives of people, and respecting the environments of producing countries, while also benefiting mining companies in a

fair and viable way”. In fact, IRMA published Standard for Responsible Mining 1.0–Guidance Document (IRMA, 2023) that thoroughly describes the four guiding principles of responsible mining – Business Integrity, Planning and Managing for Positive Legacies, Social Responsibility, and Environmental Responsibility.

It is important to understand that the standard, as proposed by IRMA (2023), is applicable to all types of industrial- or large-scale mining (including surface, sub-surface and solution mining), but excluding ASM, and all mined materials (e.g., minerals, metals) for any cut-off extraction volume, with the exception of energy fuels (i.e. oil and gas operations, thermal coal and uranium). Standard and assurance scheme covers mining and associated activities (i.e. construction, infrastructure, preliminary ore processing, all occurring only in-situ), and includes requirements that pertain to different phases of the mine life cycle. To enclose as wider scope of types and scales of mining sites as possible, the requirements have been designed at a common denominative level. It is also important to emphasise that the Standard is a living document and that it’s constantly evolving, by updates and add-ons.

The four guiding principles if IRMA standard – Business Integrity, Social Responsibility, Environmental Responsibility, and Planning and Managing for Positive Legacies, are consisted of 28 requirements (previously 26), divided in the same number of chapters (Table 6) (IRMA, 2023a).

Table 6.1. – Guiding principles if IRMA standard (2.0 draft from October 2023) and pertinent 28 requirements*.

Business Integrity	Planning for Positive Legacies	Social Responsibility	Environmental Responsibility
Legal compliance	Environmental and social impact assessment and management	Fair Labor and Terms of Work	Waste and Materials Management
Community and stakeholder engagement	Indigenous Peoples and Free, Prior and Informed Consent (FPIC)	Occupational Health and Safety	Water Management
Human rights due diligence	Obtaining Community Support and Delivering Benefits	Community Health and Safety	Management of Physical Stability (new)
Gender Equality & Gender Protections (new)	Land Acquisition, Displacement, and Resettlement	Conflict-Affected and High-Risk Area Due Diligence	Air Quality
Complaints and Grievance Mechanism and Access to Remedy	Community Emergency Preparedness and Response	Security Arrangements	Noise and Vibration
Financial Transparency and Anti-Corruption	Planning and Financing Reclamation and Closure	Artisanal and small-scale mining (ASM)	Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Energy Consumption
Mineral Supply Chain and Responsible Sourcing (new)		Cultural heritage protection	Biodiversity, Ecosystem Services and Protected Areas Land and Soil Management (new)

*Some of these requirements are less applicable in Europe (i.e. conflict-affected and high-risk areas, security arrangements), and some in rare cases (i.e. indigenous peoples and FPIC).

6.1.4. Way forward and challenges the sector will need to address to achieve responsible mining

In their yearly assessments of drivers that represent business risks and opportunities for mining and metals, EY has ranked ESG as the top factor for the past three years (2024, 2023, 2022), while prior to that, in years 2021, 2020, and 2019 it was LTO (EY's synonym for SLO) that focuses primarily on societal dimension and public perception (EY, 2023). For the Year 2024, EY (2023) concluded that risks and opportunities list doesn't differ too much from the previous couple of years, which makes some issues clearly long-term priorities, particularly ESG and SLO, others reflect new challenges in the sector.

Among ESG factor group (Figure 6.5), the environmental pillar comprises of (EY, 2023) Tailings and waste management (#2), Water stewardship (#3), Attaining net zero emissions (#4), Climate change (#6), and Biodiversity impact (#11). Social pillar comprises of Local community impact (#1), Diversity, equity and inclusion (#5), Health, safety and wellbeing (#8), Human rights (#9), Indigenous trust and reconciliation (#14), and Social inequity (#16). The governance pillar comprises of Ethical supply chains (#7), Green production (#10), Circular economy (#12), Mine closure (#13), Fraud and corruption (#15), and Anti-money laundering (#17).

ESG factors facing the most scrutiny from investors in 2024

Respondents could select multiple options

Source: EY mining and metals business risks and opportunities survey data 2024.

Figure 6.5 – ESG practices with the estimated highest impact on business risks and opportunities for mining and metals (EY, 2023).

As Clausen and Sørensen (2022) properly conclude “there’s no doubt that, from a technology perspective, the digitally connected, autonomous, and carbon-free mine have the potential to become a reality. Breakthrough effects can be expected to come not from any single technology but rather from successfully developing, implementing, and integrating the full suite of (available) automation and digitalisation technologies across entire mining operations and moving towards digitally integrated, autonomous systems considering the process and its interrelations holistically (Clausen et al., 2020).” It is important to understand that

in order achieve digital and technological transformation, in addition to the technological aspects mining companies need to consider also social aspects and “adopt a mind-set of the human-centred climate smart mine” (Clausen and Sørensen, 2021). Same authors suggest that to “successfully responding to the changing landscape of stakeholder expectations and futureproofing, mining companies need to reconsider their role in the economic, social, and environmental ecosystem they are embedded in so they can break through traditions that keep them from successfully positioning themselves as builders of social value.”

Based on the objectives and ambition of PERSEPHONE project and considering the results of the EY study (EY, 2023), the guidelines from IRMA’s standard (IRMA, 2023 and 2023a), BAT reference on the management of wastes (both - tailings and waste-rock) from extractive industries (MWEI BREF) (Garbarino et al., 2018), and several recommendations on tailings management (RMF, 2019; ICMM, 2021; GTR, 2020) the following next steps and if possible, also actions are important to address (and be taken). By efficient and holistic application of these actions will help project to achieve its objectives and ambitions (in a form of outcomes/results) (Table 6.2).

Table 6.2. Next steps (actions) can be divided into operational or internal (O) and strategic or external (S). From the temporal scope activities can be grouped into **short-term (green)**, **mid-term (blue)**, or **long-term (purple)**.

	Action		Outcome
S	Using and implementing scenarios developed on projected future climatic events	→	Achieving a net-positive impact throughout the processes and value chain.
O	Using technology and data	→	Improving ESG monitoring and measurement across the value chain — water stewardship, tailings management, minimisation of waste and unwanted excavated material; and improving cyber resilience.
O	Adopting/applying changes in construction and operation of mines	→	Improving safety and wellbeing for workers and communities.
S	Including and executing closure protocols	→	Creating long-term value for communities (LTS).
S	Assessing and integrating human rights impacts into environmental, social and health impact assessments	→	Building trust and cooperation with stakeholders.
S	Conducting a full stakeholder risk analysis	→	Enabling more informed investment decisions that incorporate financial, technical and ESG considerations and hence creating longer-term value for communities and workforce.
O	Extracting more insights from existing and new data by utilising novel computing capabilities and technologies (i.e. AI, HPC)	→	Building integrated operating model (a digital twin) for optimising planning and mining activities.
S/O	Stimulate and uptake innovations	→	Optimising benefits in all segments of operations and utilising comprehensive extraction strategy (See chapter 6.1.2 from D1.2).

O	Utilising clean energy sources and circular designs	→	Minimising environmental impacts (waste, emission, and energy consumption reductions), and reducing operational costs.
S	Co-creating regulations	→	Overcoming outdated or unfair/biased regulative/legislation.

^[1] Here, the mining industry includes all sectors of mining, metals, precious stones, and coal. The argument for it is that the public opinion doesn't distinguish between the three and consequentially attributes bad practices to the mining industry as a whole. As such the challenges to achieve good practises image lays upon the whole industry.

6.2. Reuse of Waste/Secondary Materials Generated by Current Mining Methodologies

Mining activities, whether surface or underground, result in the daily production of waste material, either excavated rock of various sizes or tailings of treatment plants. However, it is underlined that waste material generated from underground operations are orders of magnitude less than surface mining disposals and thus the underground mines, which in turn are concerning the PERSEPHONE project are the greenest operations of both abovementioned cases.

Waste generated due to mining activities poses challenging environmental, techno-economical and safety issues due to the large amounts generated worldwide. The waste material is produced in the processes of mining, extraction, processing and further treatment, and its quantity depends on a number of factors related to the geological structure of the rockmass, the quality of the deposits, methods of excavation and enrichment technology. Mining wastes are high in abundance and properties. The generated waste is very often sent for recovery or neutralization, wherein neutralization most often means disposal in dedicated landfills, which is ground storage in waste neutralization tanks. Currently, this is the most popular method of tailings management, even though it is known that continuous collection of massive amounts of waste may eventually result in disastrous environmental degradation. The waste, especially those untreated, may contain toxic and harmful elements, hence it is important to store it far from rivers and farmlands to minimise the risk of pollution of rivers and soils as well as groundwaters. However, it is not only storing and possibility of leakage to the ground, which pose a threat to the surrounding area, but also the dust that may be released from the storage tanks, which very often are not well covered (Kalisz et.al, 2022).

Typical methods of mining and treatment plant waste management are summarized as follows:

- Utilization as aggregates in concrete and road construction.
- Backfill material for underground openings.
- Recycling to recover values (Henne et al., 2018).
- Fillers in the ceramics industry (Rykusova et al., 2020).
- Permanent surface disposal in ad-hoc designed TMFs.

Taking into consideration that modern waste management systems must address the concepts of sustainability and circular economy, which are highly critical nowadays, it is worth noting through industry examples that mine design and production planning policies have to incorporate innovative approaches of waste management strategies.

The example case of Grecian Magnesite S.A. (GM) is given, which is a Greek mining company extracting, treating and calcining magnesite ores at surface and underground operations. In particular, the design of GM's vein deposits in Euboea, Greece, has been developed under the auspices of sustainability and circular economy, according to the following scheme:

- The designed underground mining method, i.e. overhand sublevel stopping with rockfill, is highly selective and ore and waste are extracted in distinct phases at the production headings. Therefore, dilution is kept to a minimum and RoM ore treatment reports significantly less waste material than typical mining methods. Adding to it, underground mine development is highly dependent on waste backfill rates, thus during the mine closure period all waste rock produced will be backfilled underground and there will be no need of permanent surficial dumps.
- Before commencing of underground mining operations, a thorough investigation of waste rock utilization was carried out at GM's research centre. The respective tests led to engineering the OLIDUN product family, which are exclusively produced from waste magnesium silicate rocks that are used in a variety of applications, i.e. slag conditioning, refractory bricks and mortars, sandblasting, fertilizers, cements and in CO₂ sequestration industries.

7. Digitalisation and Geomodelling

7.1. Digitalisation of the Mining Industry

Digital transformation has been a buzzword in the business world for quite some time now. As we enter 2024, the question arises: does digital transformation still hold any relevance, or has it become just another overused term? (Marr, 2024).

The mining industry is undergoing a transformative phase with the advent of digitalisation and sustainable practices. This transition is paramount for achieving economic, environmental, and social sustainability goals. Central to this transformation is the development and digitalisation of geological models, which play a critical role in enhancing mining operations' efficiency and reducing their environmental footprint. This requires a major business cultural change, digital transformation continually challenges the status quo, requires endless experimentation and expects users to get comfortable with failure. It is not only the adoption of technology but also a shift in mindset to agility and innovation (Figure 7.1).

Adapted from: Deloitte 2017: The digital revolution: Mining starts to reinvent the future

Figure 7.1. Digital revolution in the mining sector (Deloitte, 2017).

The hottest trends in an ever-evolving digital transformation landscape are:

1. Data-driven decision making,
2. Supply chain innovation,
3. Remote work and collaboration,
4. Cybersecurity, and
5. Generative AI in business innovation.

Hyper-innovation is currently a pivotal trend, characterised by the interaction and convergence of the synergistic fusion of the trends mentioned above. The success of autonomous geomodelling relies heavily on the ability to leverage the synergistic benefits brought about by the integration of digital twins, cloud computing and AI. It is envisaged that the development of this technology will translate into an environment that will incubate hyper-innovation, which is an environment where everybody in the organization – not only the IT department – thinks and operates like a tech company. This is an environment where employees

are challenged to think new, where innovation is prioritized, and a culture of digital fluency and agility is cultivated.

It is important for companies that digital transformation is not merely an exercise in implementing cool technology but requires mindset and culture changes on all levels of work throughout the organization.

7.2. Future of Geomodelling

The current state-of-the-art in geomodelling incorporates advanced technologies and methodologies to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of geological modelling. Key components of SoA in geomodelling include the use of:

- 1) *3D geological modelling software*, which allows for the creation of detailed, georeferenced models incorporating various geological data points.
- 2) *Geostatistical techniques* are employed to statistically analyse geological data, assessing the variability and spatial distribution of mineral resources within a deposit.
- 3) *Machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI)* applications are emerging in geomodelling, utilizing algorithms for data analysis, pattern recognition, and predictive modeling.

Looking towards the future, geomodelling is poised for a hyper-innovative transformation with the advent of *autonomous geomodelling*. This technology leverages the combined power of several advanced tools. Digital twins create virtual replicas of mines for real-time monitoring and optimization. Cloud computing provides the computational power needed for complex data processing and model building. Generative AI develops algorithms capable of independently building and updating geomodels based on real-time data and pre-established geological patterns. The expected value of advanced geomodels and digital twins for the mining industry includes improved resource estimation and management, leading to more efficient extraction and reduced waste generation, enhanced safety through proactive identification and mitigation of potential hazards, and environmental sustainability by minimising the environmental footprint of mining operations. Additionally, these technologies can increase productivity by optimising mine planning and production processes and reduce operational costs through automation and real-time decision-making capabilities. Lastly, real-time monitoring and predictive capabilities allow for the early detection of potential environmental and safety risks, thereby preventing accidents and mitigating environmental harm.

The potential of the application of digital twin technologies to create predictive geological models for more accurate mine planning has been shown in some case studies (Liu et al., 2022; Nwaila et al., 2022; Li & Cheng, 2022; Ahn et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2023). Digital twins, inclusive of geomodels, permit the optimization of production processes, energy conservation, and environmental impact reduction. The continuous flow of real-time data between the physical and virtual models facilitates the early identification of operational issues, promoting proactive management and maintenance strategies.

However, integrating digital twins and sophisticated geomodels into mining operations presents several challenges, among them are:

- *Data Security:* The risk of data breaches increases with the volume of data exchanges across various platforms.
- *Data Integration:* The seamless operation of digital tools such as AR/VR, IoT, and robotic systems demands robust integration of data and devices.
- *Network and Infrastructure:* Outdated networks struggle to handle the data generated by modern mining operations.
- *Geographical Barriers:* Remote mining sites pose challenges for real-time data processing and cloud-based solutions.
- *Cloud Computing Complexities:* Emerging cloud services offer competitive rates but may also introduce issues related to data transfer costs and vendor reliance, particularly in geopolitically unstable conditions.

Currently, the establishment of a digital twin for a mineral deposit is a process heavily reliant on human input, commencing from drilling operations, handling of core samples, analytical processes, and the determination of lithological varieties, to the intricate task of interpreting the spatial distribution features of mineral properties (Ghorbani et al., 2023). The estimation of mineral resources leverages sampling data garnered during geological explorations; however, as these samples only represent a minuscule fraction of the entire deposit, it is critical to ensure their statistical significance. This necessitates meticulous statistical analysis of the data, verification of its accuracy, and appropriate preparation for downstream applications. The intricate nature of constructing such a model is depicted in Figure 7.2.

Figure 7.2. Traditional requirements for building a geological model. Modified from Nagovitsyn & Stepacheva, 2021.

The potential for advanced automation and intellectual evolution in creating geological models through novel mathematical algorithms and intelligent procedures tailored to adapt models based on pre-established patterns is yet to be fully exploited. While the automation of excavation activities such as drilling, trenching, and channelling is in its early stages, the use of geophysical scanning

techniques—including X-ray fluorescence, gamma-spectrometry, and X-ray spectrometry—to assess borehole conditions and analyse rock debris is showing promise in efficiency gains. With complete robotization, processes that currently take up to a day could be drastically shortened to mere minutes, substantially expediting the mining cycle. This could lead to significant advantages such as improved resource management and better environmental safeguards. To fully tap into these advantages, the mining sector must address the obstacles associated with data integration, network infrastructure adequacy, and the complexities of cloud computing technologies.

8. Review of Regulatory Requirements

8.1. Relevant European Regulations

8.1.1. Environmental and extractive industries-related regulations

A frequent motivation to develop regulatory instruments in the EU is to address environmental, individual human or societal risks and impacts. Thus, achieving compliance with these EU regulations and their national subsidiaries (see below) is a major driver for environmental, safety & health, and societal impact assessment for planned projects. These regulatory instruments may be complemented by policy instruments that typically have a more proactive function by steering economic and societal activities into directions perceived as being for instance more sustainable, such as the EU 'Green Deal' (European Commission, 2019) or the forthcoming EU Raw Materials Act (European Commission, 2023).

The EU Directives and other regulations have to be transposed into or homologated with national legislation, which then becomes the enforceable legal instruments at the EU Member State level. Compliance with EU regulations cannot be directly enforced by the EU at levels below the national level. This is the obligation of the MSs through their respective regulatory system.

Typically, EU regulatory instruments only give a broad outline of the issues to be considered and actions to be taken. They set objectives, rather than describe the implementation, which usually is covered by national laws, by-laws, regulations, and codes. There is, however, also EU guidance on specific fields through the collection of BREFs (Best Available Techniques Reference Documents (for an overview of available documents see <https://eippcb.jrc.ec.europa.eu/reference>).

EU Directives relevant to the combined extraction come from a wide variety of policy-making and regulatory realms, such as the environment, water and air emissions, waste management, resources and energy conservation, nature conservation, workplace safety & health, etc. Some years ago, the European Commission initiated a study to summarise policy and legal instruments relevant to mining on both, the EU and national level (MinLex, 2017). This study produced a large range of factsheets on:

- a) **Internal market legislation:** eight items, including the principal Directives relevant to the topic of the MinLex project: Professional Qualifications Directive, Services Directive, Concessions Directive, Public Procurement Directive, Utilities Procurement Directive, Market Surveillance Directive, Accounting Directive, and Transparency Directive.
- b) **Environmental legislation:** 19 items, covering the principal environmental and industrial risk items (EIA, SEA, Environmental Liability, REACH, etc.).
- c) **Waste legislation:** 13 items where the Extractive Waste Directive and related Commission Decisions are discussed, among other waste-related items (Waste Framework Directive, Landfill Directive).
- d) **Water legislation:** six items, including surface water and groundwater topics.
- e) **Nature conservation legislation:** the two major pieces, the Habitats and the Birds Directive.

- f) **Noise and atmospheric pollution:** eight items.
- g) **Health and safety:** 24 items covering different aspects of occupational health and safety.
- h) **Statistics, nomenclature and information management:** seven different items.
- i) **Other relevant legislation:** 11 items that are resource-related pieces and cover energy minerals or topics such as underground CO₂ storage. Court case analysis indicated that some cases from the energy minerals sector may be important and relevant to the project if the reason for appeal concerns some general internal market principle.

All these will also be relevant for the permitting stage and the operational supervision of combined extraction projects. Since the Min-Lex-study was completed in 2017, a number of additional EU regulatory instruments, such as the Energy Efficiency Directive, have been put into place and they will be reviewed with respect to their relevance as well. There is no comparable compendium on national environmental regulatory instruments.

The piece of legislation most relevant to the aim of PERSEPHONE is The European Commission's Extractive Waste Directive (EWD, 2006), which sets out comprehensive rules for the management of waste from extractive industries across the European Union:

1. **Scope:** The directive applies to waste resulting from the prospecting, extraction, treatment, and storage of mineral resources.
2. **Environmental Objectives:** The primary goal of the EWD is to prevent or reduce adverse effects on the environment and human health that may arise from the management of extractive waste. This includes preventing water and soil contamination, minimising the risk of accidents or disasters, and ensuring the rehabilitation of affected sites.
3. **Permitting and Licensing:** Member states were required to establish a permitting system for extractive waste facilities, which includes obtaining permits for the operation, closure, and post-closure phases. Permit applications must include detailed waste management plans, risk assessments, and financial guarantees to cover potential environmental liabilities.
4. **Best Available Techniques (BAT):** The directive promotes the use of Best Available Techniques (BAT) to minimise the environmental impact of extractive activities. Operators are required to implement BAT measures to prevent or reduce emissions and waste generation, improve resource efficiency, and minimise the risk of accidents. Relevant BAT has been collated in MWEI-BREF (2018).
5. **Monitoring and Reporting:** Operators are required to monitor and report on various aspects of their activities, including waste generation, emissions, and environmental impacts. Member states are responsible for conducting inspections and audits to ensure compliance with the directive.
6. **Closure and Rehabilitation:** The EWD establishes requirements for the closure and rehabilitation of extractive waste facilities to ensure their long-term environmental safety. This includes measures such as stabilising

waste facilities, rehabilitating natural habitats, and implementing monitoring and maintenance plans.

7. **Financial Guarantees:** Operators are required to provide financial guarantees, such as bonds or insurance, to cover the costs of closure, rehabilitation, and any potential environmental damage that may occur during the operation of extractive waste facilities.
8. **Public Participation:** The EWD requires member states to ensure public participation in the permitting process and provide access to information on extractive waste facilities. This includes consulting stakeholders, such as local communities and environmental organisations, and allowing them to submit comments and objections.

By addressing these key aspects, the Extractive Waste Directive aims to promote the sustainable management of extractive waste and minimise its adverse impacts on the environment and human health.

In terms of PERSEPHONE's objectives the two aspects of the EWD (2006) below are of particular interest:

1. **Waste Management Plans (WMPs):** Operators of extractive waste facilities are required to develop and implement Waste Management Plans (WMPs). These plans must outline how waste will be managed throughout its life cycle of the mine, *including measures to minimise waste generation*, prevent pollution, and promote re-use and recycling. WMPs must also include provisions for the closure and rehabilitation of waste facilities once they reach the end of their operational life.
2. **Risk Assessments:** The directive mandates that operators conduct comprehensive risk assessments to identify potential environmental and human health risks associated with their activities. These assessments must consider factors such as the characteristics of the waste, the geological and hydrological conditions of the site, and the potential impact of accidents or disasters. Based on the results of these assessments, operators must implement appropriate mitigation measures to minimise risks to acceptable levels. More details are discussed in D1.2 in the context of achieving ESG goals.

In order to better understand the relevance and potential and actual impacts of certain EU Directives and regulations, it is helpful to order these according to the life-cycle of extractive activities, namely exploration, extraction, beneficiation/processing, intermediates, final products, wastes (including those from de-scaling operations and other process wastes), recycling, and long-term management of former combined extraction sites and their potential extractive waste management facilities.

Table 8.1 provides a non-exhaustive list of Environmental EU legislative acts (Directives/ Regulations / Decisions) relevant to the extractive sector and potentially applicable to combined extraction systems. The operational health and safety aspects are discussed in Section 7.1.2.

Table 8.1. Extractive operation life-cycle relevance of EU Directives and Regulations.

Directive / Regulation	No.
Environment	
Strategic Environmental Impact Assessment (SEIA)	2001/42/EC
Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA)	2014/52/EU
Environmental Liability Directive	2004/35/EC
Hazardous Chemicals (CLP Regulation)	1272/2008
Water Framework	2000/60/EC
Seveso Directive III	2012/18/EU
IED	2010/75/EU
Habitat	92/43/EEC
Birds	2009/147/EC
Waste	
Waste Framework (WFD)	2008/98/EC
Extractive Waste (EWD)	2006/21/EC
Hazardous Waste Regulations	1357/2014, 2017/997
List of Waste (LoW) Decision	2014/955/EC
Landfill	1999/31/EC
Human Health	
Restrictions of Hazardous Substances (RoHS)	2011/65/EU
Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH)	1907/2006
Sustainability	
Renewable energy	2009/28/EC
Renewable energies (RES)	2018/2001
Energy efficiency	2023/1791
Eco-design	2009/125/EC
Eco-management audit Regulation	1221/2009
Societal	
Public participation	2003/35/EC

Not listed are those regulatory instruments that cover radioactivity in form of naturally occurring radioactive materials (NORM) in process fluids, products, by-products or residues. Neither are the OHS aspects of handling contaminated equipment.

The European Emissions Trading System (EU ETS, https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/eu-emissions-trading-system-eu-ets/what-eu-ets_en) is a market-based mechanism that aims to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from industry and power generation.

At the time of writing, a revision of the current Industrial Emission Directive (IED, 2010/75/EU) is under progress. “On December 15, 2023, the Permanent Representatives Committee gave its final approval to the compromise text of the revised Industrial Emissions Directive (IED). As of now, the political compromise is provisional, pending formal adoption by the European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. This usually happens without major changes to the agreed compromise. The final wording of the IED is now foreseeable”

(Duenchheim & Herold, 2024). According to these authors “the agreement also brings mining activities into the scope of the Directive, covering the extraction including on-site treatment of ores produced on an industrial scale such as iron, copper, gold, nickel and platinum. Subject to review and legislative proposal by the Commission, the scope may be extended to industrial minerals as well, cf. Art. 73 para. 4: “The Commission shall review the need to control emissions from the on-site treatment and extraction of non-energy industrial minerals used in the industry other than for construction, as well as the need to control emissions from the on-site treatment and extraction of ores which are newly carried out in the EU.”

8.1.2. Regulations on Occupational Safety and Health (OSH)

Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) is not only relevant for the workers setting up and operating combined extraction facilities, but also for the surrounding communities and thus the social license to operate. The reason is that the workers usually are members of the local communities and the image of the operating company is strongly shaped by their attitude towards OSH and the well-being of their employees.

The European Union has developed a comprehensive set of OSH regulations in general, but also specifically for the extractive industries. The OSH Framework Directive (CEU, 1989) guarantees minimum safety and health requirements throughout Europe while MSs may maintain or establish stricter requirements. The Directive contains principles relating to the prevention of risks, the protection of safety and health, the assessment of risks, the elimination of risks and accident factors, the informing, consultation and balanced participation and training of workers and their representatives.

On the basis of this Framework Directive a series of almost 30 individual directives were adopted (Table 9), which are grouped according to the following categories: workplaces, equipment, signs, personal protective equipment; exposure to chemical agents and chemical safety; exposure to physical hazards; exposure to biological agents; provisions on workload, ergonomic and psychosocial risks; sector specific and worker related provisions.

Five of these directives have special importance for the extractive industries, namely 92/91/EEC (CEU, 1992a) setting minimum requirements for improving the safety and health of workers engaged in drilling operations in the extractive industries; 92/104/EEC (CEU, 1992b) establishing minimum OSH requirements in surface and underground mineral-extracting industries; 2003/10/EC on the risks arising from physical agents such as noise (CEU, 2003) and 2002/44/EC on vibration (CEU, 2002) as well as 2004/37/EC on the exposure to carcinogens or mutagens at work (CEU, 2004), which include mineral dusts from e.g. silica and coal, or fibres of certain asbestos minerals.

The main risks that may arise during the various phases of an extractive project or its ancillary operations, will need to be defined and assessed in the Technical Operation Plan (TOP). Definition of health and safety rules are a substantial part of the permitting process. Risk assessment included in the TOPs will need to consider all possible health and safety factors, especially concerning the work equipment used, hazardous substances and mixtures, occupational exposure of

workers to different substances, noise, vibration or ionising radiation, as well as the ergonomic set-up of the workplaces.

A number of studies in recent years have summarised (e.g. Falck et al., 2017) and also critically evaluated them (e.g. Min-Lex, 2017), where one can find more detailed information on these instruments. Table 8.2 summarises those Conventions and Treaties that are most relevant in an extractive industry context. It is subdivided into areas pertinent to operational safety & health (OSH) regulations.

Table 8.2: OSH relevant EU Directives (see also <https://osha.europa.eu/en/safety-and-health-legislation/european-directives>)

Subject area	Directive No.
Overarching instruments	
Introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health of workers at work – OSH Framework Directive	89/391/EEC
Minimum safety and health requirements for the workplace	89/654/EEC
Minimum requirements for improving the safety and health protection of workers in <i>surface and underground mineral-extracting industries</i>	92/104/EEC
Minimum requirements for improving the safety and health protection of workers in the mineral- extracting industries through <i>drilling</i>	92/91/EEC
Workplaces, equipment, signs, personal protective equipment	
Minimum safety and health requirements for the use of <i>work equipment</i> by workers at work	2009/104/EC
Minimum health and safety requirements for the use by workers of <i>personal protective equipment</i> at the workplace	89/656/EEC
Minimum requirements for the provision of safety and/or health <i>signs</i> at work	92/58/EEC
Minimum requirements for improving the health and safety protection of workers potentially at risk from <i>explosive atmospheres</i>	1999/92/EC
Workload, ergonomics, and psychosocial risks	
Minimum health and safety requirements for the <i>manual handling of loads</i> where there is a risk particularly of back injury to workers	90/269/EEC
Minimum safety and health requirements at <i>temporary or mobile construction sites</i>	92/57/EEC
Working time concerning certain aspects of the organisation of working time	2003/88/EC
On temporary workers	91/383/EEC
Chemical agents	
Chemical agents and its individual Directives 2000/39, 2006/15, 2009/161, and 2017/164 on lists of indicative occupational exposure limit values	98/24/EC
On the protection of workers from the risks related to exposure to carcinogens, mutagens or reprotoxic substances at work	2004/37/EC
Classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures (CLP) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures, amending and repealing Directives 67/548/EEC and 1999/45/EC, and amending Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006	Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008
Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) and establishing a European Chemicals Agency	Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006
Biological agents	

On the protection of workers from risks related to exposure to <i>biological agents</i> at work	2000/54/EC
<i>Physical agents</i>	
Minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to the risks arising from physical agents (<i>vibration</i>)	2002/44/EC
Minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to the risks arising from physical agents (<i>noise</i>)	2003/10/EC
Minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to the risks arising from physical agents (<i>electromagnetic fields</i>)	2004/40/EC
Minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to risks arising from physical agents (<i>artificial optical radiation</i>)	2006/25/EC
Radiation protection	2013/59/Euratom

It should be noted that PERSEPHONE is aimed at reducing the risks and exposures of the in-mine workforce by promoting the development of remotely operated and autonomous machinery. On the other hand, the joint presence of humans and operator-less machinery poses also new risks and challenges that have not yet been covered by regulations.

8.2. Selected EU Member States' Legislation and Policies

As noted above, the European Commission initiated a study to summarise policy and legal instruments on both, EU and national level (MINLEX, <http://www.minlex.eu>; MinPol, 2017). The factsheets produced by this study provided a good starting point for the following assessment.

The EU Raw Materials Information System (RMIS) maintained by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission also provides legislative country profiles for the EU Member States: <https://rmis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/member-states-legislation-08b84e>. The data are based on the MinLex (2017) study but also include the results from the MinGuide project. It is not known whether the information in RMIS is updated periodically.

Annex 1 provides a regulatory country review, focusing on the permitting aspects as controlled by the respective mining or natural resources and the environmental protection laws. The related national legislation on construction, on operational safety and health (OSH) etc. have not been reviewed. It is assumed that the OSH regulations fall under the umbrella of the respective EU Directives and regulations discussed in Section 8.1.2. Owing the long tradition of mining and mining regulators, OSH often is covered by the respective country's mining regulations and oversight rests with mining regulators, rather than e.g. labour departments as for other industrial OSH aspects.

9. Conclusions

The increased demand for raw materials in the EU is driving mining companies to operate at greater depths, creating new challenges for profitability, safety, and sustainability. Key tasks for the future are the development of new innovative technologies capable of addressing the challenges in deep mining operations, including (i) the integration of mineral processing and mining, (ii) use of modern tools like digital and automated mining, (iii) and the role of legacy data in bridging current and future mining practices.

The aim of this deliverable was to provide an in-depth analysis of the current state of technologies and applications for deep mining, including roadmaps, and identify challenges and opportunities in deep mining technologies for the PERSEPHONE project.

Based on literature data, in this document are highlighted the following challenges:

- Navigation through complex geological structures in abandoned and suspended mines, and the importance of autonomy and navigation for efficient mining operations.
- Advancing mining methods towards innovative and socially acceptable approaches.
- Limitations of current drilling tools in hard rock scenarios to meet the increasing mining industry requirements.
- Relevance of in-situ geochemical and geophysical instruments for real-time analysis.
- Effective use of MWD data, improving calibration procedures and parameters
- The significance of aligning developments in deep mining technologies and the need for technologies that are in line with current legislation in EU countries. Addressing challenges related to energy efficiency, productivity, and environmental impact in mining operations.

Within PERSEPHONE there are opportunities to further research and develop autonomous technologies for exploration and extraction in deep mines, abandoned and suspended mining projects. As interdisciplinary innovation, experimentation, and examination of legacy data are fundamental to facilitate the transition towards deep underground mining.

Outcomes from this deliverable serve as input for current and future work phases like the development of new innovative technologies capable of addressing the challenges in deep mining operations, the integration of exploration with other aspects of operation and development, and the development of in-situ real-time analysis and digital twin deposits for informed exploration.

10. References

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11. Appendix 1 - Selected EU member states' legislation and policies

A1.1 - Austria

Mineral exploration and exploitation are governed by a range of laws and regulations at both, the federal and regional level. At the federal level, the main laws and regulations that apply include the Federal Mining Act (Bundesberggesetz), the Federal Environmental Impact Assessment Act (UVP-G), and the Federal Waste Management Act (AWG).

Metal ores in general are 'free to mine' ('bergfrei') but require a mining license by the government (MinLex, 2017).

Drill-holes below 300 m depth require a license under the mineral resources act (MinroG) by the competent mining regulator. If water is to be extracted, this requires a license under the water resources act (WRG, 1959), which also regulates the re-injection. If the amount extracted exceed 10^6 m³ annually, an environmental impact assessment is required per UVP-G.

A1.2 - Belgium

Belgium is a Federal State composed of three Regions (Flanders, Wallonia, and Brussels). There are different governing laws on extraction for Flanders and Wallonia, however, metal ores on the continental shelf are owned by the state and exploration and exploitation requires licenses (MinLex 2017).

At federal level, the Mining Law (Loi sur les mines, minières et carrières <https://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/eli/loi/1919/09/15/1919091501/justel>) regulates the exploration, exploitation, and production of minerals resources in Belgium. The law defines the requirements for obtaining permits and licenses for exploration and exploitation, as well as the environmental and safety standards that must be met.

The federal Environmental Code (Code de l'Environnement) regulates the protection of the environment and establishes the requirements for environmental impact assessments (EIAs) and environmental permits for exploration and exploitation. However, much of the permitting procedures fall into the competences of the Regions. Recent policy initiatives in Flanders (new decree on deep subsurface and the implementation of an insurance system) illustrate policy support. In Wallonia the legal framework should evolve in the same direction, with a new project decree for underground resources management and a similar insurance system being discussed (Valkering et al., 2020).

A1.3 - Bulgaria

All underground ore resources are state-owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses. Mining in Bulgaria is regulated by the Concessions Act (SG No. 36/2.05.2006, <https://www.me.government.bg/en/files/download?hash=e357b9ee3f401efbee64d6a3995ac311a49da805>) and the

Subsurface Resources Act (No. 23/12.03.1999, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/bul155639.pdf>).

Other laws of relevance for permitting procedures include the Waste Management Act (53/13.07.2012); the Environmental Protection Act, the Nature Protection Act; the Protected Areas Act (133/11.11.1998); the Act for the protection of the environment (SG 91/25.09.2002, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/bul52883.pdf>); the Water Act (67/27.07.1999, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/bul33607.pdf>), which concerns the requirements for monitoring and reporting of groundwater usage (incl. dewatering for mining); the Law on Biological Diversity (SG/77/09.08.2002, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/bul154432.pdf>); and the Protected Areas Act (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/bul67271.pdf>) among others. Bulgaria has a centralised regime where all licenses for all kind of commodities are processed after a written application to the Ministry of Energy (<https://www.me.government.bg/en>). Other relevant co-authorities are the Ministry of Environment and Waters (<https://www.moew.government.bg>) and the Regional Inspectorates on Environment and Water, which coordinate the environmental permitting with the Ministry of Environment. Permits for exploration are granted by the Ministry of Energy upon approval by the Council of Ministers or for the continental shelf and the EEZ by the Council of Ministers (MinLex, 2017).

A1.4 - Croatia

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses. Croatia has a centralised permitting regime (MinLex, 2017).

Croatia has a centralised permitting regime and the authorities involved include the Ministry of Economy (issues permits/licenses for exploration and extraction, <http://www.javnabava.hr/>), the Ministry of Environmental and Nature Protection (determines specific conditions, restrictions and consent, impact assessment, <https://mingor.gov.hr/>), the Ministry of Construction and Physical Planning (spatial planning documents necessary to start the procedure for granting a concession, <https://mpgi.gov.hr/>), the Ministry of Finance (provides financial and legal documents necessary to start the procedure for granting a concession, <https://mfin.gov.hr/>) and the Ministry of Agriculture (determines specific conditions relating to exploration and exploitation of mineral resources in forests, water management and agricultural land, <https://poljoprivreda.gov.hr>). For the exploitation of mineral resources, a concession is needed for the economic use of a common good according to the Act on Concessions. Concessions for exploitation are given on the basis of a public procurement using a bidding procedure.

According to the Environmental Protection Act (OG 80/13, 153/13, 78/15, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cro170097.pdf>), before submitting a Request for Determining Environmental Impact a Request for giving instructions on the content of an environmental impact study is made. An EIS is an integral part of a Request for Determining Environmental Impact.

A1.5 - Cyprus

Cyprus is one of the EU countries with the longest metal mining history, going back to before the Bronze Age, but there is very little metal mining today. All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses and a centralised permitting regime is in place (MinLex, 2017). The legislative framework for the mineral sector in Cyprus is provided by the Mines and Quarries Law of 1965 as amended in 1995, 2001, and 2003 ([https://www.moa.gov.cy/moa/mines/minesSrv.nsf/All/CF7BCA66EE5FDBCDC22574B90035C157/\\$file/Mines%20and%20Quarries%20\(Regulation\)%20Law.pdf](https://www.moa.gov.cy/moa/mines/minesSrv.nsf/All/CF7BCA66EE5FDBCDC22574B90035C157/$file/Mines%20and%20Quarries%20(Regulation)%20Law.pdf)). The Mines Service is the competent authority of the administration of the Mines and Quarries Law and Regulation and the Explosive Substances Law and Regulation ([https://www.moa.gov.cy/moa/mines/minesSrv.nsf/All/C41AB897D6FD4079C22574B20039F5FE/\\$file/Annual%20Report%202018.pdf](https://www.moa.gov.cy/moa/mines/minesSrv.nsf/All/C41AB897D6FD4079C22574B20039F5FE/$file/Annual%20Report%202018.pdf)).

A Townplanning Permit by the Department of Town Planning and Housing is a pre-required document to apply for a Mining Lease or a Quarry Licence (https://www.moi.gov.cy/moi/tph/tph.nsf/home_en/home_en?openform#).

Likewise an Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) study is required according to national law of 2005 on Environmental Impact Assessment from Certain Plans and/or Programmes Law 102(I)/2005 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cyp87147.pdf>), which seems to mirror the respective EU Directive 2001/42/EC (CEU, 2001).

A1.6 - Czechia

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses. Mining legislation in the Czechia distinguishes between 'reserved' minerals, which are state-owned, and 'non-reserved' minerals (or deposits), which are owned by the landowner. All minerals, with the exception of building stone, gravel, and clays are 'reserved' minerals.

The primary legal basis of mineral extraction activity is the Mining Law (Mining Act) No. 44 of 1988, as amended by Law No. 186 of 2006 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cze126493.pdf>). For prospecting and exploration for reserved mineral deposits the most relevant law is the one No. 62/1988 Coll., on Geological Work (the Geological Act) as amended. Other important national Acts are the Act on the Environment (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cze4757.pdf>), the Water Act (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/cze124878.pdf>), the EIA Act (https://www.mzp.cz/en/environmental_impact_assessment). In the field of exploration of mineral deposits, the Ministry of Environment is the most important authority, i.e. the Ministry lays down the exploration areas. In the sphere of exploitation, the District Mining Authorities are the most important state bodies. The District Mining Authorities (eight in total) are part of the State Mining Administration (SMA), which is composed also by the Czech Mining Office in Prague (central mining authority), establishing a centralised permitting regime. With respect to exploitation, the District Mining Authorities are the most important state bodies. The eight Authorities are part of the State Mining

Administration (SMA), which includes also by Czech Mining Office in Prague, thus establishing a centralised permitting regime. (MinLex, 2017).

A1.7 - Denmark

All land-based mineral resources belong to the landowner, while off-shore resources belong to the state (MinLex, 2017).

Licences are provided through a tender by the Danish Environment Agency (DEA). Licences are usually awarded as a sole concession for the applied-for area. Exploration licences last for six years but can be extended for 10 years.

A1.8 - Estonia

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses under the Mining Act of 2003 (MinLex, 2017). The main responsible authority for mining permitting is the Ministry of Environment (for mineral deposit of national importance), otherwise it is the Environmental Board. The primary legal basis of mineral extraction activities is the Earth's Crust Act (<https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/507012019007/consolide>). The main responsible authority for mining permitting is Environmental Board (<https://keskkonnaamet.ee/>). The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications (<https://www.mkm.ee/>) is advised (in a non-binding way) by the Commission of Mineral Resources on issues of exploration and exploitation of mineral resources, validation of mineral reserves, among other topics. Supervision and monitoring are conducted by the Environmental Inspectorate (under the Ministry of Climate, <https://kliimaministeerium.ee/>). According to the Earth's Crust Act, holders of an exploration or extraction permit have to ensure that the plans for mining are prepared and the mining operations are conducted under the conditions set by the exploration or extraction permit. Also of relevance would be the https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/compare_original/506072023011 Water Act with respects to impacts on water resources.

A1.9 - Finland

All ores are under the jurisdiction of the state, but royalties go the landowners (MinLex, 2017).

The Mining Act:

<https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2011/en20110621.pdf>) governs the use of geological resources. Further of relevance are the Environmental

Protection Act:

https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2014/en20140527_20200905.pdf),

and the Water Act:

<https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2011/en20110587.pdf>), as well as

the Land-Use and Building Act:

https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/1999/en19990132_20030222.pdf).

A1.10 - France

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses (MinLex, 2017).

In principle, ownership of a plot of land includes the ownership of what is above and below such plot of land (Article 552 of the Code Civil, https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/codes/article_lc/LEGIARTI000006428953).

Exploration and exploitation are subject to general mining licenses granted in principle by the prime minister or the minister for mines (Decree No. 2006-648 dated 2 June 2006, <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/loda/id/JORFTEXT000000790913>).

An exploration permit (permis exclusif de recherches – PER) is required, that contains *inter alia* an environmental impact statement (notice d'impact) indicating (i) potential impacts of the works on the environment and (ii) how the contemplated project includes environmental concerns. The consent of the respective land-owner to use the site is required.

Numerous administrative bodies are likely to be involved – such as:

- The Minister in charge of mines (i.e. currently the Ministre de la transition écologique et solidaire and the Ministre de l'économie et des finances) is the recipient of the application;
- The local representative of the State (préfet) examines the application form and organises the tender procedure;
- The heads of the interested civil and military services (chefs des services civils et de l'autorité militaire intéressés) are consulted;
- The regional environment, planning and housing agency (la direction régionale de l'environnement, de l'aménagement et du logement – DREAL) drafts a report;
- The municipalities concerned are consulted;
- The General Council for the Economy, the Industry, the Energy and the Technologies (Conseil général de l'économie, de l'industrie, de l'énergie et des technologies) submits its opinion on the project.
- As far as the concession permit is concerned, the opinion of the Council of State (Conseil d'Etat) is also required, and the permit is delivered by the Prime Minister (Article 31 of the Decree No. 2006-648 dated 2 June 2006).

With effect of January 2023 the Mining Code was revised, integrating the mining permits with the environmental permits to allow for a streamlined procedure and ensure cohesive monitoring of the activities (Décret n° 2023-13 du 11 janvier 2023 relatif à l'autorisation environnementale des travaux miniers, <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/jorf/id/JORFTEXT000046971943>). This also means that only one application is made to cover both mining and pollution control aspects (MTECT, 2023).

Water management is the subject of a framework for water planning and management (Schéma Directeur d'Aménagement et de Gestion des Eaux (SDAGE)). The SDAGE must be taken into account in any administrative decision, meaning that all mining authorisations would need to have regard to the scheme

in accordance with the Environmental Code. The relationship between the mining permit and the SDAGE was clarified and confirmed with this New Mining Code (<https://codes.droit.org/PDF/Code%20de%20l%27environnement.pdf>).

A1.11 - Germany

The governing law is the German mining law (BBergG, <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/bbergg/>), but the regional mining authorities are competent for issuing licenses such as exploration licenses (Aufsuchungserlaubnis), exploitation licenses (Gewinnungsbewilligung) or mining property rights (Bergwerkseigentum) (see below). In detail, the provisions regarding the competence depend on the federal state. Prior to making a decision on the application, the competent mining authority shall ensure that the authorities responsible for safeguarding the public interest are given the opportunity to express their opinion. For research activities on the continental shelf the Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie – BSH) has to be involved.

Drilling below 100 m depth for commercial purposes, namely the extraction of mineral value requires a license. An impact assessment per Immission Law (BImSchG, <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/bimschg/BImSchG.pdf>) and the Water Management Act (WHG, <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/bimschg/BImSchG.pdf>) is likely to be required.

A1.12 - Greece

All ‘metallic’ minerals are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses. The Greek Legislation (the Mining Code, namely L.210/1973) distinguishes mineral raw materials into two broad categories: a) ‘Metallic Minerals’ which, either on the surface or underground, do not belong to the landowner, and b) ‘Quarry Minerals’, which belong to the landowner (Tzeferis, 2018). ‘Metallic Minerals’ include (native) metals, all metallic compounds, precious stones, radioactive and energy minerals, sulphur, talc, fluoride, asbestos, dolomites with MgO content >21%, feldspars, mineral salt, organic sediments, and others, as well as those ‘Quarry Minerals’ that may be treated in order to produce ‘Metallic Minerals’. At the national level, the Ministry of Environment and Energy (YPEN) and, at the regional/local level, the 7 De-centralised (Regional) Administrations (tiers of ministries) and the 13 Administrative Regions (L.3852/2010) are concerned with issuing permits. Who issues which permit depends on the mineral type, size of the project/activity, any land use peculiarities of the area of intervention (i.e. frontier area, protected area), or/and the land ownership legal status (MinLex, 2017).

A1.13 - Hungary

All minerals are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses (MinLex, 2017).

The primary legal basic of mineral extraction activity is Act No. XLVIII of 1993 on Mining (https://rmis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/uploads/legislation/Hungary_MiningAct_ENGLISH

.pdf). Important pieces of law for permitting procedures are Governmental Decree No. 203/1998. (XII.19.) (detailed permitting rules), Government Regulation No. 161/2017. (VI. 28.) on the Mining and Geological Survey of Hungary (MBFSZ), Government Regulation No. 53/2012 on mining construction permitting (<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A1200312.KOR>), Government Regulation No. 314/2005 on EIA and IPPC (<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A0500314.KOR>), Act No. LIII of 1996 on nature conservation (<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=99600053.TV>), Government Regulation No. 275/2004 on Natura 2000 sites (<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A0400275.KOR>), and Government Regulation No. 312/2012 on construction permitting (<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A1200312.KOR>). For permitting procedures, Act No. CL of 2016 on the General Order on Administration is also important (<https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A0400140.TV×hift=20170101&txreferer=A1100190.TV>).

Environmental impact assessments fall under the Governmental Decree No. 314/2005 (XII.25.) regarding the procedures of environmental impact assessment and the single procedure of authorization of utilization of the environment (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/hun109029.pdf>). Water-related matters are regulated under the Act No. LVII of 1995 on water management (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/hun5203.pdf>).

A1.14 - Iceland

The ownership of natural resources is governed by the Act on the survey and utilisation of ground resources no. 57/1998 ('Natural Resources Act', <https://www.government.is/media/atvinnuvegaraduneyti-media/media/acts/Act-No-57-1998-on-survey-and-utilisation-of-ground-resources.pdf>). The ownership of resources in the ground is attached to private land. Resources under public land are the property of the state. Resources are defined in the Natural Resources Act as "any element, compound and energy that can be extracted from the Earth, whether in solid, liquid or gaseous form, regardless of the temperature at which they may be found". However, Iceland being a young, volcanic creation, it is unlikely that solid mineral resources are to be found there.

A1.15 - Ireland

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses (MinLex, 2017).

The fundamental law is the Minerals development Act of 2017 (<http://www.mineralsireland.ie/files/MineralsDevelopmentAct2017.pdf>).

A number of specific regulations pertain to exploration and exploitation: *Planning permission* (according to the The Planning and Development Acts 2000/2021, <https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2021/act/18/enacted/en/pdf>)

is needed for any building associated with the geothermal system and it may be needed for deep drilling.

Mineral exploration boreholes need to be drilled under a license granted by the Exploration and Mining Division (EMD) of the Department of Communications, Marine and Natural Resources.

Environmental Impact Assessments are regulated under Section 72 of the Environmental Protection Agency Act of 1992 as updated to 30 September 2020 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/ire23558.pdf>). The Circular Economy and Miscellaneous Provisions Act of 2022 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/ire216857.pdf>) covers also aspects of minimising mineral raw materials use. The Waste Management Act of 1996 and updated to 9 February 2022 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/ire22204.pdf>) does not cover extractive waste and refers to the EU Extractive Waste Directive (EWD, 2006). Further of relevance is the Water Environment (Abstractions and Associated Impoundments) Act of 2022 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/ire214088.pdf>).

A1.16 - Italy

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses (MinLex, 2017). Ownership of natural resources is governed by the Italian Civil Code (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/ita197336.pdf>). Only the government of Italy can grant exploitation rights.

Namely Article 826, para. 2, provides that: “The forests that by applicable laws constitute the forested domain of the State, mines, quarries and turf pits when their disposability is taken from the owner of the land [...] are part of the non-disposable patrimony of the State”.

Article 840, para. 1, provides that: “Ownership of the soil extends to the subsoil, with all that is contained therein, and the owner can perform any excavation or work that does not cause harm to a neighbour. This provision does not apply to that which is the object of laws on mines, quarries and turf pits [...]”.

The Regions (Reggione) of Italy also have considerable regulatory power particularly also over the zoning and land-use planning.

A1.17 - Latvia

All onshore mineral resources belong to the landowner, who might be the State, local authorities, private individuals, or legal entities. The State has the right to limit the rights of legal and physical entities regarding the land and the subsoil belonging to them by imposing the limitations of the right to use the property (MinLex, 2017).

The Law on Subterranean Depths (with amendment up to 2021, <https://likumi.lv/ta/en/en/id/40249>) regulates the extraction of underground resources including minerals and water. Environmental Impact Assessment are

regulated by the law of 14.10.1998 (with amendments up to 2023, <https://likumi.lv/ta/en/en/id/51522>). Cabinet Regulation No. 696 of 6 September 2011 on the Procedure for the Issue of Licences for the Use of Subterranean Depths and Authorisations for the Extraction of Widespread Mineral Resources (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lat174595.pdf>).

A1.18 - Lithuania

All underground ore resources are state owned and exploration and exploitation requires licenses (MinLex, 2017).

The main law is the Underground Law No. I-1034/1995 (<https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/TAIS.29464?jfwid=bkaxlrq2>) and its implementing Government Resolutions (No. 1433/2001, No. 198/2002, No. 584/2002), which regulate the exploration and extraction permits. Other important laws regulating necessary permits and licences for the authorisation of exploration and extraction activities include the Environment Protection Law I-2223/1992 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lit4748E.pdf>), the Environmental Impact Assessment Law No. XIII-595/2017 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lit181537.pdf>), the Protected Areas Law No. I-301/1993 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lit180792.pdf>), the Water Law No. VIII-474/1997 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lit41412.pdf>), and the Spatial Planning Law No. I-1120/1995 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lit19457.pdf>).

A1.19 - Luxembourg

Although a small country, Luxembourg has considerable mining history (*inter alia* iron ore and hard coal). According to MinLex (2017) the main legislation governing permitting procedures for extraction is the law of 21 April 1810 (last amended in 1994, https://www.stradalex.lu/fr/slu_src_publ_leg_mema/toc/leg_lu_mema_181001_2/doc/mema_1810A0002Z), the law of 10 June 1999 relative to the classification of potentially dangerous establishments (<https://www.legilux.public.lu/eli/etat/leg/loi/1999/06/10/n5/jo>, amended by Grand Ducal regulation of 10 May 2012) which classifies the extractive industry as 'class 1' and makes it subject to an 'authorisation to operate' procedure following an investigation procedure called 'commodo-incommodo'. Other important laws are the amended law of 19 December 2008 on water (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/lux84420.pdf>) and the Law of 19 January 2004 on the conservation of nature and natural resources (<https://www.legilux.public.lu/eli/etat/leg/loi/2004/01/19/n1/jo>). Relevant authorities are the Ministry of Labour, Employment and Social and Solidarity Economy (<https://mteess.gouvernement.lu/fr.html>) and the Ministry of Sustainable Development and Infrastructure (<https://mecdd.gouvernement.lu/fr.htm>) which are the competent authorities for issuing the 'authorisation to operate' supported by its Inspectorate of Labour and Mines (ITM, <https://itm.public.lu/fr.html>).

The Water Management Authority (<https://eau.gouvernement.lu/fr.html>) has established a detailed map, that lists the areas where drilling is not permitted and those which are subject to restrictions in terms of drilling depth

<https://map.geoportail.lu/theme/eau>). An application for a class 1 classified establishment operating permit (see above), a water permit, and an environmental impact assessment are needed.

A1.20 - Malta

According to MinLex (2017) there are mainly quarrying activities on this island made up largely from limestone. The mineral extraction sector is regulated by the Mineral Resources Act (<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/423/20150731/eng>), the Environment Protection Act (<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/549/20230721/eng>), the Development Planning Act (<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/552/20230526/eng>) when it comes to mineral extraction, extensions to existing quarries and remediation of disused quarries, and the Cultural Heritage Act (<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/445/eng/pdf>). Legislation of indirect importance to which operations might be subject to includes the Land Acquisition Ordinance (<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/88/20170425/eng>), the Strategic Environmental Assessment Regulations (<https://legislation.mt/eli/sl/549.61/eng/pdf>) and the Continental Shelf Act (<https://legislation.mt/eli/cap/194/20140808/eng>).

A1.21 - The Netherlands

State-owned minerals include off-shore minerals (shells, gravel, sand and clay of the Continental Shelf – Art. §4b Excavation Act) and on-shore non-surface minerals (e.g., salt). On-shore surface minerals (e.g., construction minerals) belong to the landowner (MinLex, 2017). An amendment to the Mining Act (Minebouwwet), which only applies to minerals resources below 100 m depth, came into force on 01.01.24 (Article 2.2, <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0014168/2024-01-01>). The State Supervision of Mines (SSM) is the agency within the Ministry of Economic Affairs that oversees the production of minerals and Netherlands' continental shelf. The agency is responsible for enforcing mining laws, mine safety, and mineral production regulations on and offshore. Netherlands has a mixed (centralised-decentralised) permitting regime in which the SSM grants the exploration and extraction permits, and the Ministry of Infrastructure and Environment grants the environmental and water extraction permits; however, the consent of the provincial governments is also mandatory whereas the municipalities and local water authorities only provide consultative (legally non-binding) opinions (MinLex, 2017).

A1.22 - Poland

The State is the owner of all on- and off-shore deposits of metal ores (with the exception of bog iron ores), native metals, native sulphur, rock salt, potassium salt, potassium-magnesium salt, gypsum and anhydrite, as well as gemstones (§10.1 of the Geological and Mining Law of 09.11.21, <https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/DocDetails.xsp?id=wdu20111630981>).

Deposits of other minerals (e.g. sand and gravel, limestone, dolomite) belong to the landowner (Art. §10.3). In order to receive a prospecting or exploration licence, an environmental permit is needed (cf. Environmental Protection Law of 29.09.21, <https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/DocDetails.xsp?id=WDU20210001973>). The

Water Law of 16.09.23 is also important for mining operations (<https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/DocDetails.xsp?id=WDU20230001478>).

The competent authority is the Regional Director for Environmental Protection in the case of state-owned minerals and in case of investments located at the maritime areas of the Republic of Poland. Mining licences are granted by the Minister of the Environment for state-owned minerals, but the exact procedure and other authorities involved depends on the likely impact of the proposed mining operation (MinLex, 2017).

In Poland, there is no uniform regulation directly dedicated to investments and projects related to the use of geothermal energy. The legal environment of these investments is shaped in particular by sector-specific environmental regulations, conditioned by the level of interference in particular environmental resources (minerals, water), and horizontal regulations, relating to the comprehensive regulation of environmental protection as such (environmental protection law, impact assessment) as well as administrative regulations on investment and construction process in general (construction law, spatial planning regulations) (Szalewska, 2021).

A1.23 - Portugal

Land- and mineral rights are covered by the Decree-Law No. 47344 of 1966 and amended up to 10.01.22, approving the Civil Code and regulating its application (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/por210029.pdf>). The primary legal basis for the extraction of state-owned minerals (metals and industrial minerals) currently is Law No. 54/2015 (<https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/lei/54-2015-67552498>). The Portuguese national mining authority for state-owned minerals is DGEG (under the Ministry of Economy) which acts as a 'one-stop shop' for mining permits in the exploration, extraction and post-extraction phases. Extraction (mining) activities are subject to a mandatory EIA to be evaluated by both National Environmental Institutions, the Portuguese Environmental Agency (APA) and the Regional Coordination and Development Commissions (CCDR), as well as the Geological Institutions of DGEG and LNEG (National Laboratory of Energy and Geology), depending on the location, dimension and type of resource to be mined (MinLex, 2017).

Water- and environment-related acts are the Water Act No. 58/2005 of 09.12.05 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/por62080.pdf>), the Environment Basic Law No. 19/2014 of 14.04.14 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/por132791.pdf>), the Decree-Law No. 151-B/2013 establishing the legal regime of environmental impact assessment of 31.01.13 with amendments up to 11.12.17 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/por132059.pdf>), and the Decree-law No. 147/2008 regulating environmental damages' liability of 29.07.08 (<https://www.fao.org/faolex/results/details/en/c/LEX-FAOC081800>). The uses of off-shore geological resources are covered by the Decree-Law No. 38/2015 implementing Law No. 17/2014 establishing the Policy on the National Maritime Areas Planning and Management. (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/por147367.pdf>).

A1.24 - Romania

All mineral resources are public property of the state (Art. §1 of the Mining Law no. 85/18.03.2003, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/rom73606E.pdf>) and are administered by the National Agency for Mineral Resources (ANRM). The Romanian regulatory system for permits/licences can involve a variety of regulatory bodies and up to 6 permits, licences or approvals may be necessary for both, exploration and exploitation. However, the regulatory climate in Romania in general has been in favour of extraction (MinLex, 2017).

ANRM will review the application and may require an environmental impact assessment (EIA) before issuing the license (Law no. 292/2018, https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2021-06/frPartyVI.8h_25.06.2021_annex2.pdf). If an EIA is required, the developer must submit a comprehensive report that describes the potential environmental impact of the project and any measures that will be taken to mitigate those impacts. The report must be reviewed and approved by the National Environmental Protection Agency (NEPA).

In addition to these permits, the developer may also need to obtain permits and approvals from other regulatory bodies, such as the local municipality, the National Water Agency (Administrația Națională Apele Române, <https://rowater.ro>). and the National Energy Regulatory Authority (Autoritatea Națională de Reglementare în domeniul Energiei, <https://anre.ro>).

The regulatory instruments of relevance are the Law No. 292 of 03.12.18 regarding the assessment of the impact of certain public and private projects on the environment (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/rom216015.pdf>), Emergency Ordinance no. 195 of 22 December 2005 on environmental protection (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/rom197188.pdf>), the Law No. 122/2020 amending and supplementing the Water Law (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/rom201282.pdf>).

A1.25 - Slovakia

The legal framework relevant for permitting procedures comprises mainly the Mining Law (Law No. 44/1988 Coll.1 with amendments, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/slo43134.pdf>) and the Geological Law (Law No. 569/2007 Coll. with amendments). Other important laws are Law No. 543/2002 Coll. on nature and landscape protection, Law. No. 24/2006 Coll. on the environmental impact assessment (Law No. 39/2013 Coll., <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/slo183193.pdf>) on integrated prevention and environmental pollution control, and the Water Law (Law No. 364/2004 Coll., <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/slo182215.pdf>). Competent authorities are the Ministry of Environment of the Slovak Republic, Ministry of Economy of the Slovak Republic, Main Mining Office and the Regional (or District) Mining Offices.

According to the Mining Law No. 44/1988 and its amendments, 'reserved' minerals (e.g., metals) belong to the state (MinLex, 2017, p. 480).

License applications must include technical and economic feasibility studies, an environmental impact assessment, and a plan for the utilisation of the resource. The license is granted for a period of up to 30 years and can be extended by up to 10 years.

In order to obtain an exploration permit, a detailed exploration plan must be submitted that includes information on the proposed drilling locations, drilling methods, and the estimated resource capacity. The plan must also include a detailed environmental impact assessment on the local ecosystem and the surrounding community.

Once exploration has been completed, one needs to apply for a mining permit. The mining permit also requires an environmental impact assessment, as well as compliance with technical and safety standards.

A1.26 - Slovenia

All metal ores are state owned. The competent authority for granting exploration and extraction rights for mineral resources is the Energy Directorate (within the Ministry of Infrastructure, <https://www.gov.si/en/state-authorities/ministries/ministry-of-infrastructure/>). The local municipalities are an important co-authority as they are responsible for the municipal spatial plans. All areas with a mining concession (or with mining rights) need to be included in the municipal spatial plans and designated as “mineral extraction areas”. For such plans strategic environmental assessment or at least screening is needed (MinLex, 2017). Drillholes, deeper than 300 meters require a mining project.

Permitting for mining is also regulated by the Environmental Protection Act and (ZVO-1, SOP-2004-01-1694, <https://www.eui.eu/Projects/InternationalArtHeritageLaw/Documents/NationalLegislation/Slovenia/environmentprotectionact.pdf>). The competent authority for permitting is the Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning, which assesses the environmental impact of proposed projects.

The environmental impact assessment is prepared by an authorized expert, and must include a description of the potential impact of the project on the environment, as well as measures to mitigate any negative impacts. The Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning provides guidance and support to project developers throughout the permitting process.

Relevant regulatory instruments are the Environmental Protection Act of 07.05.20 as amended on 07.11.20 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/slv97886.pdf>), the Spatial management Act of 24.10.17 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/slv203422.pdf>), the Decree on waste of 15.12.11 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/html/slv130514.htm>), and the Water Act as amended on 08.05.20 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/slv61692.pdf>),

A1.27 - Spain

All mineral deposits and geological resources are state owned (Ley Minas of 21.07.73, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-1973-1018>). However,

the regulatory processes are highly fragmented between the state and the 17 Autonomous Regions, each with different environmental and land-use regulations, as well as different policy agendas. Each of the Regions may enact additional mining rules, provided the basic mining system governed by national provisions is respected. The permit/concession allowing extractive activities depends on the type of mineral commodity, i.e. 'mineral sections' A, B, and C (MinLex, 2017).

The drilling of boreholes and installations would be covered by the General Regulation of Basic Standards of Mining Safety contained in Royal Decree 863/1985 (<https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/1985/04/02/863>).

The permitting process for extraction is regulated by various authorities, including the Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge (MITECO), the Spanish Geological and Mining Institute (IGME), and regional governments. The process generally involves several stages, including preliminary studies, environmental impact assessments, public consultations, and approval by the relevant authorities.

Regulatory instruments concerning extraction include the Royal Legislative Decree 1/2016, of December 16, which approves the consolidated text of the Law on Integrated Prevention and Control of pollution (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/spa161835.pdf>), the law no. 21/2013, last amended 09.12.18, on Environmental Impact Assessment (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/spa129010.pdf>), the Law 7/2022 of 08.04.22 on waste and contaminated soils for a circular economy (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/spa209455.pdf>), the Law 22/2011 of 28.07.11 on waste and contaminated soils (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/spa104715.pdf>), and particularly article 57 of the Royal Legislative Decree No. 1/2001 - Water Law - in its recast form of 09.04.22 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/spa28470.pdf>).

A1.28 - Sweden

All metal ores are state owned. In Sweden, the right to grant access to concession minerals and permits to extract mineral deposits is reserved to the state. The 'concession minerals' are legally defined and listed in the Minerals Act 1991:45 of 24.01.91, last amended 01.01.06, (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/swe42438.pdf>) and comprise metallic ores, a wide range of industrial minerals, coal, oil, gaseous hydrocarbons and diamonds. The Swedish Environmental Code 1998:808 of 11.07.98, last amended 01.01.18 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/swe50970.pdf>) is particularly relevant, as permits for extraction must be granted under both the Minerals Act and the Environmental Code. The primary law concerning the extraction of 'non-concession minerals' is the Environmental Code (1998:808) (MinLex, 2017). The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (SEPA, <https://www.naturvardsverket.se/en/>) is responsible for issuing permits for drilling projects. The SEPA assesses the environmental impact (based on the Environmental Assessment Regulation 2017:966 of 02.11.17, last amended on 01.01.18, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/swe187160.pdf>) of the proposed project and ensures that the project complies with regulations related to water,

waste, and emissions. The EPA also consults with other relevant authorities, such as the Swedish Geological Survey and the Swedish Radiation Safety Authority in case of NORM (naturally occurring radioactive materials) that may appear in scales.

Extraction projects also require a permit from the Swedish Mining Inspectorate (<https://www.sgu.se/en/mining-inspectorate/>), which is responsible for regulating mining and drilling operations. The Mining Inspectorate assesses the safety of the project, including the stability of the underground formations and the risk of earthquakes.

Other relevant regulations are the Land code 1970:994 of 17.12.70, last amended 12.11.20 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/swe202065.pdf>), the Act on the carrying into effect of the Water Act of 1983 of 01.01.94, last amended on 01.01.99 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/swe24831E.pdf>).

Before submitting an application for permits, project developers are encouraged to consult with local communities and other stakeholders to address any concerns and ensure that the project is compatible with local land use and other activities.

A1.29 - Turkey

The objective of the Minerals Act, No. 3213 of 04.06.85 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur50790.pdf>), amended by Law No. 6592 of 18.02.15 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur153084.pdf>) and last amended by Regulation on mining of 11.12.22 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur222940.pdf>) is to define the principles and methods of exploring and processing minerals, and to regulate the proprietary rights. Energy minerals, metal minerals, industrial minerals, precious minerals, and liquid and gas containing above minerals are listed in the act. Proprietary rights for minerals are defined in detail. Turkish citizens and companies are eligible to explore for and process minerals. Minerals are explored under an exploration license, valid for 30 months. This license cannot be renewed. This exploration period is followed by a preliminary operational license, which is valid for 3 years and also cannot be renewed. A final operational license is granted to mines having adequate reserves. This license is valid for a minimum of 10 years and is renewable and transferable.

The Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources sets forth the terms and conditions for obtaining exploration and exploitation licenses. According to such terms and conditions, the Special Provincial Administration or (if there is a metropolitan municipality in the relevant province) the Provincial Directorate of Planning and Coordination of Investment of the metropolitan municipality is responsible for the issuance of licenses. The Administration notifies the General Directorate of Mining Affairs regarding license applications and its approval thereof. Where necessary, the Administration may request the General Directorate of Mineral Research and Exploration's to conduct an evaluation of the planned project prior to the issuance of a license.

There are also various other state entities involved in the development, such as for environmental and land acquisition purposes.

There is inter-agency cooperation between the Administration and the General Directorate of Mining Affairs in the licensing process.

Other legislation of relevance includes the Environment Law No. 2872 of 09.08.83 last amended on 01.01.22 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur7700.pdf>), the Regulation regarding point source land pollution and soil contamination control of 08.06.10 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur130480.pdf>), Regulation on water allocation of 10.12.19 (where mining is mentioned specifically, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur196786.pdf>), Act No. 167 relative to groundwaters of 16.12. 60 (mining also mentioned, <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur2564.pdf>), Regulation on water pollution control of 31.12.04 last amended on 17.12.22 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/tur89033.pdf>). It seems that the Zero Waste Regulation of 12.07.19 (<https://www.fao.org/faolex/results/details/en/c/LEX-FAOC187824>) does not apply to extractive waste.

A1.30 - United Kingdom

In general, onshore ores are privately owned (landowner), with the exception of gold and silver (MinLex, 2017). Pre-Brexit laws and regulations in general emulate EU-Directives and -Regulations, where necessary. Following the European Union (Withdrawal) Act (2018 Ch.16) of 26.07.18 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/uk180139.pdf>) tens of thousands of pieces of legislation that made reference to the fact that the UK were an EU Member State were amended to remove such references and convert them into purely UK law.

The key piece of legislation with respect to mining is the Planning Act 2008 (Ch. 29) of 26.11.08 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/uk89714.pdf>), which is amended by the Environment Act 2021 (Ch. 30) of 09.11.21 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/uk209376.pdf>), and the Environmental Assessments and Miscellaneous Planning (Amendment) (EU Exit) Regulations 2018 (S.I. No. 1232 of 2018) of 08.11.18 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/uk181928.pdf>). The latter addresses in particular regulatory issues arising from Brexit. Other relevant legislation includes the Water Act 2014 (Ch. 21) of 14.05.14 last amended on 19.08.18 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/uk143276.pdf>), and the Planning (Hazardous Substances) Act 1990 (c. 10) of 24.05.90 last amended on 22.07.20 (<https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/uk75905.pdf>).